

Celebrating the Phaistos Disc: A Decipherment in Mycenaean Transcription and Greek Translation

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On the 10th anniversary of my personal “discovery” of the Phaistos Disc

a-k^ha-i.ja e-zu wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo a-k^ha-i.ja.
te-sa-i e-zu-ki-jo ki-ko-ro sa-pe-ku-ta ka-ku-pte-ze-ka-ki-jo.
ko-ro-ki-jo e-o ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo.
ko-ro-ki-jo tu-ke wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo.
ko-ro-ki-jo e-o ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo to-re.
a-tu-pte-ki-jo ko-pi-me-e.
te-sa-me-ki-jo te-ko-ro ku-ta-ki-jo ke-lu-ka ki-ko-ri.ja-ka ke-pi-k^ho-ki-jo de-ma-ma.
ko-ri.ja-ma ki-pi-ta.
ku-e-zu-ki-jo.

ko-ri.ja mu-i-de-ma ko-i-te-ta-jo ko-ku-re-u-ti.
ke²-ko-ra-ma-no ta-ku-tu-ko.
ko-ri.ja-ko te-ku-ko mu-i-de-ka.
ke²-ko-ra-ma-no.
ko-ri.ja-ma zu-ke²-ma.
ke²-ko-ra-ma e-ka-ti-jo ke-re-pte-te-ta e-ke-ma ku-ze-to te-po-ta-ta-ma e-a-mu-ka.
pi-ra-ko-jo te-pi-ta-ko mu-ri-na-no.
ku-e-zu-ko-te² ke-re-e-zu.
a-ku-tu-to ki-po-ta-ke ka-mu-no u-tu-na-jo te-ko-ri-ja-ka ko-pi-no-ki-jo.

A *kopis* festival in Achaean-occupied Laconia, perhaps predating the cults of Hyakinthos and Apollo.

“[E]ach correct decipherment eventually ends up being recognized for its true value.”
Consequently, decipherer and decipherment “will triumph in the end over all competitors and critics.”¹

The discovery of the Phaistos disc

It is well established that, in July 1908, the Phaistos disc (PHd),² measuring 17 cm. (6.67”) across,³ was discovered during a routine inspection by a foreman on Luigi Pernier’s archaeological team at Phaistos. Both the disc and PH 1, a Linear A tablet, were found among ashes and earth approximately 20” above the depository floor of Room 8, Building 101, in the NE complex.⁴ Evidence *seems* to suggest that the upper floor collapsed during an earthquake, perhaps associated with the first of two volcanic eruptions, marking the transition (ca. 1700 BCE) between Middle Minoan periods II (Proto-Palatial) and III (Neo-

¹ Duhoux (2000) 598.

² In contravention to the established use of PhD for *Phaistos Disc*, I have elected to use PHd, to not only avoid ambiguity but to also remain consistent with the conventional, tablet reference of PH for *Phaistos*. I wish to downgrade *Phaistos Disc* from a title to a general reference, with a small *d*, to allow room for a new title upon successful decipherment and translation.

³ *SMI* (1909) 23.

⁴ Baldacci (2021).

Palatial). Eisenberg states that “[m]ost scholars agree with Pernier that [the disc] was made c. 1600-1700 B.C. It should be noted also that the room contained several Middle Minoan IIIB vases that date c. 1650-1600 BC.”⁵ According to Pendlebury, the comparatively “new type” of Cretan hieroglyphs, as represented in seals, did not survive beyond MMII, presumably providing a firm criterion for dating.⁶ Whether the PHd signary is to be included among these hieroglyphs, especially for the purpose of dating, has yet to be determined by a successful decipherment.

And, yet, in an effort to preserve its integrity, the disc has been shielded from typically destructive, archaeometric analysis,⁷ thus limiting its dating to that of its findspot. Unfortunately, this understandable effort to preserve prevents more accurate dating of an artifact that, despite the circumstantial evidence of its discovery, may have been more recently deposited prior to a belated collapse of an older ruin. I argue for the disc’s later creation and, perhaps, an incidental association with PH 1 and the Minoan vases. At the moment, support for this hypothesis is limited to implied, historical context.

Using stamps comprising metal, wood, or perhaps clay, the “scribe”, or author, impressed, in a spiral pattern on both sides of the fired, clay disc, 241, unambiguous, “tokens” comprising 45 signs. The 242nd token, in initial position at A-24 in a left-to-right (sinistroverse) reading, appears to have been erased.

Field dividers delineate 31 sign groups on “side A” and 30 sign groups on “side B”, as established by Evans.⁸ Of these 61, sign groups, 52 are unique. Reading direction, phonetic values, and language are disputed in absence of an attested solution.

While Evans’ establishment of sides A and B is arbitrary, evidence suggests that this establishment is correct. Reading from center to periphery, the sign groups on sides A and B are accordingly numbered.

A question of authenticity or hoax

To some, the Phaistos disc falls into the “too good to be true” category, presumably because Dr. Pernier felt compelled to “outdo” Federico Halbherr at Gortyna and Arthur Evans at Knossos “by making a discovery that would astound the archaeological community”.⁹ In this regard, the Phaistos disc joins the company of other controversial discoveries, such as the Bernstorff amber, the Kafkania pebble, and the Psychro inscription. The credibility of such discoveries is called into question, often for lack of obvious parallels in the historical record. Apparently, no discovery is allowed to bask in unprecedented glory and must at all times be preceded by authenticating evidence. Rather than viewing these maverick discoveries as opportunities to expand our knowledge, we treat them with suspicion. To hastily declare a discovery a forgery, as does Eisenberg,¹⁰ is to close one’s mind to a novel artifact that may potentially expand the holograph of history.

To make a convincing case for forgery, a scholar must be able to prove the availability of all relevant, archaeological models at the time of an artifact’s creation. Thus, regarding the question of the Phaistos disc, Baldacci makes a single, compelling argument for its authenticity: Any presumed forger of the Phaistos disc would not have had the benefit of relevant fine-ware motifs, which would not be discovered on site until 1955, nearly 50 years later.¹¹

Impressions of stamps stylistically very similar to the ones impressed on the Phaistos disc are common on the walls of MM IIA/B Phaistian pots, and they constitute the most important piece of evidence in support of the belief that the Phaistos disc is a MM IIB/IIIA artifact manufactured in Phaistos.¹²

⁵ Eisenberg (2008) 11.

⁶ Pendlebury (1939) 140.

⁷ Anastasiadou (2019) 211.

⁸ *SMI* (1909) 280-282.

⁹ Eisenberg (2008) 10.

¹⁰ *Ibid.* (2008 and 2008, *Addenda*).

¹¹ Baldacci (2017) 74, as regards PHd *21; Sanavia (2017) 96.

¹² Anastasiadou (2019) 212.

An argument for “a Cretan object of foreign origin”

My personal “discovery” of the Phaistos disc on January 6, 2013 was followed by an entry in my decipherment log: “Noted, in Cotterell (1979:78), the belief that the Phaistos disc is Carian, per the feathered headdress and round shield.”¹³ I tended to agree with assertions that the disc was imported¹⁴ and idly considered Carian as the underlying language. Following brief research into crested-helmet styles, my interest ended until August 2020, when it was renewed with the publication of Anastasiadou’s argument for the disc as a Cretan object.

Anastasiadou makes stylistic comparisons between PHd impressions and the “compartmented, stamp seals” comprising copper or bronze and dated to “the late-third and early-second millennium in the Bactria-Margiana region and the Sistan area of the Iranian Plateau.” In her opinion, “these excellent parallels constitute very strong evidence that the Phaistos Disc stamps were made of metal and looked very similar to these eastern stamps as opposed to [the] wood that [Thomas] Berres suggests.”¹⁵ The Phaistos palace overlooks the Western Messara plain and is one of three principle sites – along with Hagia Triada and Kommos – that constitute the Minoan Triangle.

Anastasiadou further states that, “[w]hile the form of a clay disc impressed by stamps is not (yet) paralleled in Minoan Crete, the elements from which the artefact is put together and the specific way in which they are combined are typical of the MM II/III Messarian culture.”¹⁶ For the sake of comparison, the closest parallel to the stamped, Phaistos disc is the heart-shaped, Magliano disc, discovered in Magliano, Tuscany in 1882. This disc comprises lead and is incised with Etruscan characters.

Sanavia takes Anastasiadou’s argument to the next level, with his documentation of similar, stamp impressions found on fine ware, especially at Phaistos.¹⁷ Some impressions have clear parallels on the Phaistos disk whereas others simply compel thematic comparison. These parallels and comparisons will be noted in the sign analyses.

While these arguments make a compelling case for the disc as a Cretan object, Glotz’s counter-argument is equally compelling: “No one knows [whence or how the disc came]; but it is certain that there is nothing Cretan about it. The [fine] clay is not of the island.”¹⁸

Yet, evidence suggests that as high as 50% of the PHd signary may find correspondence among the linear-script syllabaries. Moreover, at least five, PHd signs, or 11%, have direct parallels among fine-ware motifs and potters’ marks: rather impressive for a signary presumed to have no known parallels. I now believe that the disc was written in an alternate form, or dialect, of Mycenaean Greek. Stawell lends support:

“On my view, there was nothing to prevent the language of the Disk from being Greek, and, indeed, Ionian Greek of the same, general type as the Minoan, but the system would have been developed by a different *tribe*, standing to the Minoans, we might say, much as Ulysses stood to the Phaeacians or Theseus to Ariadne.”¹⁹

Faucounau concurs with his proposal of the proto-Ionian dialect.²⁰

States Duhoux, “Greek is the language most often proposed, and I should be quite happy should the disc turn out to have been written in that language. But is it possible?”²¹ In Duhoux’s view, apparently not. Among Duhoux’s criticisms of Faucounau’s mixed syllabary is that it comprises alphabetic consonants and CCV syllables in addition to V and VC syllables. This tendency, which can include CV

¹³ Leonhardt (2011-13) January 15, 2013.

¹⁴ Pendlebury (1939) 141, 170; Ventris (1940) 497; Cotterell (1979) 78.

¹⁵ Anastasiadou (2019) 213; see images in Sanavia (2017) 97, figs. 27 and 28.

¹⁶ Anastasiadou (2016) 34.

¹⁷ Sanavia (2017).

¹⁸ Glotz (1923) 381.

¹⁹ Stawell (1931) 57.

²⁰ Faucounau (1999) 12.

²¹ Duhoux (2000) 598, Faucounou (1999)

syllables and numerous logograms, is found among other would-be decipherers.²² Ultimately, the Phaistos disc “should correlate less with the language of Linear B, Greek, and more with the language of Linear A”,²³ a reasonable assumption, given its association with a Linear A tablet.

However, Anastasiadou emphasizes Berres’ caution:

“To the very important question of whether the script on the Disc can be deciphered on the basis of Linear A, [Berres] suggests that only frequency analysis may provide an answer. If it is proven by this type of analysis that at least four words occurring in Linear A also occur on the Disc, then a firmer foundation for exploring such a possibility further will be available. Every possible result needs, however, to always be subjected to control mechanisms.”²⁴

Perhaps Duhoux will find the “Greek hypothesis” more palatable with a high correspondence between PHd sign groups and both Linear B and the Greek language. In the substitution of Linear B for Duhoux’s Linear A, Berres’ low bar of “at least four words” is easily exceeded, as demonstrated by the *PHd Lexicon* that follows decipherment (see *Table 1*, pp. 54-56).

Reading direction and stamping “peculiarities”

In any decipherment, which emerge(s) first: the phonetic values or the language? The answer is that they simultaneously emerge in a linguistic dance of sound and meaning, which are founded upon a correct assumption about reading direction.

No matter the argument for any language, the scholar will find support for its reading direction in the orientation of the living figures represented on the disc. Glotz states that the direction of Cretan writing

“runs from left to right, sometimes returning from right to left (boustrophedon), and presents the figures of living beings with their back[s] to the reader, whereas the writing of the Egyptians runs from right to left, like those of the Babylonians, Hittites, and Semites, and presents the figures with their face[s] to the reader.”²⁵

Evans uses the right-facing orientation of the animate signs to justify his left-to-right (sinistroverse or sinistrograde) numbering of sign groups from center to periphery. I retain this numbering for my own decipherment.

Glötz, following Evans, nevertheless argues for a non-Minoan source, and finds support in the “living beings with their face[s] to the reader.” He then proceeds to analyze the non-Minoan “types” and “forms” of the signs.²⁶ Pendlebury likewise offers his observations about the disc’s “un-Minoan” character:

“Except for a few chance resemblances, the characters have no relation with the Minoan script, the inscription seems to be read from right to left, and the human and animal figures face the beginning [as in the Egyptian system]. The human figures are definitely un-Minoan; the plumed head-dress [PHd *02] is reminiscent of that of the Peoples of the Sea, who 400 years later are shown on Egyptian monuments; the bow [PHd *11] is an Asiatic bow; the pagoda-like structure [PHd *24] resembles later Lykian architecture,²⁷ and we may safely assume an Anatolian origin for the disk even though nothing resembling it has as yet appeared in Asia Minor.”²⁸

²² Stawell (1931) 59, fig. 6; Achterberg *et al.* (2021) 30-71.

²³ Duhoux (2000) 599.

²⁴ Anastasiadou (2019) 219.

²⁵ Glötz (1923) 373.

²⁶ *Ibid.* 382.

²⁷ Thus far, in Lykian architecture, the pillar tomb bears the closest resemblance to this “pagoda-like structure”.

²⁸ Pendlebury (1939) 170.

While Pendlebury argues for the disc's dextroverse reading, he nevertheless provides an argument for sinistroverse. "At the very beginning of MM IIIa [ca. 1700 BCE], the old hieroglyphic script was abandoned in favour of an advanced form of linear script in which only about a third of the signs can be traced to their hieroglyphic originals." This script is always read from left to right and differs from the dextroverse, Egyptian system insofar as the living signs "never face the beginning." Moreover, Pendlebury confirms that signs were impressed upon bars, fiddle-shaped labels, and "nearly square" tablets.²⁹

Godart is among those scholars who also argue for a dextroverse reading, at least in part because "several peculiarities demonstrate that the disc was stamped from the exterior to the interior, with the exception of a few corrections made after impression."³⁰ However, by scholarly reckoning, the current tally of "a few corrections" equals 15: two noted by Alessandro Della Seta (1909), two by Ernst Grumach (1962), 10 by Jean-Paul Olivier (1973), and one by Godart (1995). Of the 15 proposals, the overstamped erasure at A-24 shows the most promise for easy detection, and is treated as an additional, sign group in the *PHd Lexicon*.

Momentarily disregarding arguments for either reading direction, it is conceivable that, notwithstanding the corrections, numerous attempts were needed to achieve effective spacing. Thus, the "unique" Phaistos disc may have been the only surviving attempt among numerous "artist's proofs", identical, perhaps, to Berres' "models".³¹

I would be remiss if I did not at least rule out the possibility of the Vladikavkaz disc as one such artist's proof. This missing, clay fragment, discovered in 1991 in the capital of the Russian Republic of North Ossetia-Alania, had previously been ruled a forgery and returned to its owner. It comprises 10 whole or partial fields containing crude approximations of the stamped signs of the Phaistos disc. While Eisenberg has published a reversed image of this fragment and dismisses it as a possible "forger's prototype for the disk or merely an [attempted copy of] the original forgery"³², I believe that it is more likely a careless recreation of the Phaistos disc. Whereas the "re-creator" appears to copy the sign order in various fields, the fields themselves do not faithfully follow PHd order. For example, A-08 is incised above A-30/31 rather than A-14, a "misprint" which provides reason enough for invalidation.

Note that, in Godart's publication, the photographic images of both sides of the Phaistos disc are reversed.³³ In light of Godart's preference for a dextroverse reading, it is unclear whether this reversal is intentional or accidental. However, given that the images of individual sign groups, in subsequent analyses, are true to the original orientation, the former may simply be inadvertent. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the sign groups featured in Godart's analysis have been renumbered in reverse order to reflect a dextroverse reading.³⁴ Despite any disagreement regarding reading direction, Godart's enlarged images are recommended for their sharp detail, especially when examining corrections.

Ultimately, however, to those who argue for a Minoan provenance, as does Duhoux, there is no reason to believe that the transition to an "advanced form of linear script" necessitated a change in reading direction, from the presumed, dextroverse reading on the disc to a sinistroverse reading in the Linear A tablets.

Allography and polyvalence in the use of motif stamps and potters' marks

Baldacci ponders the placement of the "unique" Phaistos disc in archaeological context:

"Given the existence of other classes of materials with similar signs, namely the Phaistian potters' marks and impressed ware, the Disc seems to fit into the cultural context of Phaistos during the transition from the Protopalatial to the Neopalatial period. The use of writing was well

²⁹ *Ibid.* 141, 168.

³⁰ Duhoux (2000) 597.

³¹ Anastasiadou (2019) 214.

³² Eisenberg (2008, *Addenda*) 14.

³³ Godart (1995) 58-59.

³⁴ *Ibid.* 63-85; 98-107.

known at Phaistos, but the Disc fits also into the skilled artisanal context of local, ceramics manufacture. . . . Moreover, it fits into contemporary sealing practices, involving the impression of designs by stamping devices. While the message itself remains unclear to us, the Disc would not have been unique to those who viewed it. That is a useful starting point for any new consideration of its message and meaning.”³⁵

In any case, Baldacci’s “new consideration” must admit at least three, possible hindrances to decipherment. The first hindrance arises in a limited signary, such as that which may be represented by the short text of the Phaistos disc. Duhoux observes that “the disc, with 45 different signs, more closely approximates Cypriot, with 40-45 different signs (and a total syllabary of 56 signs), than Linear B, with 50-53 different signs (and a syllabary of 89 signs).”³⁶

Conversely, in the combined signaries for both LA and LB, approximately 750 signs and their presumed variations have been documented.³⁷ And, yet, disregarding ligatures, the known, or surmised, phonetic values of these signs constitute a small fraction of the corpus. Consequently, an expectation of phonetic overlap is reasonable.

Thus arises a second hindrance in the use of *allographs*, or ‘other signs’ with the same, phonetic value. According to Fuls, Mayan, hieroglyphic writing employs at least 13 allographs for the syllable, /u/.”³⁸ As for the Phaistos disc, Stawell seems undaunted in her proposal of at least five pairs of allographs.³⁹

Returning to the problem of a limited signary, a third hindrance arises in the use of *polyvalence*, or the assignment of alternate values for the same sign. Fuls highlights the Akkadian language, which had assigned new, phonetic values to Sumerian cuneiform without changing their meanings. Thus, DINGIR had three functions and five values: 1) as logograms for both ‘goddess’ and ‘heaven, sky’, 2) as a determinative for ‘deity’, and 3) as the syllabic sign for both AN and IL.⁴⁰

Duhoux is nevertheless suspicious of such irregularities: “A decipherment should be internally coherent, with few irregularities, and should make plausible sense. To argue (as some have done) that certain signs have variable phonetic readings is suspect.”⁴¹

Disregarding Duhoux, what if the disc’s author simply exercised his creative license with an existing repertoire of fine-ware motifs and potters’ marks, conceivably both redundant and inadequate? In such case, why must this ancient author be limited by contemporary sensibilities? Thus, I am compelled to admit the possibilities of both allography (different signs for the same value) and polyvalence (different values for the same sign): “I can use these stamps for this syllable, and this stamp, with two names, will work for these syllables. Any literate person will know what I mean.”

A coherent, decipherment process

The natural tendency, when deciphering signs in pictorial scripts, is to turn to the controversial, acrophonic principle to establish phonetic values. Duhoux argues that “[t]he acrophonic principle (e.g. a picture of a dog stands for the sound *d* or *do*) is an admirable means of arriving at a suspect decipherment. It often turns out that the interpretation of the object said to be depicted by the sign is arguable.”⁴²

We certainly can agree that many such interpretations are arguable. And, yet, given that written language is founded upon pictures, to initially convey ideas and to subsequently convey sounds, I do not see a more reasonable alternative to the acrophonic approach. When multiple, acrophonic interpretations

³⁵ Baldacci (2021).

³⁶ Duhoux (2000) 599.

³⁷ Douros, G. The current, internet resource for *Unicode Fonts for Ancient Scripts > Aegean* may be found at <dn-works.com/ufas/>. However, the comprehensive corpus (PDF) of Linear A, Linear B and Arcado-Cypriot signs, embodied first in *Aegean600* and then in *Aegean615*, appears to be no longer available. I was able to download this corpus in 2012, but am unable to find it under any, new title.

³⁸ *Ibid.*

³⁹ Stawell (1931) 58-59, figs. 6 and 7, *Phaestos Signs*, which she numbers in order of acrophonic assignment.

⁴⁰ Fuls (2019) 7.

⁴¹ Duhoux (2000) 598.

⁴² *Ibid.*; Fuls (2019) 37.

are possible, even in an assumed language, success obviously requires the correct option. For example, PHd *05 appears to depict a naked boy, a *hapax* occurrence in word-initial position in B-28. Assuming Greek, does PHd *05 depict κούρος (KO) ‘a boy’, or νήπιος (NE), παῖς (PA), or υἱός (U) ‘a child’? So, by all means, proceed with an open mind tempered by caution. A decipherer’s successful argument for his interpretation is largely founded upon his ability to present a coherent translation that does not strain the limits of credulity.

One lament regarding Michael Ventris’ process is that his work-notes lack “the mental gymnastics or the intuitive leaps” that lead to their creation; that, “despite his best efforts, Ventris was unable to produce a coherent narrative of his method.”⁴³ This difficulty is hardly surprising, given the multi-tracked nature of decipherment, where derailed trains of thought constitute the rule rather than the exception, where backtracks and sidetracks are frequent, and where revelations are tantamount to arrivals. The entire, non-linear process⁴⁴ defies coherence. Consequently, I have largely abandoned any attempt to offer a chronological account of my process and have elected, instead, to methodically build my decipherment in order of numerical assignment, from PHd *01 to *45, and to consolidate numerous trains of thought into one, coherent itinerary.

The endeavor of this decipherment implies disagreement with previous, decipherment attempts. Nevertheless, to strengthen my own arguments, I have mined those attempts for points of consensus, which I include under an *Attestation* section, an acknowledgement that “it takes a community of scholars to decipher and to translate the Phaistos disc.”

The sign groups, within each of the 45 grids, shall be presented according to the following hierarchy:

1. by the featured sign’s placement in initial, medial, and final positions;
2. by the number of signs within each group; and
3. by the numerical assignments of adjacent signs.

In groups that comprise redundant signs (e.g. 07-45-07), the hierarchy shall be followed for each occurrence; thus, three, sign groups (A-15, A-28, and B-07) will be featured twice in their relevant grids.

In each of eight pairs of allographs, the secondary (i.e. less frequent) syllable shall be distinguished with a super-script numeral (e.g. PHd *38 A and PHd *43 A²).

For each, completed, sign group, the alternate values of any polyvalent sign shall be included for the sake of comparison. The preferred choice shall be indicated in black, whereas the lesser choice shall be indicated in red.

Moreover, each sign group shall be featured multiple times until transliteration is completed. For example, 33-39-01 is consecutively featured under PHd *01, *33, and *39. Moreover, readers may skip ahead to the highest, numerical assignment to read a completed transliteration; thus, the completed transliteration of 33-39-01 may be found under PHd *39.

Patterns among sign groups shall be highlighted to enhance analysis.

While each, sign grid is designed to assist scholars with both paradigmatic (i.e. sign-group) and frequency analyses, I have chosen to forego these approaches in favor of direct decipherment.

The *Notes* section may include references to the *Catalogue of Hieroglyphic Signs* (CHS) in *SMI*, 181-231 and the *Corpus Hieroglyphicarum Inscriptionum Cretae* (CHIC), in *Études crétoises*, No. 31.

My Japanese hypothesis

For awhile, I debated the wisdom of including in this paper my *Japanese hypothesis*, which postulates proto-Japanese as the underlying language of LA. My *arguments against inclusion* highlight a seemingly unnecessary layer of complexity in my attempts to justify my decipherment. The winning *arguments for inclusion* highlight the inescapability of both the foundation of my methodology and an ever-increasing body of evidence. My main consideration is whether I can include this evidence without losing focus.

⁴³ Robinson (2002) 81-82.

⁴⁴ Fuls (2019) 23.

Regarding the underlying language of Linear A and its influence upon Greek language and culture, my hypothesis ⁴⁵ proposes that, sometime following the volcanic eruption of Thera in 1450 BCE, the Minoans left Crete to settle elsewhere. Linguistic evidence suggests some settlement upon Cyprus. Around 1000 BCE, concurrent with the arrival of the highly advanced Yamato culture ⁴⁶, a contingent of the sea-loving Minoans sailed around the Sinai Peninsula, followed the southern coast of Asia, and entered Japan through the southern Ryukyu Islands (now Okinawa). The Minoans, with their deep appreciation for beauty, would have been enamored with the Japanese islands. Moreover, they would have found the climate agreeable, as both Crete and Tokyo, Japan, are roughly situated at latitude 35° N.

Moreover, concurrent with the discoveries of Minoan sites on Crete during the past century and beginning with Evans, there have been numerous, authoritative comparisons between the Minoan (Greek) and the Japanese cultures. It is true that, when viewed in singular context, each of these comparisons may be easily dismissed as little more than scholarly musing. It is also true that the cumulative weight of these musings foreshadows a convergence of evidence too great to be indefinitely ignored.

While I do not argue for a Linear A, or “Japanese”, foundation for the Phaistos disc, profound, mutual influence between LA and LB cannot be overlooked in a Mycenaean-Greek decipherment that recognizes signs common to both syllabaries. For those interested in linguistic comparisons between the linear scripts and the Japanese language, my article, entitled *Fifteen, Linear-Script Signs with Correspondences in Japanese Kanji and Hiragana*, may be found on Academia.edu.

A note about attestation

In the highly competitive race for a plausible decipherment, scholars will naturally grasp even the smallest support to validate their claims. While consensus is indeed a powerful tool for advancing an interpretation, it is no guarantee of accuracy. Consensus merely strengthens an argument for or against an interpretation and should never be regarded as definitive proof until sufficient data is in.

Like any self-respecting scholar, I cite consensus for highly debated interpretations. Yet, I am rarely in complete agreement with both interpretation and acrophonic assignment. Consequently, *Attestation* for any sign may include either consensus of meaning or consensus of acrophone or both.

A final note about image quality

While all signs have been impressed in the clay, the relationship between light and shadow may be distorted as the disc image is turned to ensure the correct orientation of some signs. Moreover, to enhance image detail, the “noise” of irrelevant, adjacent details has largely been reduced or eliminated.

The Decipherment of the Phaistos Disc

The “walking (or running) man” appears to be wearing the iconic dress of the Minoan or Cretan male, who, perhaps, represents the author of this disc.

My immediate impression is that this action exemplifies both ἔξω and ἔρχομαι, which appear to be related to εἶκω ‘to give way, to yield; to retire from’ < > εἰκῆ ‘without plan or purpose, at random, at a venture’. Moreover, ἔρχομαι is,

perhaps, *ἔξομαι with epenthetic R.

ἔξω ‘out’ or ‘out of’, prob. > ἔρχομαι ‘to set out, to walk; to go or to come’ > B *046 JE

⁴⁵ Leonhardt (2018) 1.

⁴⁶ Munro (1908) 4-5.

Orientation: Walking right.

Attestation:

Manning (2009: 1, #1): “Some scholars compare this ‘running man’ sign to AB46 (je/ye), a sign that appears in only six, sign groups in Linear A.”

Owens (2014: 4, in Younger): “AB 46 JE”

Notes: Perhaps CHS #1.

Grid 1: E													
A-02								01	13				
1								e					
A-11								01	28				
A-17								01	28				
2-3								e					
B-16								01	33	29			
4								e					
A-06								01	13	12	02		
5								e					
B-14								01	27	09	02		
6								e					
B-19								01	38	25	27		
7								e					
B-23							18	01	13	07	15		
8								e					
A-31							18	01	13	12	02		
9								e					
B-24						33	39	01					
10								e					
A-21					07	40	41	01					
11								e					

PHd *02 JO
for IO

Noting the prolific pairs, *02-*12 or *12-*02, I continue with PHd *02, which Evans describes as the “[h]ead of a man in a close-fitting, crested helmet.”⁴⁷ A corollary to my helmet research is an association between PHd *02 and B *36 JO, which is confirmed in the linear depiction of the crest and in both the curve and the angle of an Ionian warrior’s head.

Ἴων ‘an Ionian’ (warrior) > B *036 JO for IO.

Cf. LB *i-ja-wo-ne* [KN B- 164] > Ἴωνες, or Ἰάονες, ‘Ionians’. Beekes states that, “[a]s the proper meaning is unknown, the name remains without a clear etymology.”⁴⁸ Nevertheless, an association with the Egyp. *jwn*, ‘column, pillar; tree trunk’ has gained universal acceptance. From *jwn* arises *jwt* ‘a kind of bow’ > *jwtj* > ‘archer, Bowman’, pl. *jwtjw* ‘Bowmen’. *Cf.* ἰά, pl. of ἰός, ‘arrow’. See PHd *10, the “arrow shaft” sign, for further discussion.

Also worth noting is Boeot. ἰών, ἰώνγα for first-person pronoun ἐγώ, ἐγώγε. Moreover, *cf.* Boeot. ἰώνει. as well as Ἰωνία ‘Ionia’, for Lacon. ἐγώνη.

Ἴωνες δὲ ὅσον μὲν χρόνον ἐν Πελοποννήσῳ οἴκειον τὴν νῦν καλεομένην Ἀχαιίην, καὶ πρὶν ἢ Δαναόν τε καὶ Εὐϋθὸν ἀπικέσθαι ἐς Πελοπόννησον, ὡς Ἕλληνες λέγουσι, ἐκαλέοντο Πελασγοὶ Αἰγιαλέες, ἐπὶ δὲ Ἴωνος τοῦ Εὐϋθου Ἴωνες.⁴⁹

These Ionians, as long as they were in the Peloponnesus, dwelt in what is now called Achaea, and before Danaus and Xuthus came to the Peloponnesus, as the Greeks say, they were called Aegialian Pelasgians. They were named Ionians after Ion, the son of Xuthus.

If one argues for a sinistroverse reading of the disc, JO is exclusively found in word-final position – 19 times in 61 sign groups – for an approximate, PHd frequency of 31%. Among those who argue for a dextroverse reading, Timm compares “frequent, end signs” on the Phaistos disc with those in the linear scripts.⁵⁰ Thus, his analysis does not associate “initial” PHd *02 with “final” AB *36 JO, which enjoys the highest, LB frequency of 10% among unique, sign groups. *Cf.* AB *02 RO, which enjoys the next highest, LB frequency of 5%.

Orientation: Facing right, alternately facing downward.

Cross References: PHd *10, the “arrow-shaft” sign; *a-k^ha-i.ja* [A-01] in *Translation*, below

Notes: A crude version of this sign may be found on the Archalokori axe.

Grid 2: JO												
A-06					01	13	12	02				
1					e			jo				

⁴⁷ *SMI* (1909) 275, #2.

⁴⁸ Beekes (2010) *s.v.* Ἴωνες, 608-9.

⁴⁹ Hdt.7.94. (trans. A.D. Godley, 1920)

⁵⁰ Timm (2008) Table 1.

B-14				1	27	09	02												
2				e			jo												
B-28				05	23	37	02												
3							jo												
A-24				18	06	12	02												
4							jo												
A-10				26	31	12	02												
A-13				26	31	12	02												
A-16				26	31	12	02												
5-7							jo												
A-20				40	32	26	02												
8							jo												
B-03			07	23	35	06	02												
9							jo												
B-30			07	40	22	12	02												
10							jo												
A-31			18	01	13	12	02												
11				e			jo												
A-27			33	40	04	12	02												
12							jo												
A-22			35	19	41	12	02												
13							jo												
A-20			38	23	32	12	02												
14							jo												
A-12			18	23	10	25	27	02											
A-18			18	23	10	25	27	02											
15-16							jo												
A-03		21	37	35	27	27	12	02											
A-15		21	37	35	27	27	12	02											
17-18							jo												
A-09		27	18	32	14	27	12	02											
19							jo												

PHd *03 K^hA

PHd *03 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

Evans notes that “an 8-shaped mark is visible on the cheek” of the bald-headed man depicted in PHd *03.⁵¹ Anastasiadou concurs that the tattoo is similar to that borne by “a Keftiu man on a wall painting in the tomb of Rechmire”. Moreover, “the eight-shaped element on the

Rechmire tomb figure [denotes] a Minoan, gift bringer [and] is a neat attestation to the fact that the facial eight-shaped, jewel/tattoo was an inherently Minoan custom.” Anastasiadou concludes that “the Phaistos disc, which features the first known depiction of such a feature, was created by Minoans.”⁵²

Although I am disinclined to agree with her belief that the disc is a Minoan creation, which implies an association with Linear A, Anastasiadou’s observation has compelled a comparison with the Minoan, figure-eight shields and ultimately with the snake, a prominent symbol in Minoan culture via the Snake Goddess and, perhaps, Cybele (see PHd *34). In some depictions of *ouroboros* – a symbol of eternal, cyclical renewal – the snake is twisted into a figure eight, which may linguistically be compared with ∞ ‘eternity’ in the Germanic languages: Ger. *Ewigkeit*, Dut. *eeuwigheid*, Dan. *evighed*, and Nor. and Swed. *evighet*. Cf., also, *ether*.

Attis was a consort of Cybele and is sometimes associated with snake handling. It is possible that Attis is an alternate name for *Sabazios*, a Phrygian diety, associated with Cybele and certainly known for snake handling. These associations are worth further research, which will not be undertaken here. For scholars who are intrigued by these implications, I recommend “Attis on Greek Votive Monuments: Greek God or Phrygian?” by Lynn Roller.

I have long pondered a possible association between Attis and Attika, via the K^hattic (*aka* Hattic) people. At the very least, however, I feel confident in an association between the Minoans and the K^hatti, as confirmed by Maspero.

In 1903, around the time that Sir Arthur Evans was in London, exhibiting his archaeological finds, Maspero’s *History of Egypt* was going to press. In Book V, Maspero describes in detail the male characteristics of the K^hatti, as described by the Egyptians. For example, the clean-shaven men grew their hair, which they “divided into two or three locks”. Moreover, they wore thick-soled shoes “turning up distinctly at the toes”,⁵³ similar to the footwear worn by the Minoans.⁵⁴ In his Mid-Century Report to Ventris, Caratelli makes numerous, linguistic comparisons between the Minoans and the K^hatti.⁵⁵ Other scholars have similarly explored a Minoan/K^hattian association.⁵⁶

Moreover, I believe that the Japanese people are culturally related to the K^hattians, via the Minoans, principally from the merchant colony of Karum Kanesh in central Anatolia. In *Nihon-go*, ‘Japanese language’, *Hatti* (K^hatti) would be pronounced *hachi* ‘eight’, an echo of the facial tattoo, the figure-eight shield, and Cybele, the snake goddess. In Japanese mythology, 八岐大蛇 *Yamata no Orochi*, or *Orochi*, is the eight-headed and eight-tailed dragon. Speculation about the etymology of *oroichi* considers O. Jap. 尾 *worö* ‘tail’ with a regular shift to *oro*. Cf. οὐροβόρος *ouroboros* ‘the tail eater’, from οὐρά, Ion. οὐρή ‘tail’ (akin to ὄππος ‘rump’) + βopός ‘gluttonous’.

⁵¹ *SMI* (1909) 275, #3.

⁵² Anastasiadou (2016) 36-37, fig. 18.

⁵³ Maspero (1903) Vol. V, 133-140.

⁵⁴ Hood (1971) 98.

⁵⁵ Carratelli in Ventris (1988) 51.

⁵⁶ Akulov (2016) 28: The language “of the [Phaistos] disc has reduplication of root and well elaborated prefixation; it means that Minoan can probably be relative of Anatolian languages, or Hattic, or Sumerian (languages which also have well elaborated prefixation)”; Revesz (2017) 306: “The Hattic language is generally considered to be a language isolate. Hence, some form of Proto-Hattic seems to be a likely source of Minoan, because it fits well with the known data”; Schrijver (2019) 336: “It is argued that the Minoan language of second-millennium BC Crete stands a good chance of being descended from the language that was imported into Crete by the earliest farmers that colonized the Island in the 7th millennium BC. Evidence is presented that links Minoan to the Hattic language of second-millennium BC northern Anatolia.”

If attested, then PHd *03 K^hA and *02 JO quite possibly signify an alliance between the K^hattians of Linear A and the Ionians of Linear B.

K^hattian, Keftiu, Minoan > > K^hA

Orientation: Facing right.

Attestation:

SMI (1909:275, #3): “Head of a man depicted as bald or with a close-fitting cap. An 8-shaped mark is visible on the cheek. This, as Dr. Pernier has suggested, may indicate a tattoo mark or a painted ornament such as appears on certain Minoan figures.”

Anastasiadou (2016: 36-37, fig. 18): The figure-eight, facial tattoo is similar to that borne by “a Keftiu man on a wall painting in the tomb of Rechmire”.

Cross Reference: PHd *34 DE, re: Cybele

Grid 3: K ^h A														
A-01								38	03	10				
A-04								38	03	10				
1-2									k^ha					

PHd *04 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

Despite popular interpretation, I am unable to see a captive or a slave in the depiction of PHd *04, primarily because the ‘captive’, walking with one arm crossed in front of his body, is shackled in an awkward and impractical manner. Bound wrists are typically held, uncrossed, at either the front or the back of the body. Although Godart

concurr with Evans’ interpretation of a captive, he also notes that “captives depicted on the Egyptian monuments . . . have their hands tied behind the back. Certainly, this detail is not sufficient for us to link the image of sign 4 with Egypt, for, since time immemorial and among all peoples on earth, prisoners’ hands have been tied behind the back.”⁵⁷ Evans’ drawing “corrects” this sign, which was perhaps damaged by washing.

Although mutilation makes this sign difficult to scrutinize, I see the suggestion of the right leg crossed in front of the left leg, as though the figure were dancing.

χορευτής ‘choral dancer’ > > K^hO

Cf. the κούρητες, which, in Greek society, were ‘young men, *esp.* young warriors’, who developed military prowess through dances,⁵⁸ such as the Πυρρικός χορός ‘Pyrrhic dance’ and the Πεντοζάλι “Κρήτες” Ηρώδειο Ο χορός, also known as ‘the Cretan War Dance’. *Cf.* also LB *ko-re-te* [PY Jn 829+], which provides plausible foundation for Κρήτη ‘Crete’.

Orientation: Facing right.

Cross Reference: PHd *07 KO

⁵⁷ Godart (1995) 124.

⁵⁸ Lawler (1947) 344.

Grid 4: K^hO														
A-27							33	40	04	12	02			
1									k^ho		jo			

PHd *05 U

As previously stated, PHd *05 depicts a naked boy, a *hapax* occurrence on side B.

Of the four choices previously discussed – κοῦρος (KO), νήπιος (NA or NE), παῖς (PA), or υἰός (U) – the last one proves to be the best choice in context.

υἰός ‘a boy, a child; a son’ > > U

Orientation: Facing right.

Attestation:

SMI (1909: 275, #5): a “naked, male child”

Stawell (1931: 59, fig.7, #31): “Boy”, with a proposed value of PA, for παῖς ‘child’.

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *30 U².

Grid 5: U														
B-28									05	23	37	02		
1									u			jo		

PHd *06 TA

Although “[t]he whole aspect of [PHd *06] contrasts with Minoan /Mycenaean types,”⁵⁹ the depicted woman appears to be wearing a flounced skirt, characteristic of the apparel worn by Minoan women. Furthermore, regarding the association between TA and ‘woman’, Evans observes that AB *01 DA is often written above AB *59 TA and that either or both signs may be followed by B *102 MUL, “the

‘woman’ sign”.⁶⁰

In LB, *cf.* AB *59 TA in word-final position, with an approximate frequency of 4% among unique, sign groups. Moreover, the pair, *ta-jo*, occurs 19 times in LB, whereas the inflected *-ta-jo-jo* occurs in three of those 19 words.

‘a woman, a priestess’ > > TA

Orientation: Facing right

⁵⁹ Glotz (1923) 275.

⁶⁰ *SM2*, 9, AB14.

Attestation:

Stawell (1931:58, Fig. 6, #6): “Woman”, with a proposed value of GU, for γῦνή ‘woman’.
Faucounau (1999:11 #6): “signe 6 ‘femme’ TA/DA”

La valeur phonétique incite a y voir l'equivalent proto-ionien d l'hom δαμαρ: ‘femme marié e’, ‘épouse’, plutôt que d’y chercher le nom de quelque déese (e.g. δαναη).

The phonetic value encourages us to see in it the proto-Ionian equivalent of the l’hom δαμαρ: ‘married woman’, ‘wife’, rather than to look for the name of some goddess (e.g. Daphne).

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *24 TA².

Notes: Cf. a similar, fine-ware motif, found principally at Phaistos.⁶¹

Grid 6: TA														
A-24							18	06	12	02				
1								ta		jo				
B-03					07	23	35	06	02					
2								ta	jo					
A-08					19	17	18	06						
3								ta						
B-15					33	39	32	35	06					
4								ta						

PHd *07 KO

Beginning with Evans, PHd *07 is popularly interpreted as a woman’s breast.⁶² Despite consensus, I was initially inclined toward an interpretation of κάρα or Ion. κάρη ‘peak’. Manning states that, although, “some scholars suggest that D#7 is a ‘helmet’,” he is “unaware of any Bronze Age examples of this type of helmet.”⁶³ And, yet, my own

continued research into helmet styles reveals a stylistically similar helmet with cheek and neck pieces included.⁶⁴ Eisenberg corroborates with a depiction of a boar’s-tusk helmet, also with cheek pieces.⁶⁵ Perhaps a κόρυς (χορός) was originally a line of helmeted warriors practicing war maneuvers in an “armed exercise”.⁶⁶

Cross References: PHd *04 K^hO; PHd *09 TI, for comparison with *tiara*.

κόρυς ‘helmet’ > KO

⁶¹ Sanavia (2017) 93, Fig 23.
⁶² *SMI* (1909) 275, #7.
⁶³ Manning (2009) 5, #7.
⁶⁴ *Docs*, 377, fig. 26E.
⁶⁵ Eisenberg (2008) 16, fig. 30.
⁶⁶ *Athen*. 14.25.

Orientation: Pointing upward

Attestation:

SMI (1909:275, #7) “I have taken this sign to represent a woman’s breast. Dr. Pernier would see in it a *pileus* or cap.”

Eisenberg (July 2008; 16, fig. 30) “Mycenaean relief of a boar’s tusk helmet. Cf. disk sign no. 7, the helmet.” In his *Addenda* (2008: 15), Eisenberg considers an alternate interpretation of “breast” of similar shape, which requires inversion and additional detail to transform the peak into a nipple.

Timm (2008): “breast” or “helmet”. Timm’s decipherment, nevertheless, favors ‘breast’.

Mosenkis (2021; 6, #7): “κόρυς gen. κόρυθος ‘helmet’.”

Surnin (2013: 50-54): “This image is identified by modern science as a helmet,” which is accompanied by four images of Cypriote figures or statuettes in helmets identical to PHd *07. However, despite his graphic evidence for “helmet”, Surnin, like Timm, favors “breast”, for a logographic value of “woman”.

Cross References: PHd K^hO and allograph PHd *26 KO²; PHd *09 TI.

Grid 7: KO												
B-17								07	45			
1								ko				
B-07								07	45	07		
2								ko		ko		
A-29								07	45	29		
B-11								07	45	29		
3-4								ko				
A-21								07	40	41	01	
5								ko			e	
B-04								07	18	39	30	09
6								ko				
B-03								07	23	35	06	02
7								ko			ta	jo
B-13							08	07	36	29		
8								ko				
B-05							08	07	36	29	22	
B-10							08	07	36	29	22	
9-10								ko				
A-26							12	07	45	27		
11								ko				
B-29							35	07	45	27		
12								ko				

B-07						07	45	07											
13						ko		ko											
B-08						35	18	07											
14								ko											
B-06						24	18	23	07										
15									ko										
B-21						35	40	24	07										
16									ko										
B-23						18	01	13	07	15									
17							e		ko										

PHd *08 KE²

κεστός is a “stitched (glove)”, comprising leather straps, worn by ancient boxers. Cf. L. *cestus*, with an ancient reference to a “woman’s belt or girdle”. Similarly, *casts*, for setting broken bones, comprise bandage strips hardened with plaster or Fiberglas.

Although the Minoan woman in PHd *06 is wearing a girdle, the association with *cestus* is reserved for PHd *08.

κεστός ‘stitched (glove)’ > > KE²

Attestation:

SMI (1909:276, #8): “Fist bound with *cestus*, like those of Minoan pugilists.”

Backstrom (1911, in Mosenkis, 6): “Boxer’s fist in *cestus* ‘boxing glove.’”

Mosenkis (2021: 6, #8) fist bound with *cestus* ‘boxing-glove’, ‘glove’ ”, with logographic value of “μειλίχη ‘boxing-glove’ = Μειλίχιος ‘gracious’ (epithet of Zeus and Dionysus).”

Cross References: allograph PHd *33 KE and PHd 06 TA²

Notes: Perhaps CHIC #09

Grid 8: KE²																			
A-25									08	44	27								
1									ke²										
B-13									08	07	36	29							
2									ke²	ko									
B-05									08	07	36	29	22						
B-10									08	07	36	29	22						
3									ke²	ko									

B-12								13	08	29							
4									ke²								

PHd *09 TI

While researching helmet styles for PHd *02, I also encountered the *tiara* worn by the Achaemenid archers of the first, Persian empire (550-330 BCE) and immediately compared this article to both PHd *09 and AB *037 TI. Following the Ventris decipherment, many concurrent interpretations have missed this acrophonic association. Nevertheless, in ancient sources, this iconic headgear was

“variously described as *tiara*, *kurbasia* or *kitaris*”.⁶⁷

The origin of the tiara is unclear, but identical headgear is featured on grave goods in Japan. During the 古墳 Kofun, or 方墳 *houfun*, ‘old tomb’ period (ca. 300-700 CE; cf. *coffin*), aristocratic burials in Japan were accompanied by 埴輪 *haniwa*, hollow, terracotta statues. The headgear on the horsemen include a *tiara* and a helmet with cheek pieces (see PHd *07 KO). A simple, internet search of *haniwa* images will demonstrate the variety of helmet styles featured on warrior statues.

τιάρα, τιάρας, or Ion. τήρης ‘*tiara*’ > TI

Attestation:

SMI (1909:277, #9): “This sign has every appearance of being a kind of *tiara*.”

Hempl (1911: 194): “*tiara*, τήρης”, with a proposed value of TI.

Stawell (1931:59, fig. 7, #41): “*Tiara*”, with a proposed value of TI, for τήρης, and an association with Arc.-Cyp. TI.

Faucounau (1999:11): “Sign 9: The most generally accepted meaning is that of ‘*tiara*’ or ‘Hittite bonnet’, prob. LI for λικμός or λίκνον.”

Achterberg *et al.* (2021:40) “crown or *tiara*”

Cross Reference: PHd *07 KO, for κóρυς ‘helmet’

Grid 9: TI																	
B-14								01	27	09	02						
1								e		ti	jo						
B-04					07	18	39	30	09								
2					ko				ti								

PHd *10 I.JA

Some interpret PHd *10 as a paddle, whereas others see the shaft of an arrow. Although sing. *iós* ‘arrow’ renders masculine IJO, I favor the feminine, plur. *ía* for I.JA, which appears to be supported in some depictions of B *025 A₂ (i.ja), suggesting an arrow nocked on a bowstring. Moreover, cf. Jap. 矢 *ya* ‘arrow’.

⁶⁷ Berndt Ersöz, S. (2020) 65.

Finally, one cannot help but to compare Ἴων ‘an Ionian’ (warrior) and ἰός ‘arrow’. Any question regarding the etymology of Ἴων may be resolved in an association between the Ionians and archery

ἰός, ‘arrow’ > B *025 A₂ (i.ja)

Attestation:

SMI (1909:279, #10): “The arrow sign in a more cursory form appears in the Minoan series.”

Stawell (1931: 59, fig. 7, #45; 67, no. 45): “arrow” for οἰστός.”, with a proposed value of O, which she associates with the Arc-Cyp. O.

Manning (2009:5, D#10): “Though D#10 looks like an ‘oar’, the striations on the ‘paddle’ area suggest that this is the feather end of an arrow.”

Cross References: PHd *02 JO, PHd *11 TO²

Notes: CHIC #50, which depicts the arrow point.

Grid 10: IJA														
A-01								38	03	10				
A-04								38	03	10				
1-2									k ^h a	i.ja				
A-12								18	23	10	25	27	02	
A-18								18	23	10	25	27	02	
3-4										i.ja			jo	

PHd *11 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

τόξον ‘a horned or Asiatic bow’ > > TO²

Attestation:

SMI (277, #11): a “horned or Asiatic bow . . . found in Crete”.

Hempl (1911: 194): “τόξον ‘bow’ ”, with a proposed value of TO.

Stawell (1931: 59, fig. 7, #42): “Bow”, with a proposed value of TO, for τόξον ‘bow’.

Pendlebury (1939: 141, 170): “an Asiatic bow”.

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *16 TO.

Grid 11: TO²													
A-19										11	39		
1										to²			

PHd *12 KI
for QE

In PHd *12, the sign preceding *02 JO, I am compelled to see the obvious parallel with AB *078 QE. However, despite Eisenberg’s compelling comparison with a Kadesh battle relief,⁶⁸ I disagree with the consensus that PHd *12 represents a round shield with a central boss and six, peripheral bosses.⁶⁹ This interpretation is problematic primarily due to the improbable number of “bosses” depicted within variations of the linear-script sign, with as few as one

and as many as 25. Three elements enjoy the greatest frequency, but four and five elements are also documented. In the majority of LA depictions, the random placement of the elements⁷⁰ precludes any interpretation of a manufactured item. Duhoux uses one such example in his table of sign correspondences.⁷¹ Moreover, in some, LB depictions, the “bosses” are linear.

I argue, instead, for a re-interpretation of both PHd *12 and AB *078 QE as an encompassed village, which broadly signifies its ‘place on earth’.⁷² Cf. QE with Ion. κη, a locative enclitic that means ‘anywhere, somewhere’⁷³; Aeol. κῆ and Att. ἐκεῖ ‘there, in that place’; and Att. γῆ and Aeol.-Dor. γᾶ for γαῖα ‘earth’. In LB, word-final *-qe* occurs in, perhaps, 130 words.

Moreover, the universality of the locative enclitic, κη, is underscored in the cuneiform texts of the Murašú Archive, principally found at Nippur (ca. fifth-century BCE): “The prepositive, determinative URU marks small settlements; the postpositive, determinative KI marks large towns and old cities”, as demonstrated in EN.LÍL.KI ‘Nippur’ and E.KI ‘Babylon’.⁷⁴ Moreover, in the “Mari documents” (ca. 18th century BCE), “*Kapitariyu*^{KI} is an understood reference to the Cretans or to Crete, itself.”⁷⁵

Fig. 1 suggests the evolution of Sumerian *KI*, beginning as early as 3000 BCE. In column B of his table

Sumerian KI 3000 2800 2500 BC	AB *78 QE Linear A Linear B	Japanese <i>ki</i>
<i>large town, old city</i>	proposed * <i>place;</i> <i>country, earth,</i> <i>ground, land</i>	<i>fortress</i> (<i>surrounded by a</i> <i>moat, a wall, etc.</i>)
Figure 1: Linear-script QE as Sumerian KI, and Japanese ki		

of Cretan pictographs, Evans includes both versions of this sign: the vertical, Sumerian sign and the circular, linear-script sign. Column B represents signs “inscribed on clay tablets & sealings”, whereas column A represents signs “engraved on signets”.⁷⁶ Cf. the fine-ware motif on the “teapot” vase, found at Knossos.⁷⁷

Consistent with the foregoing reinterpretation, I have assigned PHd *12 the phonetic value of KI in lieu of QE.

κη ‘anywhere, somewhere’ > AB * 078 QE > KI

⁶⁸ Eisenberg (2008) 16, Fig. 8.

⁶⁹ *SMI* (1909) 277.

⁷⁰ Raison and Pope (1972) 210, fig. 159.

⁷¹ Duhoux (1983) 34, [table] “Correspondances possibles entre signes du disque de Phaestos et du linéaire A”.

⁷² Leonhardt (2021) 2.

⁷³ TLG s.v. πού.

⁷⁴ Stolper (1992) 73.

⁷⁵ Leonhardt (2021) 3.

⁷⁶ *SMI* (1909) 232, fig. 102, #52B and #53B.

⁷⁷ Sanavia (2017) 95, fig. 25.

Attestation:

Duhoux (1983: 34, “Correspondances possibles entre signes”): “qe”

Owens (2014: 2, in Younger): “AB 78 QE”

Akulov (2016, 33, pic. 8: “Signs known through Linear A”): “QE

Notes: CHIC #52, #53

Grid 12: KI														
A-07									12	26	31			
1									ki					
A-30									12	40	24			
2									ki					
A-26									12	07	45	27		
3									ki	ko				
B-26									12	20	24	33		
4									ki					
A-06						01	13		12	02				
5						e			ki	jo				
A-24						18	06		12	02				
6							ta		ki	jo				
A-10						26	31		12	02				
A-13						26	31		12	02				
A-16						26	31		12	02				
7-9									ki	jo				
B-30						07	40	22	12	02				
10						ko			ki	jo				
A-31						18	01	13	12	02				
11							e		ki	jo				
A-27						33	40	04	12	02				
12								k ^h o	ki	jo				
A-20						38	23	32	12	02				
13									ki	jo				
A-03				21	37	35	27	27	12	02				
A-15				21	37	35	27	27	12	02				
14-15									ki	jo				

--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Beginning with Evans, the ubiquitous *12-*02 is popularly characterized as ‘a man with a crested helmet and a shield’⁷⁸ and presumed to be, in a dextroverse reading (*02-*12), a proclitic determinative for a class of people. Paraphrasing Berres, Anastasiadou observes the treatment of these signs, which are

“most often paired. . . . at the start of a word. They are very often the object of corrections, i.e. they tend to be forgotten in the initial inscription and added in the text at a later stage. This is an indication that on the level of the language they are so unimportant that they can be forgotten (they are probably not ‘heard’ in oral speech because the added meaning they provide is understood by the context) but in the level of the script they are important enough to be added. These signs may work together as a pair but also separately.”⁷⁹

In fact, *12 is exclusively paired with *02 in 11 sign groups, eight of which are unique. In four, additional, sign groups, *12 is the initial sign in a sinistroverse reading, as indicated in Grid 12, above.

My own preference for sinistroverse was initially more intuitive than rational; however, this preference is strengthened by my proposed decipherment of *12-*02, as *qe-jo*. In LB, however, the only instance of *qe-jo* occurs in *to-ro-qe-jo-me-no* [PY Eq 213] < τροχίος ‘round’. The closest phonetic parallel to suffix *qe-jo* is *ki-jo*, which occurs approximately 39 times in 11, unique words, the most prolific of which is *po-ni-ki-jo* in 25 occurrences.

Thus, dextroverse *jo-ki* (*02-*12) at the beginning of the word makes less sense than sinistroverse *ki-jo* (*12-*02) at the end of the word, especially when treated as a probable alternation of the LB suffix, *ti-jo*. On the Phaistos disc, the single instance of *ti-jo* (09-02) at B-14 is notable as a possible alternation of *ki-jo*. In LB, both *ki-jo* and *ti-jo* are also found in initial and medial positions.

Also, in LB, suffix *te-jo*, (60 occurrences) appears to be an alternation of *ti-jo* (92 occurrences). Unlike *ti-jo*, which seems never to stand alone, *te-jo* stands alone in at least two occurrences on the Knossos tablets [KN Dv 7617, KN L-565], thus compelling a comparison with Dor.-Ion. τεός and Boeot. τίος, for τις ‘anyone, anything’ and Dor. τίος, one of three genitives of σύ ‘thou’, which appears to strengthen Anastasiadou’s argument for implied elements in oral speech.

Indeed, I regard *ki-jo* the “key” to my decipherment. While the phonetic assignment of QE is sufficient for now in the LB signary, for the Phaistos disc, the assignment of KI is aligned with its broad use as an enclitic in LB and beyond.

While enclitic *ki-jo* may simply mark a noun, initial KI in four words potentially implies a different role, which will be addressed, following decipherment. See *The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc*.

Some scholars, after Evans, have associated PHd *13 with a knotted club, “such as that attributed to Hercules.”⁸⁰ I was also influenced by a comparison between PHd *13 and AB *79 ZU.

Although I am unable to find that reference for proper attribution, I have assigned ZU to PHd *13, based upon a rough, phonetic approximation to ξύλον. An assignment of KSU for ξύ is improbable for lack of results in the Greek lexicon. In the linear scripts, however, AB *79 ZU is more

prevalent in LA, occurring in 14 words, compared to just four words in LB.

⁷⁸ *SMI* (1909) 277, s.v. #12.

⁷⁹ Anastasiadou (2019) 213, as suggested by Berres.

⁸⁰ *SMI* (1909) 277, #13.

ξύλον ‘a cudgel, a club; a mace’ > AB *79 ZU

Attestation:

SMI (1909:277, #13): “This looks like a knotted club, such as that attributed to Hercules.”

Cross Reference: *e-zu* [A-02], in *Translation*.

Grid 13: KU														
B-12										13	08	29		
1										zu	ke ²			
A-02									01	13				
2									e	zu				
A-06									01	13	12	02		
3									e	zu	ki	jo		
A-31							18	01	13	12	02			
4									e	zu	ki	jo		
B-23							18	01	13	07	15			
5									e	zu	ko			
B-24						33	39	01	13					
6									e	zu				

Some scholars see a pair of breasts, whereas I and others see a yoke for a team of oxen. Likewise, Olmsted associates PHd *14 with Sans. *Śindu* “yoked team” and further with Heb. *shin* and Gr. *Σ sigma*

ξεύγος ‘yoke’ >

Attestation:

Hempl (2011:194): “yoke, ξεύγλη”, with a parallel value of ZE

Manning (2009:5, D#14): “This sign may be a depiction of a ‘yoke’ meant for a pair of oxen.”

Hoffman (2020): “yoke?”

Olmsted (2020: 3, chart 1, S#): “*Śindu*, yoked team”, associating the character with Heb. *shin* and Gr. *Σ sigma*.

Grid 14: ZE														
B-17								18	14	16				
1									ze					
A-09						27	18	32	14	27	12	02		
2									ze		ki	jo		

PHd *15 TE²
for DA/TA

PHd *15 is a *hapax* occurrence on side B.

Confirming the value of PHd *15 as AB *02 DA proved rather challenging, primarily because I was focused upon ‘axe’. Noting that Arcado-Cypriot lacks the D-series and that the sign for AB *01 DA equals Arc.-Cyp. TA, I received my first confirmation with τύκος ‘instrument for working stone, mason’s hammer or *pick*’ and ultimately with the generic τεῦχος ‘implement, a tool’. At the root of both words

is τεύχω ‘to make’. Cf. LB *te-u-ke-i-jo* > *τευχέω ‘to be armed’ [TH Av 106].⁸¹
Assigning the value of PHd *15 is somewhat arbitrary, since DA, TA, and TE are all plausible contenders. In some instances in LB, final DA shifts to τε or τη (e.g. *a-ko-i-da* > ἀκοίτη ‘bedfellow, husband’ [KN DI 943] and *sa-ma-da* > Σαμάτης or Σαρμάτης ‘Sarmatian’ [KN Np 267]).

τεῦχος ‘implement, tool’ > TA > TE² for DA/TA

Attestation:

SMI (1909:277, #15): “Pickaxe.”
Eisenberg (2008:16, Fig. 38; 18, #15) “Mattock or pick”, with a comparison to B *232 and a prism seal from Crete

Cross References: allograph PHd *35 TE.

Notes: CHS #12; CHIC #43

Grid 15: TE ²														
B-23					18	01	13	07	15					
1						e	zu	ko	te ²					

⁸¹ L&S 2nd, s.v. τευχέω and τετευχῆμαι, “an Ep. pf. pass with pres. signif. formed from the Subst. τευχέα, without any pres. in use.”

PHd *16 TO

Note that I have reversed the conventional direction of the Arc.-Cyp. TO for ease of comparison. AB *05 TO is still a possibility; however, the extended, second line makes an association dubious though not necessarily implausible.

Eisenberg compares this sign to AB *74 ZE and the Egyptian hieroglyph for *set*. Cf. ξεστός ‘hewn, shaved, planed’. Nevertheless, τομῖς ‘knife’ seems the more plausible choice, since, for the adjacent sign, PHd *14, in B-

17, I have already assigned ZE for ζεῦγος ‘yoke’.

τομῖς ‘knife’ > Arc.- Cyp. TO

Attestation:

SM1 (1909:277, #16): “Apparently a knife with a curved back.”

Bäckström (1911, in Mosenkis 7, #16): “knife.”

Eisenberg (July 2008: 18) “Saw or knife”, with a comparison to AB *74 ZE and “an Egyptian, hieroglyphic sign – *set*.” Cf. ξεστός ‘hewn, shaved, planed’.

Achterberg *et al.* (2021: 45, #16): “a knife”.

Mosenkis (2021:7): “knife”, with a logographic value of σμίλη ‘knife’.

Cross References: allograph PHd *11 TO²; PHd *14 ZE

Notes: CHS #23; CHIC #45

Grid 16: TO														
B-17							18	14	16					
1								ze	to					
B-25						43	18	23	16					
2									to					

PHd *17 PE

PHd *17 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

πέλιτη “small, leather shield’ may be compared with both *pelt* and the larger, leather shield depicted in AB *77 KA. See PHd *27 KA for further discussion.

Ion. πέλιτη, Dor. πέλιτα ‘a small, light, rimless, leather shield’ > B *072 PE

Attestation:

Denev (2016: 5, Table 1, #16, in Daraktchiev): “Shield: side view”.

Cross Reference: Phd *27 KA

Notes: CHIC #47 is possible.

Grid 17: TA														
A-08								19	17	18	06			
1									pe		ta			

Evans states that “the linearized representation of the flying eagle, but without the serpent, occurs in both classes of Cretan, linear script.”⁸² He apparently is referring to an alternate version of A *81 KU (Fig. 2, second image), However, PHd *18 appears to be a simpler version of A *81 (first image). Alternate versions of the second image, found in B *81, are not shown.

A *81 KU	Japanese <i>ku</i>	Japanese <i>ku</i>	Japanese <i>koku, kakou</i>	hexahedron or cube Greek κύβος	Japanese <i>kuchi</i>	Japanese <i>kuni</i>	Japanese <i>ku</i>
	hiragana character	<i>quadrature; carpenter's square, ruler</i>	<i>box, enclosure, surround</i>	Platonic solid, earth	<i>mouth, opening</i>	<i>country</i>	<i>district, section, ward</i>

Fig. 2: Linear-script KU, the cube, and Japanese ku, after Gretchen Leonhardt

The following analysis is adapted from Leonhardt:

The first version of A *81 KU suggests the squaring of stone, as does the *hiragana* character, < *ku*, echoed in Jap. 矩 *ku* ‘quadrature’. An ancient name for ‘earth’, *ku* or *qu* is found not only in *quadrature* but also in other *four-ness* words such as *quarter*, *square*, and *cube*. Cf. Egypt. *kub* ‘set square’. Whereas the two-dimensional *square* is an ancient symbol for earth, the three-dimensional, hexahedron or *cube* represents ‘earth’ as one of the five, Platonic solids. Notes Schneider, “Regardless of culture, the square was the pre-eminent symbol for the ancient, Earth Mother goddess.”⁸³ Cf. Κυβέλη ‘Cybele’, the Phrygian, *Idaeon Mother*. Although not pictured, 角 *kaku* ‘angle; square, cube’ may be compared with 口 *koku* (alt. 囿 *kakou*) ‘box, enclosure’. Cf., further, *ku*’s placement in the progressive *monad, duad, triad, tetrad* (L. *quad*). In these numerous ways, we express the ‘four corners of Earth’.⁸⁴

Japanese < *ku* ‘quadrature’ > <> AB *081 KU <> Egyp. *kub* ‘set square’

⁸² SMI (1909) 279, #31.

⁸³ Schneider (1994) 66-69.

⁸⁴ Leonhardt (2020) 15.

Attestation:

SMI (1909:278, #18): “A carpenter’s angle.”

Stawell (1931: 59, fig. 7, #35; 65, No. 35): “Angle” or “The Carpenter’s Angle”, with a proposed value of RE, for *ῥηχοι ‘prongs’, the interpretation of which appears to instead be aligned with that proposed for AB *27 RE (see PHd *39).

Eisenberg (2008, #18): “Boomerang or set square: The source could be . . . the Egyptian sign or amulet for the set square (*kub*).”

Surnin (2013: 189 *Identification Table*) “Carpenter’s square”.

Mosenkis (2021, 7, #18): “-γωνος ‘-angular’ ”.

Cross Reference: PHd *34 DE

Notes: CHS #42

Grid 18: KU															
B-17									18	14	16				
1									ku	ze	to				
A-24									18	06	12	02			
2									ku	ta	ki	jo			
A-23									18	01	13	07	15		
3									ku	e	zu	ko	te ²		
A-31									18	01	13	12	02		
4									ku	e	zu	ki	jo		
A-12									18	23	10	25	27	02	
A-18									18	23	10	25	27	02	
5-6									ku		i.ja			jo	
B-08								35	18	07					
7									ku	ko					
B-06								24	18	24	07				
8									ku		ko				
B-25								43	18	23	16				
9									ku		to				
B-04								07	18	39	30	09			
10								ko	ku			ti			
A-09								27	18	32	14	27	12	02	
11									ku		ze		ki	jo	
A-08							19	17	18	06					
12							pe	ku	ta						

In four of 12 sign groups, KU occurs in initial position. In two of the sign groups, KU, like KI, appears to have a different role, which will be addressed following decipherment. See *The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc*.

For numerous reasons, scholars seem to miss an association between PHd *19 and AB *031 SA. Evans, for example, asserts “a kind of plane”,⁸⁵ whereas Stawell is inclined to regard *19 (“The Crook”) as the progenitor of the Greek, minuscule λ, due to an implausible, phonetic association with λαβίς ‘handle’.⁸⁶ Manning, however, postulates a “forked tree branch”, which he compares to AB *01 DA.

I concur with Manning regarding the ‘forked, tree branch’ but must disagree regarding an association with AB *01. Preferring, instead, to seek acrophonic evidence for AB *031 SA, I am rewarded with σαῖς ‘loppings, twigs stripped from a tree’ and am yet able to come around to Stawell’s ‘crook’ (cf. M.E. *croche*, or *crotch*) and Manning’s ‘fork’ via the Jap., *on* reading for *sa* 叉 ‘crotch, fork (in river, road, tree, etc.)’.

An interesting validation of Jap. *sa* is found in the simple but obvious *kanji*, 丫 *ya* ‘bifurcation, fork’, a seeming echo of Greek *upsilon*. Moreover, cf. Jap. 矢 *ya* ‘arrow’ and Greek ἰά ‘arrows’ (see PHd *10). The earliest arrows were probably forked twigs, selected for their “trueness”. Perhaps someone had the ingenious idea that the forked twig could “fly” more easily by inserting feathers on the shaft (“Lose the fork!”) both to control and to extend the trajectory.

σαῖς ‘loppings, twigs stripped from a tree’ > 丫 > 丫 | 丫 AB *031 SA

Orientation: upright

Attestation:

Stawell (1931:59, Fig. 7, #23; 64, No. 23): ‘Crook’ or “The Crook”, with a proposed value of LA, for λαβίς ‘handle’.

Manning (2009:6): “This is probably a depiction of a ‘forked tree branch’,” with a proposed value of DA.

Achterberg *et al.* (2021:47): “sa₁”, following PHd *18 with a proposed value of SA.

Mosenkis (2021: 7, #19): ‘loppings, twigs stripped from a tree’ ”, with a proposed, logographic value of κοῦρος ‘boy’.

Notes: A version of this sign may be found on the Archalokori axe.

Grid 19: SA														
A-08										19	17	18	06	
1										sa	pe	ku	ta	
A-05								35	19	23				
2									sa					
A-22								35	19	41	12	02		
3									sa		ki	jo		

⁸⁵ *SMI* (1909) 278, #31.

⁸⁶ Stawell (1931) 64, #23.

PHd *20 PO

Evans readily indicated this sign's resemblance to jugs "common in the Cycladic wares at Melos and elsewhere" and further noted the effacement of the sign during the disc's cleaning⁸⁷ in 1908-09; however, the handle is included in his drawing.⁸⁸

Potable essentially means 'drinkable' and may be associated with AB *11 PO, which depicts ποτήρ 'a drinking cup'. Cf. πῶ 'Drink!' Whether or not the

meaning of ποτήρ can be expanded to include a pitcher, it is conceivable that a pitcher can be so named for the potable water that it contains. Cf. *pottery*.

Drinking, in the form of libations, figures prominently in the roots of LB and LC words. Cf. πότις 'drinking, drinker'. *po-ti-ni-ja* is a literal reference to "the mistress to whom we make libations", and *a-ta-na*po-ti-ni-ja* is the *ἄθᾶνα πότνια 'undying mistress', an apparent, Doric epithet of Ἀθᾶνα 'Athena' [KN V- 52]. Alternate roots include *po-si* [KN Sd 4402+] > πόσις 'a beverage, a drink' (cf. Poseidon, a reference to the 'long water' of the Mediterranean Sea), and *pi-ti* > πῖθι 'drink', at the root of πίθος and inscribed in LC upon at least three vessels [ICS 207, 346, 347].

ποτήρ 'a drinking cup' and perhaps *'a pitcher holding potable water' > AB *011 PO

Attestation:

SM1 (1909:278, #20): "Handled vase."

Mosenkis (2021:7, #20): "a kind of vessel", for a logographic value of κισσύβιον.

Notes: CHS #47, CHIC #53. Cf. the parallel, low-relief, potters' mark, principally found at Phaistos.⁸⁹

Grid 20: PO														
B-26									12	20	24	33		
1									ki	po				
B-18									35	20	24	24	29	
2										po			ma	

PHd *21 WA
for OA

PHd *21 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

This sign popularly inspires an interpretation of 'a curious double comb or rake'.⁹⁰ Notes Anastasiadou, the "comb motif" is reproduced, at Phaistos, on a sealing (HMs 992 from room 25).⁹¹ A further study, which attests the authenticity of the Phaistos disc, highlights the use of

⁸⁷ SM1 (1909) 278, #20.

⁸⁸ Fischer (1997) 68.

⁸⁹ Sanavia (2017) 88, fig. 12. 88, cup fragment (F. 6190) from the Grande Frana at Phaistos; Anastasiadou (2019) 38, fig. 20. The exhibit labels do not coincide with the description, so the origin of the fragment is unclear.

⁹⁰ SM1 (1909) 278, #21.

⁹¹ Anastasiadou (2016) 32, fig. 13a.

identical, low-relief, potters' marks,⁹² principally found in the Minoan Triangle.⁹³

Nevertheless, I disagree with the “comb” interpretation and, like Manning, see a resemblance to AB *054 WA. Manning, however, compares PHd *21 to a disassembled loom⁹⁴ whereas I see both a pictorial and phonetic relationship to ὄα ‘the border or the fringe of a garment’ and ῥα ‘sheepskin’ < ὄϊς ‘sheep’. See, also, PHd *30.

A reference to the fringe of a garment makes little sense in a ceramic context until one considers the tributary relationship between the Pharaohs and the Minoans. While there has been much speculation about a Minoan endonym, “Keftiu” is, perhaps, the most discussed. Alternatively, the Minoans, with their distinctive, three-stranded hairstyle, may have marked their pottery with WA (or OA) to distinguish themselves from other tribute-bearing peoples. Note the “three-stranded” evolution of this sign.

In another historical, tributary relationship, the Chinese refer to Japanese traders as *Wa*.

ὄα ‘the border or the fringe of a garment’ > > AB *054 WA

Attestation:

Manning (2009:6, D#21): “This is the Disc script's odd looking ‘loom or weaving’ symbol” which “equates well to AB54 (wa/va)” and appears to depict “a loom that is disassembled”, with a phonetic value of WA/VA.

Notes: CHS #41; CHIC #41, #163. Cf. the parallel, potters' mark, principally found at Phaistos.⁹⁵

Grid 21: WA																
A-03										21	37	35	27	27	12	2
A-15										21	37	35	27	27	12	2
1-2										wa					ki	jo

It is easy to see why scholars associate PHd *22 with AB *31 SA; however, I regard *22 as a distinct sign with no discernable equivalent in the linear scripts.

For this sign, I considered plausible values to fill phonetic gaps and then sought the acrophones for validation. In four, sign groups, νόγμα ‘prod’ provided the most plausible acrophone. Nevertheless, given the RU | RO alternation in LA | LB word pairs: e.g. *a.ti.ru* | *a.ti.ro*; *di.de.ru* | *di-de-ro*; *ka.sa.ru* | *ka-sa-ro*, NO, rather than NU, seemed the better

phonetic fit to express Greek.

In any case, inverted νόγμα offers a plausible, acrophonic origin for Greek ν ‘nu’.

νόγμα or νύγμα ‘prick, prod’ > > NO for NU

Notes: CHS #60, CHIC #19

⁹² Baldacci (2017) 70.

⁹³ *Ibid.* 68.

⁹⁴ Manning (2009) 6.

⁹⁵ Sanavia (2017) 14; Baldacci (2017) 70, fig. 5; 74, fig 9; and 75, fig. 10.

Grid 22: NO														
B-27							27	25	22					
1									no					
B-30							07	40	22	12	02			
2							ko		no	ki	jo			
B-22							25	42	37	22				
3										no				
B-05					08	07	36	29	22					
B-10					08	07	36	29	22					
4-5					ke ²	ko			no					

PHd *23 I or TU

This simple depiction seems too lightweight to be a club or mace, a role more effectively filled by PHd *13, and too insubstantial to be a weight-bearing, Minoan column or pillar.

Duhoux states that “[a] decipherment should be internally coherent, with few irregularities, and should make plausible sense. To argue (as some have done) that certain signs have [variable readings] is suspect.”⁹⁶ I may be inclined to agree with Duhoux if the variable readings amount to variable

interpretations of an object but not if they amount to synonyms for the same object. The shape of PHd *23 is ideally suited as a fastener and recalls the minuscule i and perhaps the magiscule T.

ἦλος ‘nail; nail head, stud’ > > i or I for ἦ

and

τύλος ‘wood bolt with knob on end’ > AB *05 TO > Greek T *tau*.

In all but one, sign group, *23 occurs in initial and medial positions. For this reason, I propose TU rather than TO, the latter of which is represented by PHd *16.

Cf. “ἦλος καὶ τύλος”, a medical reference to warts and calluses,⁹⁷ with emphasis on the ‘knob’. *Cf.*, also, τύλος with Jap. 吊 悬 *tsuru* ‘to hang, to suspend’, perhaps from a ‘knob’ or ‘stud’. In fact, 吊 appears to incorporate the depicted stud or bolt.

Notes: CHS #26

Both alternatives will appear in subsequent charts. In those charts containing the completed, sign groups, my preferred choice will be highlighted in black. Moreover, *Table 3*, which appears in the preface of the *Sign-Group Analysis*, outlines my proposals for the ten, sign groups.

⁹⁶ Duhoux (2000) 598.

⁹⁷ Dsc. 1.104

Grid 23: I/TU														
A-14									23	33				
1									i					
									tu					
B-28								05	23	37	02			
2								u	i		jo			
								u	tu		jo			
B-09								25	23	34	27			
3									i					
									tu					
B-02								25	23	34	29			
4									i					
									tu					
B-03								07	23	35	06	02		
5								ko	i		ta	jo		
								ko	tu		ta	jo		
A-20								38	23	32	12	02		
6									i		ki	jo		
									tu		ki	jo		
A-12								18	23	10	25	27	02	
A-18								18	23	10	25	27	02	
7-8								ku	i	i.ja			jo	
								ku	tu	i.ja			jo	
A-05								35	19	23				
9								sa	i					
								sa	tu					
B-06								24	18	23	07			
10								ku	i	ko				
								ku	tu	ko				
B-25								43	18	23	16			
11								ku	i	to				
								ku	tu	to				

PHd *24 TA²

As previously stated, in Lykian architecture, the pillar tomb (aka *tower tomb*) in Turkey bears the closest resemblance to this “pagoda-like structure” (see *Reading Direction*, above). While most of the square pillars appear to be regularly shaped structures, some, irregular structures inspire comparison with the “pagoda” on the left. Two examples are the pillar tomb in Pinara and the Harpy tomb in Xanthos.

The problem of anachronism is a fair concern when comparing the dating of the tombs (ca. 4th century BCE) with the conjectural dating of the disc (ca. 17th century BCE). However, charges of anachronism will persist in the absence of mechanical dating.

ταφή ‘burial, burial place’ >

Does the simplistic, AB *59 TA represent a chamber tomb?

Attestation:

SM1 (1909:26) “[T]he . . . probable explanation is that [in PHd *24] we have here the face of rectangular building with a hull-shaped roof. . . . The framework of the structure was necessarily of wood, and the projecting eaves and platform certainly recall the typical features presented, for example, by the well-known façade of the rock tomb at Myra, or certain prominent buildings, probably also tombs, rising above the town walls on the Pinara reliefs. It is natural that the sepulchral art of classical Lycia should have preserved the domestic architecture of a more remote period.”

Achterberg *et al.* (2021: 50): “[A]ccording to Mellink, this sign looks much like . . . graves in the form of a house in Lycia”, with a proposed value of PA for *parna* ‘house’.

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *06 TA.

Notes: CHS #41.

Grid 24: TA ²															
B-06									24	18	23	07			
1								ta ²	ku	i	ko				
								ta ²	ku	tu	ko				
A-30						12	40	24							
2						ki		ta ²							
B-26						12	20	24	33						
3						ki	po	ta ²							
B-21						35	40	24	07						
4								ta ²	ko						
B-18						35	20	24	24	29					
5							po	ta ²	ta ²						

B-18						35	40	24	24	29						
6								ta ²	ta²							

Initial KI in one sign group potentially implies a different role, which will be addressed, following decipherment. See *The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc*.

PHd *25 MU

The resemblance of PHd *25 to a ship is rather obvious and can be compared with AB *86, the value of which is unknown; however, to both signs, I have assigned the syllabic value of MU.

Per Evans, “the absence of a mast distinguishes [this ship] from all the figures of the vessels that occur in the hieroglyphic or linear scripts of Minoan Crete.”⁹⁸ In ligatures A *565 and *566, a second sign, which sits atop

the ship, may be construed as either freight or a “forecastle”.

μύδιον > ‘a small boat’ > AB *86 (see also ligatures A *565 /*566)

Regarding the small size of μύδιον, cf. μῦα or Att. μῦα ‘fly’ and 虫 *mushi* ‘insect, cricket, moth, worm’, the sign of which resembles a snail or a slug with a metaphorical sail upon its back. Cf. also 虫 *mushi* to μῦς ‘mouse’. Jap. *mu* may be expressed as either *hiragana* む or *katakana* ム. On a side note, cf. 虫 *mushi* ‘soft’ with *mushy* ‘soft, pulpy, without firmness’.

Orientation: Moving left to right, sometimes standing on end to save space.

Attestation:

SMI (1909:278, #25) “Ship, with, apparently, an arrow pointing from its prow.”

Stawell (1931:59, Fig. 7, #30) “Ship”, with a proposed value of NE, for νηῦς ‘ship’.

Manning (2009:7, D#25): “The Disc's 'ship' sign equates well to AB86, a sign of unknown syllabic value.”

Mosenkis (2021:8, #25): κύδαρος ‘small ship’ is one of a number of possibilities, which include “ναῦς, νηῦς ‘ship’ ”.

Notes: CHS #57; CHIC #041

Grid 25: MU																
B-09										25	23	34	27			
1										mu	i					
										mu	tu					
B-02										25	23	34	29			
2										mu	i					
										mu	tu					
B-22										25	42	37	22			
3										mu			no			

⁹⁸ *SMI*, (1909) 278, #25.

B-27								27	25	22							
4									mu	no							
B-19							01	38	25	27							
5							e		mu								
A-12						18	23	10	25	27	02						
A-18						18	23	10	25	27	02						
6-7						ku	i	i.ja	mu		jo						
						ku	tu	i.ja	mu		jo						

PHd *26 KO²

I had previously assigned KO to PHd *07, which I believe depicts κόρυς ‘a helmet’. A second sign about which I feel fairly certain is PHd *26. Whereas some see a horn,⁹⁹ I see κόμη ‘tail’. Cf. the logograph, B *151, with the generic assignment of CORNus ‘horn’, which, nevertheless, resembles the scaly tail of a fanciful, sea monster (cf. κῆτος, ‘any sea monster or huge fish’ > L. *cetacea*). One possible attestation for the tail interpretation may be found in

Georgiev, who states that the Phaistos disc “contains many identical or similar signs [to Luvian], including the famous ‘tail’,¹⁰⁰ which is without clear reference for the uninitiated reader.

Although seemingly convoluted, the association between PHd *07 and AB *70 KO is possible. On the one hand, I have long interpreted AB *70 as ‘liquid pouring from the mouth of a vessel’.¹⁰¹ In a re-interpreted context of funerary rites (see KN A- series), KO appears to be the foundation for LB *ko-wo* > χόω ‘to throw or to heap up’ (i.e. to pour upon), in burial, and its inflection, *ko-wa* > χοή ‘a pouring, esp. a drink offering (libation)’. Cf. PHd *20 PO. Yet, the popular interpretation of the LB record is effectively silent about funerary rites, which constitute such an important aspect of Greek culture.

On the other hand, AB *70, in some renderings, can conceivably be interpreted as the tail of a large animal. I suspect that κόμη ‘a tail’ is a metaphorical reference to χοή ‘a pouring’.

Finally, the sign, A *708k, which resembles “T”, may simply be a linear version of *70.

κόμη ‘a tail’ > B *151 (aka CORNus) > KO²

Cross Reference: PHd *33 KE

Notes: allograph PHd *07 KO.

Grid 26: KO²																	
A-10										26	31	12	02				
A-13										26	31	12	02				
A-26										26	31	12	02				
1-3										ko²		ki	jo				

⁹⁹ SMI (1909) 279, #26, “horn of an ox”; Stawell (1931), 58, fig. 6, #15; Rasmussen (2009).
¹⁰⁰ Cotterell (1979) 79.
¹⁰¹ Leonhardt (2020) 9.

B-14								01	27	09	02				
3								e	ka	ti	jo				
A-25							08	44	27						
4							ke ²		ka						
B-19						01	38	25	27						
5						e		mu	ka						
A-26						12	07	45	27						
6						ki	ko		ka						
B-09						25	23	34	27						
7						mu	i		ka						
						mu	tu		ka						
B-29						35	07	45	27						
8							ko		ka						
A-03						21	37	35	27	27	12	02			
A-15						21	37	35	27	27	12	02			
9-10						wa			ka	ka	ki	jo			
A-12						18	23	10	25	27	02				
A-18						18	23	10	25	27	02				
11-12						ku	i	i,ja	mu	ka	jo				
						ku	tu	i,ja	mu	ka	jo				
A-03						21	37	35	27	27	12	02			
A-15						21	37	35	27	27	12	02			
13-14						wa			ka	ka	ki	jo			
A-09						27	18	32	14	27	12	02			
15						ka			ka	ki	jo				

PHd *28 O

PHd *28 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

Godart notes that “[t]his sign represents the leg of a bull. A seal of the same shape and profile . . . was found at Apodoulos in 1994, in a Protopalatial level (1750 BC).”¹⁰³ This note is accompanied by an image of the seal, with its exaggerated emphasis on the hoof rather than on the leg, understandable given its role as a stamp.

Beginning with Evans, depictions of PHd *28 are universally “corrected” with hoof side down. Although I agree with Godart’s premise that “inverted signs alternate with regular ones within sets of identical signs,” I disagree with his conclusion that the inversion

¹⁰³ *Ibid.* 136, #28.

of this particular sign is insignificant.¹⁰⁴ If the author intended to emphasize the hoof, rather than the leg, then the inverted orientation makes sense.

ὄνοξ ‘a hoof’ > > O

Attestation:

SMI (1909:279, #28): “Ox’s foot.”

Bäckström (1911, in Mosenkis 8, #28): “calf’s hoof.”

Stawell (1931:58, Fig. 6, #4; 60, No. 4): “Oxhoof” or “The Ox Hoof”, with a proposed value of BO, for *βου-πούς ‘ox foot’.

Manning (2009:7, D#28): “ ‘bovine foot’ sign”.

Achterberg *et al.* (2021: 53): “lower leg with hoof”.

Mosenkis (2021:8, #28): “διόνυξ ‘clover hoof’ (sic) for a logographic value of Διόνυσος ‘Dionysus’.

Mosenkis may have intended ‘cloven hoof’, a plausible alternate definition for ‘double nail’.¹⁰⁵

Grid 28: O														
A-11									01	28				
A-17									01	28				
1-2									e	o				

PHd *29 MA

PHd *29, acting as suffix in A-29 and B-11, has been popularly interpreted, beginning with Evans, as “an animal of the feline genus”¹⁰⁶, much like the controversial AB *80 MA. Certainly, given some versions of this sign in LA, the interpretation of ‘cat’ is reasonable,

In LB, however, the sign has largely diverged from ‘cat’, thus compelling a different interpretation that explains both the original and the evolved signs. Cf. Jap. 魔 *ma* ‘demon, devil; evil spirit; evil influence’.

In LA, the angry visage of the ‘demon’ is reanalyzed, in LB, as an ‘evil spirit’ in an attitude of incantation. In Nihon-go, the LA sign is recognizable as the cursive, *hiragana* め *me*. In all of this sign’s permutations, the majuscule “M” becomes apparent.

Cats have long been associated with bad luck, black magic, sorcery, and demonic forces. In folklore, witches and sorcerers are often accompanied by black cats known as *familiars*, which are alternately known as *imps* “small, mischievous demons”, typically more playful than evil.

魔 *ma* ‘demon; devil; evil spirit; evil influence’ > > AB *80 MA

Orientation: facing right

Attestation:

Bäckström (2011, in Mosenkis, 8): ‘not necessarily cat’.

Akulov (2016, 33, pic. 8, “Signs known through Linear A”): “MA”.

¹⁰⁴ Godart (1995) 74.

¹⁰⁵ L&S 2nd s.v. διόνυξ.

¹⁰⁶ *SMI* (1909) 279 #29.

Notes: CHS #74, #75

Sanavia not only interprets ‘cat’ but further associates this sign with a fine-ware impression depicting a crouching animal in profile.¹⁰⁷

Grid 29: MA														
A-28							34	29	29					
1.a								ma	ma					
B-16						01	33	29						
2						e		ma						
A-29						07	45	29						
B-11						07	45	29						
3-4						ko		ma						
B-12						13	08	29						
5						zu	ke ²	ma						
A-28						34	29	29						
1.b							ma	ma						
B-02					25	23	34	29						
6					mu	i		ma						
					mu	tu		ma						
B-05					08	07	36	29	22					
B-10					08	07	36	29	22					
B-13					08	07	36	29	22					
7-9					ke ²	ko		ma	no					
B-18				35	20	24	24	29	22					
10					po	ta ²	ta ²	ma	no					

PHd *30 U²
for OU

PHd *30 is a *hapax* occurrence on side B.

In addition to the *Hyakinthia*, the two, other, major, Spartan *heïromenia* were γυμνο-παιδία > *Gymnopaedia* ‘naked youth’ and the Κάρνεια, which was celebrated by the Dorians, in August, in honor of *Apollo Karneios*, the ram-horned Apollo.

This profile is identical to that facing left on a stater from Salamis. Two, dextroverse signs under the head of a crouching ram read *pa-si*, which is typically an abbreviation of *pa-si-le-wo-se* > βασιλεύς ‘chief, commander’ [ICS 324a]. Cf. LB *qa-si-re-u* [PY Jn 421+]. The obverse,

¹⁰⁷ Sanavia (2017) 91.

which features a ram's head in profile, reads *e-u-wa-te-o-se* on two lines, which may perhaps be compared to εὐετία, poet. εὐετή, 'thriving, prosperous'.

The phonetic journey from ὄϊς 'sheep' to U defies neat correspondence but is still plausible when considering numerous cognates in IE languages, which include OHG *ouwi*, Dutch *ooi*, OS *ewi*, and, of course, English *ewe*. See, also, PHd *21

ὄϊς 'sheep' > > L. *ovis* < PIE **o-wi-*> Eng. *ewe* > U² for OU

Orientation: facing upward

Attestation:

Stawell (1931: 58, Fig. 6, #20): "Ram", with a proposed value of KRI, for κρῖός 'ram'.

Manning (2009:8, D#30): " 'ram's horn' sign", with a proposed value of SU, for AB *58 SU.

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *05 U; PHd *21 WA

Notes: CHIC #16

Sanavia compares PHd *30 with the thematically-similar, fine-ware impression of a horned animal in profile.¹⁰⁸

Grid 30: U²														
B-04						07	18	39	30	09				
1						ko	ku		u²	ti				

PHd *31 RO

The 'flying eagle with a serpent in its claws' compels a comparison with a *roc*, that monstrous, legendary bird that 'dashes' its prey on the *rocks*, like ῥοχθέω 'to dash with a roaring sound (of the sea)'. Cf. ῥωγᾶς 'ragged' + θέω 'to run'; therefore, 'to run ragged'. Cf., also, *rugged* with ῥωγάδας ἐς πέτρας 'clefts in the rocks'.¹⁰⁹

LB *ru-ki-ti-jo* [KN Ga 415] in the context of Tyrian-purple production,¹¹⁰ is used in the sense of 'dashing over, washing'. Speculation about the etymology of *roc* highlights Pers. رُك *ruk^h* or *rok^h*.

Moreover, while some may dismiss a correlation with *rook*, a member of the *Corvidae* family, numerous species of crows are known to drop prey, such as crustaceans, molluscs, and turtles. Other species mentioned in the same study include eagles, gulls, ospreys, and vultures.¹¹¹

Prey dropping is principally used to break shells and carapaces and is expanded to include bones, eggs, and nuts. It is conceivable that the species of bird depicted in PHd *31 is less important than its tendency to occasionally drop its food on hard surfaces to access the meat, thus, perhaps, earning a generic designation of *rook*. Consequently, the definition of ῥοχθέω is potentially expanded to include prey dropping.

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid.* 91, fig. 16.

¹⁰⁹ Theoc.24.95.

¹¹⁰ Leonhardt (2017) 14.

¹¹¹ Cristol and Switzer (1999) 221, table 1.

ῥοχθέω ‘to dash (on the rocks)’ > *rok^h* (*rook*) > AB *02 RO

Attestation:

SMI (1909) 279, #31): “Flying bird, apparently an eagle, who seems to hold a serpent in his claws.”

Orientation: Flying right (2x), flying upright (2x), and flying upside down, left (1x).

Grid 31: RO														
A-10								26	31	12	02			
A-13								26	31	12	02			
A-16								26	31	12	02			
1-3								ko ²	ro	ki	jo			
A-07							12	26	31					
4							ki	ko ²	ro					
A-23							35	26	31					
5								ko ²	ro					

Continuing the bird theme, PHd *32 depicts a standing bird in profile (perhaps to emphasize πέρυξ ‘wing’), the generic nature of which may be characterized as *pte-no* > πτηνός ‘flying, winged’ [KN Sd 4402+]. The acrophonic value of πτηνός recalls B *62 PTE, which resembles the “horns of consecration” prominently displayed at Knossos and placed upon rooftops, shrines, and tombs in Neopalatial Crete.¹¹² Cf. also *pe-te-re-wa* [KN So 894] and *pte-re-wa* [KN Se 879+] >

πελέα ‘elm’. Among the woods used in chariot-wheel construction (see ROTA in the KN Se and So series), the elm is often characterized as “the spreading tree”.

Bradać, citing Dow and Rutkowski, however, would dismiss such a “connection” between B *62 PTE and the horns of consecration: “The sign, ‘horns of consecration’, does not exist in Linear A repertory, but it appears in Linear B in the so-called, canonical shape. The meaning of the sign is *pte*. No connection whatsoever between the phonetic group *pte* (suggested as the name of the object) and the horns could be established.”¹¹³

If the aim is to establish a connection between the acrophonic value of B *62 and “horns of consecration”, then I agree: no connection exists. However, simply based upon their resemblance to *62, I wish to reinterpret “horns of consecration” as “wings of invocation” as they pertain to ἔπεα πτερόεντα ‘winged (lofty) words’ and perhaps to ‘winged prayers’:

θάμβησεν δ’ Ἀχιλεὺς, μετὰ δ’ ἐτράπετ’, αὐτίκα δ’ ἔγνω Παλλάδ’ Ἀθηναίην: δεινὸν δέ ὄσσε φάανθεν: καὶ μιν φωνήσας ἔπεα πτερόεντα προσηύδα:¹¹⁴

¹¹² Gessell (1985) 62.

¹¹³ Bradać (2005) 188.

¹¹⁴ Hom. *Il.* 1.199.

The astonished Achilles, seized with wonder, immediately recognized Pallas Athene; terribly her eyes shone. Then he addressed her with winged words. . . .

“Wings of invocation” upon rooftops finally make sense.

πτηνός ‘flying, winged (of birds)’ B *62 PTE, re-interpreted as “wings of invocation”

Orientation: Standing on tail

Notes: CHS #76, #80

Grid 32: PTE														
B-15							33	39	32	35	06			
1									pte		ta			
A-20							38	23	32	12	02			
2								i	pte	ki	jo			
								tu	pte	ki	jo			
A-09							27	18	32	14	27	12	02	
3							ka	ku	pte	ze	ka	ki	jo	

PHd *33 KE

There appears to be universal consensus that this fish represents θύννος ‘*tunny*, tuna’, with a reasonable, proposed value of TU, by Stawell. However, TU does not work well in decipherment. For PHd *33, the alternate, κῆτος ‘*tunny*, fish’ is affirmed. Note that the broader definition of κῆτος is “any sea monster or huge fish”; see Phd *26 KO². Nevertheless, an association with AB *44 KE is questionable.

κῆτος ‘*tunny* fish’ > > KE

Attestations:

- SMI* (1909:279, #33): “Fish, probably rightly identified with a tunny, by Dr. Pernier.”
- Bäckström (2011, in Mosenkis): “tunny fish”
- Hempl (1911:194): “θύννος ‘tunny fish’.”
- Stawell (1931:59, #43): “Tunny” for θύννος ‘*tunny*, tuna’ with a proposed value of TU.
- Godart (1995:137, #33): “Fish, perhaps tunny according to Pernier.”
- Achterberg *et al.* (2021:57): “fish, possibly tunny”.
- Mosenkis (2021: 9, #33) ‘fish, probably tunny’.

Cross Reference: Phd *26 KO², allograph PHd *08 KE².

Notes: CHS #59

Grid 33: KE														
B-24									33	39	01	13		
1									ke		e	zu		
B-15									33	39	32	35	06	
2									ke		pte		ta	
A-27									33	40	04	12	02	
3									ke		k ^h o	ki	jo	
B-16								01	33	29				
4								e	ke	ma				
A-14								23	33					
5								i	ke					
								tu	ke					
B-26						12	20	24	33					
6						ki	po	ta ²	ke					

PHd *34 DE

According to the Bible, Deborah (דְּבֹרָה *dburh* ‘a bee’) was a prophetess and a judge or ruler of ancient Israel.¹¹⁵ As ‘Queen Bee’, Deborah may be compared with the Minoan Bee Goddess, whose descendants included Cybele, Demeter, and Rhea, the *Melissae*, from μέλισσα *Melissa* (Att. μέλιττα *Melitta*) ‘a bee’. Likewise, Deborah’s priestesses were known as *Deborahs*. Cf. דָּבָר *dabar* ‘speech’, which may be compared with the buzzing of bees.

In LA, *du.pu₂.re* may be found, not only in the alternation, *du.pu₃.re* [KO Za 1], but also in both *a.di.ki.te.te.*307.pu₂.re* [PK Za 8] and *ja.di.ki.te.te.-du.pu₂.re* [PK Za 15]. See also LB *da-pu₂-ri-to-jo* [KN Gg 702+].

In *Uchina:guchi*, the language of Okinawa, 御拝 で一ひーる *nifée deebiru* means ‘thank you’, perhaps an extended meaning of the vocative “Deborah”. Cf. the vocative, *Elohe* ‘God’, with Haw. *aloha* ‘hello, good bye’.

Note that the *hiragana*, ひ *bi*, recalls the body of a honey bee.

דְּבֹרָה *dburh* ‘a bee’ > AB *045 DE

Attestation:

SMI (1909:279, #34): “an insect, possibly a bee seen from above.”

Godart (1995: 137, #35): “Bee.”

Stawell (2009:59, #28): “Bee”, with a proposed value of ME, for μέλισσα.

¹¹⁵ Judges 4 and 5 KJV.

Manning (2009:8, D#34): “This Disc sign is a depiction of a ‘honey bee’ or ‘flying insect’. It compares well to AB45(de). . . . Though AB45 is a very simplified linear version of a ‘honey bee’ it is, nonetheless, the only Linear AB sign that resembles a ‘honey bee’,” with a proposed value of DE.
 Surnin (2013: 112-113): “bee”, with a logographic value of “prosperity, wealth, well-being”

Cross Reference: PHd *18 KU

Notes:

CHS #86; CHIC #20

Grid 34: DE														
A-28										34	29	29		
1										de	ma	ma		
B-09							25	23	34	27				
2							mu	i	de	ka				
							mu	tu	de	ka				
B-02							25	23	34	29				
3							mu	i	de	ma				
							mu	tu	de	ma				

PHd *35 resembles the pictographic form of AB *04 TE, which, in turn, resembles the Sumerian sign for ‘barley’. Cf. the identical, Sumerian *še* ‘barley’ with *σῖτος* ‘grain’. Cf., also, Jap. 手 *te*, which is most recognizable in 空手 *karate* ‘empty handed’, where it is presumed to be an ideograph for ‘hand’.

Although AB *04 is sometimes represented with five ‘fingers’, it is commonly represented with six, much like a stalk of barley. Even the ‘six-fingered’ version of the early-Japanese ideograph¹¹⁶ resembles barley more than it does a hand. A six-fingered hand seems a stretch, in any case.

Nevertheless, the sign has a phonetic role in *karate*, an unattested, Japanese cognate of the Greek *κρᾶτέω* ‘to conquer, to prevail; to get the upper hand’, which is found at the root of ‘ruling’ words, such as *aristocrat* and *democrat*. Moreover, Aeol. *κρετέω* suggests a possible association with *Κρήτη* ‘Crete’, where the martial arts flourish in modern times.

Attestation:

SMI (1909:279, #35): “A plant or tree sign.”

Duhoux (1983: 34, “Correspondances possibles entre signes”): “te”.

Timm (2008:2, Table 1): “An association with AB *04 TE as a “frequent, end sign”.

Owens (2014: 2, in Younger): “AB 04 TE”.

Akulov (2016, 33, pic. 8, “Signs known through Linear A”): “TE”.

¹¹⁶ Henshall (1988) *s.v.* #32 *te* “hand”.

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *15 TE².

Notes: CHS #97, #102, #128; CHIC #25

Grid 35: TE														
B-08									35	18	07			
1									te	ku	ko			
A-05									35	19	23			
2									te	sa	i			
									te	sa	tu			
A-26									35	26	31			
3									te	ko ²	ro			
B-29									35	07	45	27		
4									te	ko		ka		
B-21									35	40	24	07		
5									te		ta ²	ko		
A-22									35	19	41	12	02	
6									te	sa		ki	jo	
B-18									35	20	24	24	29	
7									te	po	ta ²	ta ²	ma	
B-03							07	23	35	06	02			
8							ko	i	te	ta	jo			
							ko	tu	te	ta	jo			
A-03							21	37	35	27	27	12	02	
A-15							21	37	35	27	27	12	02	
9-10							wa		te	ka	ka	ki	jo	
B-15							33	39	32	35	06			
11							ke		pte	te	ta			

I propose that initial TE in six words assumes the role of τε, a proclitic article, which will be addressed, following decipherment. See *The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc*.

PHd *36 RA
for RE

In addition to plausible, acrophonic overlap – as demonstrated with the allographs for syllables such as KO and KE – a second anomaly occurs in which two, seemingly related depictions assume different acrophones, perhaps to reflect the pronunciations by different dialects.

In the linear scripts, the value, RE, has been assigned to AB *27, which some interpret as a crocus (CHS #88) or as a non-descript plant (CHS #92). Few scholars may see the

wisdom in assigning RE to PHd *36, as reflected in Evans’ statement that the latter “closely resembles certain varieties. . . of the olive branch.”¹¹⁷

And, yet, I see, not two distinct ideas but alternate renderings of the same interpretation, as reflected in different dialects. That is, two dialects both read ‘branch, twig’ but represent that idea differently.

Dor. ῥᾶχός for Ion. ῥηχός ‘branch, twig’ (cf. ῥηχοῖ ‘prongs’) > PHd*39
> AB *27 RE

Attestation:

SMI (1909:279, #36): “closely resembles certain varieties. . . of the olive branch”.

Stawell (1931:58, Fig. 6, #11): “Branch”, with a proposed value of K, for κλάδος ‘branch, shoot of a tree’.

Stawell reserves a proposal of ῥηχοῖ ‘prongs’ for PHd *18.

Manning (2009:8, D#39): “This is the ‘lily, crocus, or iris’ flower sign. It compares well with AB27 (le/re) and to . . . CHIC#s 023 and 031.”

Cross References: PHd *39, PHd *18 KU

Notes: CHS #101, CHIC #029.

Grid 36: RA														
B-20								40	36	26	02			
1									ra	ko ²	jo			
B-13							08	07	36	29				
2							ke ²	ko	ra	ma				
B-05							08	07	36	29	22			
B-10							08	07	36	29	22			
3-4							ke ²	ko	ra	ma	no			

¹¹⁷ *SMI* (1909) 279 #36.

PHd *37 NA

Although I can accept a provisional value of NA for PHd *37, I initially felt unable to justify an acrophonic association. My early notes indicate an alternate possibility of NI. To the list of possibilities, I would later add BU and PA following a suggestion that the sign depicts *papyrus*¹¹⁸, the Greek word for which is βύβλος and from which arises *bible*. Nevertheless, I was unable to tie *papyrus* to any word beginning with NA, until I encountered *Narcissus papyraceus*, commonly known as *paperwhite*.

At the root of both *νάρκισσος* ‘narcissus’ and *narcotic* is *νάρκη* ‘numbness’. The personification of *narcissus* is embodied in the myth of the beautiful youth who is enamored with his pond reflection. Numb to the world around him, he spends his days staring at his reflection until he is transformed into a narcissus flower, which grows next to the pond. For further discussion about youth who are transformed into flowers, see *ko-pi-me-e* [A-21] below.

According to Pliny, of two species of *narcissus* (family *amaryllidaceae*, genus *narcissus*), the “herbaceous narcissus”, in addition to being both an emetic and a purgative, “produces dull, heavy pains in the head”.¹¹⁹ Moreover, *Narcissus poeticus*, a species native to Greece, is known for its “intoxicating” fragrance. Likewise, papyrus (family *cyperaceae*, genus *cyperus*), known for its use in papermaking, is also an ingredient in the perfume industry. Popular in Indian perfumes, the “heady scents” of papyrus range from spicy to woody. I surmise that the utility of papyrus as paper was discovered in the dried, pulpy byproduct of oil extraction, which, perhaps, was originally burned as incense. For *37, I have since ruled out papyrus, due to its leafless stems, but retain an interest in *narcissus*.

Yet another species, featured in Minoan art and known for its intoxicating quality, is the lily (family *liliaceae*, genus *lilium*), the numerous varieties of which generally grow between two- and six-feet tall and feature small, pinnate leaves on their stalks.

For the moment, however, the various, physical attributes of these three species defy ready association with PHd *37. Consequently, I am less inclined to associate PHd *37 with a known species and more inclined to at least recognize a generic reference to its narcotic quality. It is conceivable that such species would have earned the generic designation, *narcissus*.

νάρκη ‘numbness’ > *νάρκισσος* ‘narcissus’ >

Attestation:

Achterberg *et al.* (2021: 59): “possibly *papyrus*”

Notes: Minoan seal, CMS VS1A-046-2, Agios Charalambos, Höhle.¹²⁰

Grid 37: NA															
A-03									21	37	35	27	27	12	02
A-15									21	37	35	27	27	12	02
1									wa	na	te	ka	ka	ki	jo

¹¹⁸ Achterberg *et al.* (2021) 59.

¹¹⁹ Plin. *Nat.* 21.75.

¹²⁰ <http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/objekt/165274>, in the Arachne database of the Archaeological Institute at the University of Cologne.

B-28							05	23	37	02				
2							u	i	na	jo				
							u	tu	na	jo				
B-22							25	42	37	22				
3							mu		na	no				

PHd *38 is a hapax occurrence on side A and recalls the Sumerian sign for *an*, *anu* ‘heaven’, an eight-pointed star, which appears to have devolved into the Arc.-Cyp. six-pointed star, with the phonetic value of A. A plausible, alternative interpretation is ἄστὴρ ‘star’.

Attestation:

Rasmussen (2009): “An eight-pointed star is a common symbol for heaven.”

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *43 A².

Notes:

Cf. the parallel, fine-ware motif, principally found at Phaistos¹²¹ and the compartmented, stamp seal from the Bactria-Margiana region.¹²²

Grid 38: A														
A-01									38	03	10			
A-04									38	03	10			
1-2									a	k ^h a	i,ja			
A-20									38	23	32	12	02	
3									a	i	pte	ki	jo	
									a	tu	pte	ki	jo	
B-19							01	38	25	27				
4							e	a	mu	ka				

¹²¹ Sanavia (2017) 86, fig. 9; 87, fig. 10; 91, fig. 19; 97, fig. 28c.

¹²² *Ibid.* 97, fig. 28c.

PHd *39 RE

In the linear scripts, the value, RE, has been assigned to AB *27, which some interpret as a crocus (CHS #88) or as a non-descript plant (CHS #92). Yet, few scholars may see the wisdom in assigning RE to PHd *36, as reflected in Evans' association with an olive branch.

Nevertheless, in both PHd *36 and *39, I see, not two distinct ideas, but alternate renderings of the same idea, as reflected in two dialects; thus, *36 RA and *39 RE.

Ion. ῥηχός 'branch, twig' for Dor. ῥᾶχός (cf. ῥηχοι 'prongs') > PHd *36 RA

Attestation:

Owens (2014: 3, in Younger): "AB 27 RE"

Cross Reference: PHd *36 RA

Notes: CHS #88

Grid 39: RE														
A-19								11	39					
1								to ²	re					
B-24								33	39	01	13			
2								ke	re	e	zu			
B-15								33	39	32	35	06		
3								ke	re	pte	te	ta		
B-04							07	18	39	30	09			
4							ko	ku	re	u ²	ti			

PHd *40 PI

PHd *40 compels a comparison with AB *39 PI. The rounded body of one version of B *39 resembles a tongue; however, the seemingly inserted "I" makes any association dubious.

πικρίς 'ox tongue' > AB *39 PI

Attestation:

Rasmussen (2016: 7, fig. 3. #40): “tongue”.

Grid 40: PI																	
B-20										40	36	26	02				
1										pi	ra	ko ²	jo				
A-30								12	40	24							
2								ki	pi	ta ²							
A-21								07	40	41	01						
3								ko	pi	me	e						
B-21								35	40	24	07						
4								te	pi	ta ²	ko						
B-30								07	40	22	12	02					
5								ko	pi	no	ki	jo					
A-27								33	40	04	12	02					
6								ke	pi	k ^h o	ki	jo					

PHd *41 ME

While Evans has not ventured a guess regarding the meaning of PHd *41, at least, four scholars agree that it represents ‘a bone’, even as they disagree about acrophonic value.

μερίς ‘a part, a portion’, esp. of μῆρα or μηρός ‘thigh bone’ > > ME

Attestation:

Manning (2009:9, D#41): “This sign appears to be a depiction of a ‘bone’,” with a proposed value of TA₂.

Rasmussen (2016: 7, fig. 3. #41): “bone”.

Achterburg *et al.* (2021: 62, D41): “possibly bone”.

Mosenkis (2021: 9, #41): ‘rib’, with a proposed logographic value of πλευρόν.

Grid 41: ME																	
A-21								07	40	41	01						
1								ko	pi	me	e						
A-22								35	19	41	12	02					
2								te	sa	me	ki	jo					

--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PHd *42 RI

Phd *22 is a *hapax* occurrence on side B.

My immediate impression of this sign is of waves breaking on a pebbled beach.

ῥηγμίν or ῥηγμίς ‘the sea breaking on the beach; the surf’ > RI for ῥη

Cross Reference: PHd *45 RI.JA

Notes: CHIC #071.

Grid 42: RI														
B-22								25	42	37	22			
1								mu	ri	na	no			

PHd *43 A²

PHd *43 is a *hapax* occurrence on side B, which depicts ἄφρασις ‘release’, i.e. ‘a conduit, a sluice’. Cf. LB *a-pe-i-si* [KN Od 666].

However, the similar, AB *66 TA₂ (ti.ja) probably arises from διάττος ‘sieve’ < διά ‘through’.

ἄφρασις ‘release’, i.e. ‘conduit, sluice’ A² = B *66 TA₂ (TI.JA) < probably διάττος ‘seive’

Attestation:

Godart (1995: 139, #43): “Strainer.”

Manning (2009:9, D#43): “This sign, a ‘triangular sieve’, compares well to [CHIC#047] except that the Disc’s ‘sieve’ has a triangular shape.” However, Manning believes that “[i]t is far more likely that D#43 is the Disc’s version of [A-78(qe)].”

Cross Reference: allograph PHd *38 A.

Notes: CHS #51.

Cf. the fine-ware motif, principally found at Phaistos.¹²³

¹²³ Sanavia (2017) 88, fig. 11; 92, fig. 20.

Grid 43: A²														
B-25									43	18	23	16		
1									a²	ku	i	to		
									a²	ku	tu	to		

PHd *44 LU

PHd *44 is a *hapax* occurrence on side A.

This sign is distinguished from hieroglyphic renderings of the wolf's head, which include a protruding tongue; however, some renderings are similar insofar as the heads point downward.

In the absence of the L-series in both LA and LB, and despite the L-series' coincidence with the R-series in LC, I was surprised to find its presence on the Phaistos disc. Yet,

with the limited sample of the Phaistos disc, I would regard as suspect any proposed PHd signary with a comprehensive L-series.

Among PHd scholars who favor Greek, Stawell proposes acrophonic values for LA, RE, RI, LO, and LU.¹²⁴ The seamless blending of the L- and R-series is interesting for the fact that Stawell's PHd scholarship predates Ventris' scholarship by at least 20 years. Nevertheless, I regard this blending more accidental than deliberate.

Notes:

CHS #72, 73; CHIC #13, #17, #18

Grid 44: LU														
A-25									08	44	27			
1									ke ²	lu	ka			

PHd *45 RI.JA

Given its similarity to AB *076 RA₂ (RJA or RIJA), *45 is easy to discern, even though scholars do not make a direct, numerical reference to the linear-script sign. While two interpretations, ῥῆα and ῥέω, seem possible, context appears to govern the choice of interpretation.

'Flow', 'emanation', and 'radiation' are very important concepts in Greek thought; cf. ῥῆα 'easily' > ῥέω, Ep. ῥείω 'to flow, to gush, to stream' with Sp. río 'river'. These ideas are expressed in numerous ways throughout LB. Examples

include *ro-a* > Dor. ῥόά, ῥοή 'a flood, a river, a stream' [KN Xd 148] and *pe-ri-ra-wo* > περιρρέω 'to flow around' [PY An 654] in the military tablets.

Given this sign's association with PHd *42 RI, it seems fitting to offer RI as an dual value in at least two, identical sign groups [A-29, B-11]. Both seem plausible in context, so the choice may be finalized in debate.

¹²⁴ Stawell (1931) 58-59, figs. 6 and 7 #23, 24, 25, 35, 36.

NF

> AB *076 RA₂ (RJA or RIJA).

Attestation:

SMI (1909:280, #45): “Dr. Pernier considers that this sign may be a conventional representation of water.”

Hempl (1911: 194): “stream”, with a proposed value of PE for πηγῆ ‘stream’.

Stawell (1931: 59, fig. 7, #33): “River”, with a proposed value of PO, for ποταμός ‘river, stream’.

Duhoux (1983: 34, “Correspondances possibles entre signes”): “ra₂”.

Rasmussen (2009:7): “flood”, with a proposed value of JA for a “[s]imilar Luwian hieroglyph *ia*. H: *ijal* ‘spring’.

Akulov (2016: 33, pic. 8: “Signs known through Linear A”): “RA”, a likely reference to RA₂.

Achterberg *et al.* (2021: 65, D 45): “water”, with a proposed value of NÁ; *cf.* *νάω* ‘flow’. In LC, the phonetic value of this sign is NE, which aligns with *νάα*, the Ion. acc. of *νάως* ‘ship’.

Cross Reference: PHd *42 RI

Notes: CHS #115; CHIC #69.

Grid 45: RIJA												
B-01								07	45			
1								ko	ri			
								ko	ri,ja			
B-07								07	45	07		
2								ko	ri	ko		
								ko	ri,ja	ko		
A-29								07	45	29		
B-11								07	45	29		
3-4								ko	ri	ma		
								ko	ri,ja	ma		
A-26							12	07	45	27		
5							ki	ko	ri	ka		
							ki	ko	ri,ja	ka		
B-29							35	07	45	27		
6							te	ko	ri	ka		
							te	ko	ri,ja	ka		

As previously stated, perhaps Duhoux will find the “Greek hypothesis” more palatable with a high correspondence between PHd sign groups and both LB and the Greek language. Substituting Linear B for Duhoux’s Linear A, Berres’ low bar of “at least four words”, is easily exceeded as demonstrated by the *PHd Lexicon*.

Table 1: PHd Lexicon

with correspondences in Linear B (LB) and Arcado-Cypriot (LC)

Dem. = Demotic Greek

Sign Group	Field(s)	Linear-Script Correspondence(s)	Inscription(s)	Proposed Translation	Proposed Definition
<i>a-k^ha-i-jo</i>	A-01 A-04	LB <i>a-ka-i-je-ja</i> LB <i>e-ke-a</i> LB <i>e-ke-i-ja</i> LB <i>e-ke-ja</i> LB <i>we-ke-i-ja</i> LB <i>a-ka-i-jo</i> LB <i>wa-ke-i-jo</i> LB <i>we-ke-i-jo</i>	TH Of 27 KN V- 831 PY Va 1324 PY Vn 1339 KN Am 819 KN De 1084 KN Vc 177+ PY Jn 927	<i>ἀχαία</i> <i>Ἀχαία</i> <i>Ἀχαιός</i> <i>Cf. ἀχέω</i>	‘grief’ ‘Achaea’ ‘Achaean’ ‘to grieve, to mourn’
<i>a²-ku-tu-to</i>	B-25			<i>ἀκάττυτος</i>	‘not stitched’ i.e. ‘new’ (of shoes)
<i>a-tu-pte-ki-jo</i>	A-20	LB <i>a.i-ku-pi-ti-jo</i>	KN DB 1105	> * <i>α-τυπητέος</i> <i>Cf. τυπητέος</i>	*‘to be unbeaten’ ‘to be beaten’
<i>de-ma-ma</i>	A-28			> <i>δέδημαι</i>	pf. pass. of <i>δαμάζω</i> and <i>δέμω</i> ; of maidens, to make subject to a husband.
<i>e-a-mu-ka</i>	B-19			> <i>ιαμβύκη</i>	‘a musical instrument’
<i>e-ka-ti-jo</i>	B-14	LB <i>a-ke-si-ja</i> LB <i>a-ke-ti-jo</i> LB <i>e-ka-te-jo</i> LB <i>e-ke-si-jo</i> LB <i>je-ki-si-ja</i> LB <i>e-ki-si-jo</i> LB <i>e-ko-si-ja</i> LB <i>e-qe-si-ja</i> LB <i>e-qe-si-jo</i> <i>Cf. LC a-ke-ta-i</i> <i>Cf. LC a-ke-ti</i> <i>Cf. LC a-ke-ti-se</i> <i>Cf. LB e-qe-ta-i</i>	KN Ap 637 PY An 209 KN Sf 4418 PY Cn 4 KN Lc 527 KN Am 821+ MED Zg 1 KN Ld 571+ KN Lc 646 in ICS or KA ICS 114 KA 60 PY An 607	<i>Ἑκάταϊος</i> Dor. <i>ἔκατι</i> for <i>ἔκητι</i> Dor. <i>ἀγέτις</i> for <i>ἠγέτις</i>	‘of or for Hecate’ ‘because of, by virtue of’ ‘leader’
<i>e-ke-ma</i>	B-16	LB <i>a-qe-mo[?]</i>	KN Db 1160	> <i>ἄκημα</i>	‘cure, relief’
<i>e-o</i>	A-11 A-17	LB <i>e-o</i>	PY Eb 173+	<i>ἔω</i>	‘to release, to utter’
<i>e-zu</i>	A-02	<i>Cf. LB e-zo-wo</i>	KN Xe 5900+	> * <i>ἔζω</i> for <i>ἴζω</i>	‘to place, to set’
<i>e-zu-ki-jo</i>	A-06	LB <i>i-ja-zo-qi-jo</i>	PY Un 1193	> <i>ἐξοχία</i>	‘eminence, a piece of rising ground’
<i>ka-ku-pte-ze*ka-ki-jo</i>	A-09	LB <i>ka-ki-jo</i> LB <i>ke-ki-jo</i> LB <i>iki-ki-jo</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ki</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ki-de</i>	KN So 894 PY An 657 KN Da 1435 PY An 197+ PY An 654+	> * <i>τά κυπτάζεις κᾶκίω</i> > <i>κηκίω</i> > <i>κηκίω</i> > <i>κηκίς</i> > <i>κηκίδα</i>	*‘the lurking spring’
<i>ka-mu-no</i>	B-27			> <i>κάμνον</i>	*‘hardpressed, embattled’
<i>ke²-ko-ra-ma</i>	B-13				
<i>ke²-ko-ra-ma-no</i>	B-05 B-10	<i>Cf. LB ke-ka-u-me-no</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ke-me-na</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ke-me-no</i>	PY Ta 641 PY Ep 704 PY Ep 704	> <i>κεκορημένος</i> > <i>κεκαρμένα</i> > <i>κεκαρμένος</i>	*‘satiated, satisfied’; thus, *‘appreciation, approval’ ‘satiation’ i.e. ‘consumption’ through burning (<i>καίω</i> ‘to burn’) and cutting (<i>κείρω</i> ‘to cut, to shear’)

<i>ke²-lu-ka</i>	A-25			> κάλυκη Cf. <i>calyx</i>	Dem. ‘cover’
<i>ke-re-e-zu</i>	B-24	LB <i>ke-re-za</i>	PY Aa 762+	> κράζω	‘to call for, to clamor for’
<i>ke-re-pte-te ta</i>	B-15			*Κρήπητά ? < <i>ke-re-te</i> > Κρήτη ‘Crete’ + <i>pte-te-ta</i> <> ποτητά ‘fowl, birds’	metaphor for ‘refugees, i.e. tourists, visitors’, or even ‘ex patriots.’
<i>ke-pi-k^ho-ki-jo</i>	A-27			<i>untranslated</i>	
<i>ki*ko-ri-ja-ka</i>	A-26			> κύριακή or > (Αγια) Κυριακή	‘of belonging to a lord’ or ‘Haghia Kyriaki’
<i>ki*ko-ro</i>	A-07	LB <i>ti-ko-ro</i>	PY Cn 1197	> *κη χορός	* ‘dance place’
<i>ki-pi-ta</i>	A-30			> κηπίδες	‘garden’, metaphor for κηπεύω ‘to cultivate’
<i>ki*po-ta-ke</i>	B-26			*πόταγε, for Dor. πρόσαγε	‘brought to’
<i>ko-i-te-ta-jo</i>	B-03			*κοιτηταιο > κοιταῖος Cf. κοιτάτηριον	‘lair of the wild beast’ ‘bed chamber’
<i>ko-ku-re-u-ti</i>	B-04			*κοκυρεύτι > κορκυρεύεται	‘exhausted; *hibernating’
<i>ko-pi+me-e</i>	A-21	LB <i>ko-pi</i>	KN Ap 639	> *κοπι+μείς	*‘ <i>kopis</i> month’
<i>ko-pi-no-ki-jo</i>	B-30	Cf. LB <i>ko-pi-na</i>	PY Ep 613	*κόφινος	‘basket’; metaphor for ‘debt’
<i>ko-ri-ja</i>	B-01	Cf. LB <i>ko-ri-jo</i> Cf. LB <i>ko-ri-ja-da-na</i> Cf. LB <i>ko-ri-ja-do-no</i>	KN Db 1267+ MY Ge 605 MY Ga 674+	χόριος, χορείος	‘of or belonging to a chorus or dance’
<i>ko-ri-ja-ko</i> See <i>te*ko-ri-ja-ka</i>	B-07			> κύριακός	‘lord, master’
<i>ko-ri-ja-ma</i>	A-29 B-11			> *κόρευμα = κορεία [B-11] > *χόρευμα [A-29] Cf. > *κόρημα [A-29] or > *χώρημα [A-29]	‘maidenhood’ ‘choral dance’ ‘sweepings, refuse’ or ‘space, room’
<i>ko-ro-ki-jo</i>	A-10 A-13 A-16	LB <i>ko-ro-ki-ja</i> LB <i>ko-ro-ti-ja</i>	PY Ab 372+ KN Ld 587+	> κροτέω	to smite’ i.e. *‘to clap’
<i>ku*e-zu-ki-jo</i>	A-31	LB <i>i-ja-zo-qi-jo</i>	PY Un 1193	> *ἔξοχία	‘eminence, a piece of rising ground’
<i>ku*e-zu-ko-te²</i>	B-23			> *ἔξοχότης	‘ <i>eminentia</i> ’ or ‘eminence’ ‘fame or recognized superiority, esp. within a sphere or profession’
<i>ku-ta-ki-jo</i>	A-24	LB <i>ku-ta-si-jo</i> LB <i>ku-ta-ti-jo</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-ja</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-jo</i>	KN Da 1394 KN Ga 419+ PY Ta 713+ PY Ta 707	> κτήσιος	‘protector of one’s property’
<i>ku-ta-ta-jo</i>	A-24 error	LB <i>ku-te-ta-jo</i>	PY Ta 707	> *κτητέος	‘to be possessed’
<i>ku-tu-i-ja*mu-ka-jo</i>	A-12 A-18	LB <i>ku-su-i-ja</i>]	TH Fq 278	> *κυττοία-μῦκάιος	*‘sound receptacles’
<i>ku-ze-to</i>	B-17			> *γάζετο epic impf of γάζω	‘was causing to retire’
<i>mu-i-de-ka</i>	B-09			> *μυιδέκα	*small laws, decrees’
<i>mu-i-de-ma</i>	B-02			> *μυιδέμας	*‘small, bodily frame’
<i>mu-ri-na-no</i>	B-22			> *μυρίνινος	‘myrrh’ (of color)
<i>pi-ra-ko-jo</i>	B-20	LB <i>pi-ra-ki-jo</i>	KN Vf 1002	> *περιέχω	‘to embrace, to surround’
<i>sa-pe-ku-ta</i>	A-08	Cf. LB <i>sa-pa-ka-te-ri-ja</i>	KN C- 941	> σφάκτης > σφάκτρια	‘priest’ ‘priestess’
<i>ta*ku-tu-ko</i>	B-06			> *τά κτύκος = τά κτύπος	‘the sound of many voices’
<i>te*ko-ri-ja-ka</i> See <i>ko-ri-ja-ko</i>	B-29			> *τε κύριακός	< ‘lord, master’
<i>te*ko-ro</i>	A-23	LB <i>ti-ko-ro</i> Cf. LB <i>ko-ro</i>	PY Cn 1197 PY Cn 131	> *τε χορός χορός	‘the chorus’ ‘chorus, round dance’

<i>te*ku-ko</i>	B-08	<i>Cf. LB ko-ku</i>	KN Dh 1240	> *τέ κόκκῶ > *τέ κοῦκκος	‘cuckoo’ = κόκκυξ ‘stammerer’
<i>te*pi-ta-ko</i>	B-21	LB <i>pi-ta-ke-u</i>	PY Jn 389	> *τε πτάκος	‘a cowering (animal), i.e. a hare
<i>te*po-ta-ta-ma</i>	B-18			> *τε ποτητάμα	*‘winged (things)’
<i>te-sa-i</i>	A-05	LB <i>te-se-e</i>	PY Na 531	> *στάσει	‘position or standing, state, of a person’
<i>te*sa-me-ki-jo</i>	A-22	LB <i>sa-me-ti-jo</i> LB <i>sa-mu-ta-jo</i>	KN K- 875 PY Jn 389	> *τε σημάτιον	‘a small omen’
<i>to-re</i>	A-19	LB <i>to-re</i>	PY Xa 412	*τορη > τορέω	‘to bore, to pierce’ metaphor ‘to proclaim in shrill, piercing tones’
<i>tu-ke</i>	A-14	LC <i>tu-ke</i>	KA 3457	> τύχη	‘fate, fortune, providence’
<i>wa-na-te-ka*ka-ki-jo</i>	A-03 A-15	LB <i>wa-na-ka-te</i> LB <i>wa-na-ke-te</i> <i>Cf. LB wa-na-ko-to</i> LB <i>ka-ki-jo</i> LB <i>ke-ki-jo</i> LB <i>ji-ki-jo</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ki</i> <i>Cf. LB ke-ki-de</i>	KN So 894 PY An 657 KN So 894 HV Wq 117 PY An 657 KN Da 1435 PY An 197+ PY An 654+	> ἄνακτες > ἄνακτες <i>Cf. ἀνατήκω</i> ἀνακτός > *ἀνατήκα-κᾶκίω > κηκίω > κηκίω > κηκίς > κηκίδα	‘king, lord, master’ ‘to melt’ *‘melting spring’ ‘drawn from a spring’
<i>u-tu-na-jo</i>	B-28	LB <i>u-ta-ni-jo</i>	KN B- 807	> *Ἀθηναῖος	‘Athenian’
<i>zu-ke-ma</i>	B-12			> *σχῆμα	‘form, shape, figure’

It is worth noting that the combined, 20% ratio of the signs in the proposed K-, K², and K^h- series of the Phaistos disc roughly mirrors the combined, 19% ratio of the signs in the K- and Q- series in LB.

Sound changes on the Phaistos disc

As demonstrated in the previous table, the sound changes from σ or τ to κ, as highlighted in the prolific suffix, *12-^{*}02, or -*ki-jo* constitute one of the most interesting linguistic features of the Phaistos disc. This triad is demonstrated in the corrected, sign group, A-24 (18-06-12-02), transcribed as *ku-ta-ki-jo* and alternately transcribed in LB as follows:

<i>ku-ta-ki-jo</i>	A-24	LB <i>ku-ta-si-jo</i> LB <i>ku-ta-ti-jo</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-ja</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-jo</i>	KN Da 1394 KN Ga 419+ PY Ta 713+ PY Ta 707	> κτήσιος	‘protector of one’s property’
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In LB, there is at least one other pair of sign groups that reflects the κ/τ alternation: *o-da-ku-we-ta* [KN So 4435+] (alt. *o-da-ke-we-ta*) and *o-da-tu-we-ta* [KN So 894].

The κ / τ / ζ alternation in *ki-jo* / *ti-jo* / *si-jo* may be compared to Thess. κίς, Attic τίς, and Cyp.-Arc. σίς ‘anyone, anything’. Cf. the dominant, LB suffix, *si-jo* (179 occurrences).

The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc

This section defies easy articulation, due in large part to the limits of my linguistic understanding; however, it is not beyond my ability to observe and to speculate. For lack of a better term, I will characterize these four, initial, sign-group elements as *proclitics*. Perhaps my speculations will be proved correct; perhaps not.

In July 1952, Ventris appeals to Chadwick for collaboration on a scholarly submission to the *Journal of Hellenic Studies* (JHS). To Ventris’ concern about the absence of the definite article in Mycenaean Greek, Chadwick replies that “[t]he definite article ought not to be present, as it is not fully developed in

Homer. . . . I should have been much more worried if you *had* found the article.”¹²⁵ Present or not, articles in LB are generally unrecognized

And, yet, the Phaistos disc, if the presumed MM II/III dating (ca. 1700 BCE) is correct, appears to belie Chadwick’s assertion. In seven, sign groups (A-05, A-22, and A-26; B-08, B-18, B-21, and B-29), the initial sign is PHd *35, recognizable as AB *004 TE. These sign groups cannot be translated without isolating the proclitic article, much in the same way that such articles are isolated in Arc.-Cyp. (*aka* LC). Cf. the role of the proclitic, definite article *to-* in *to-i-e-re-o-se* [ICS 17] and *to-i-e-re-wo-se* [ICS 255], alternates that may be translated as τό ἱερεύς, Ion. τό ἱερῆος, or Cyp. τό ἱερῆφος ‘the diviner, the priest, the sacrificer’. Cf. also LB *i-je-re-u* [PY Eo 247] and Arc.-Cyp. **i-ye-re-u-se** [ICS 90, 91].¹²⁶ Alternately, cf. *to-i-pa-si-le-wo-se* > τοι βασιλέως ‘of the kings’ [ICS 117].

Following are my proposals for the four, proclitic signs found on the Phaistos disc:

PHd *12 KI, in three of four sign groups:

- 1) *ki*ko-ri-ja-ka* [A-26] (see also *ti*ko-ri-ja-ka* [B-29]),
- 2) *ki*ko-ro* [A-12], and
- 3) *ki*po-ta-ke* [B-26].

I initially treated this sign as an alternation of τις, τι, an indefinite pronoun for *anyone, anything*, but have since changed my mind. I now believe that it is the proclitic version of the locative enclitic κη, πη ‘somewhere, anywhere’ (see the broader discussion under PHd *12 KI), especially when considering the difference between *ki*ko-ro* [A-12] and *te*ko-ro* [A-23].

PHd *18 KU, in two of five sign groups:

- 1) *ku-e-zu-ki-jo* [A-31] and
- 2) *ku*e-zu-ko-te²* [B-23].

I initially regarded this proclitic as an alternation of tú, σύ, second-person pronouns for ‘thou’. However, this second-person reference does not make sense in context and may be linguistically premature in the Greek language. I now consider the possibility that it is simply a linguistic appendage akin to the tendency of the Thessalian language to affix κ to some words, like κάπᾶνη for ἀπήνη ‘four-wheeled wagon’.¹²⁷

PHd 24 TA² occurs in just one sign group:

- 1) *ta²*ku-tu-ko* [B-06].

Perhaps an alternation of the prolific PHd *35 TE > τέ.

PHd *35 TE, in six of seven sign groups:

- 1) *te*ko-ri-ja-ka* [B-29] (see also *ki*ko-ri-ja-ka* [A-26]),
- 2) *te*ko-ro* [A-23] (see also *ki*ko-ro* [A-12]),
- 3) *te*ku-ko* [B-08],
- 4) *te*pi-ta-ko* [B-21],
- 5) *te*po-ta-ta-ma* [B-18], and
- 6) *te*sa-me-ki-jo* [A-22].

In PHd, used perhaps an indefinite pronoun, τέ, linguistically preceding its association with the second-person pronoun, σύ.

Parallels in the linear scripts

Scrutiny of the PHd signary reveals numerous signs with obvious and not-so-obvious parallels in linear scripts A (LA) and B (LB) and in Arcado-Cypriot (Arc.-Cyp. or LC). The obvious parallels are readily

¹²⁵ Robinson (2002) 112.

¹²⁶ In LC, asterisks are used to isolate a sign group within a transcription that lacks word separation.

¹²⁷ L&S 2nd s.v. Κ κ κάππα.

attested by other scholars. The less obvious parallels include both signs attested by one or two scholars** and signs without noted parallels.

Obvious parallels include

- PHd *12 with AB *78 QE,
- PHd *35 with AB *04 TE,
- PHd *29 with B *80 MA,
- PHd *45 with AB *76 RA₂ (RIJA)

Less obvious but proposed parallels include

- PHd *01 with A *46 JE**,
- PHd *02 with AB *36 JO,
- PHd *07 with Arc.-Cyp. KO (?),
- PHd *09 with AB *37 TI and Arc.-Cyp. TI,
- PHd *13 with A *79 ZU**,
- PHd *15 with AB *02 DA,
- PHd *16 with AB *05 TO,
- PHd *17 with B *72 PE,
- PHd *18 with A *81 KU,
- PHd *19 with A *31 SA,
- PHd *34 with AB *45 DE,
- PHd *37 with AB *06 NA,
- PHd *38 with Arc.-Cyp. A,
- PHd *39 with AB *27 RE,

Sign-Group Analysis

In addition to the 45 signs and the 61 sign groups, the disc features three types of punctuation. Least controversial is the vertical line that separates sign groups.

In a dextroverse reading, favored by the majority of scholars, the five, vertically aligned dots, placed perpendicular to the edge of each side, are construed to mark the beginning of the text in a dextroverse reading:

“The spiral-shaped lines and the symbols were created with direction from the periphery to the centre and thence from right to left. For this reason, it is considered almost certain that the row of symbols was read from the periphery to the centre, starting from the vertical line with the five dots, which is considered to signify the start of the row of symbols.”¹²⁸

Moreover, the oblique strokes, or “thorns” (\), placed on the bottom edges of 18, seemingly random signs, are construed to mark the last signs of their respective sign groups.¹²⁹

Instead, I favor a sinistroverse reading in which the five dots mark the last, rather than the first, word on each side. Furthermore, I argue that the thorns mark the beginnings of phrases and are, perhaps, functionally similar to the crosses, as mentioned by Pendlebury, that sometimes mark sign groups on hieroglyphic seals,¹³⁰ seemingly to mark reading direction.

¹²⁸ Anastasiadou (2016) 17. Cf. the parallel, fine-ware motif of five, vertical dots in Sanavia (2017) 88, fig. 14.

¹²⁹ Anastasiadou (2019) 215, with reference to the chapter, “The so-called thorn” in Berres; Achterberg (2021) 66, D46.

¹³⁰ Pendlebury (1939) 141.

Beginning with side A, and reading from left to right, sign groups are listed on *Table 2* in the order of appearance, and are followed by translation and analysis of the sign groups in context.

Table 2: Transcription and Translation			
<i>Thorns</i> are indicated by shaded, field numbers.			
A-01	38-03-10	<i>a- k^ha-i.ja</i>	Ἀχαΐα ‘Ak ^h aia’
A-02	01-13	<i>e-zu</i>	*ἔζω ‘situated (in)’
A-03	21-37-35-27-27-12-02	<i>wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo</i>	*ἀνατήκα-κακίω ‘melting spring’
A-04	38-03-10	<i>a- k^ha-i.ja</i>	ἀχαΐα ‘weeps’
A-05	35-19-23	<i>te-sa-i</i>	*στάσει ‘stood’
A-06	01-13-12-02	<i>e-zu-ki-jo</i>	*ἔξοχία ‘raised’
A-07	12-26-31	<i>ki-ko-ro</i>	*κι χορός ‘the dance ground’
A-08	19-17-18-06	<i>sa-pe-ku-ta</i>	σφάκτης ‘priest’
A-09	22-17-32-14-27-12-02	<i>ka-ku-pte-ze-ka-ki-jo</i>	τά κυπτάζεις- κηκίω ‘the lurking spring’
A-10	26-31-12-02	<i>ko-ro-ki-jo</i>	*κροτέω ‘(the crowd) applauded’
A-11	01-28	<i>e-o</i>	ἔω ‘to amplify’
A-12	18-23-10-25-27-02	<i>ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo</i>	*κυττοία-μυκάλιος ‘sound receptacles’
A-13	26-31-12-02	<i>ko-ro-ki-jo</i>	*κροτέω ‘(the crowd) applauded’
A-14	23-33	<i>tu-ke</i>	τύχη ‘providence (of)’
A-15	21-37-35-27-27-12-02	<i>wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo</i>	*ἀνατήκα-κακίω ‘melting spring’
A-16	26-31-12-02	<i>ko-ro-ki-jo</i>	*κροτέω ‘(the crowd) applauded’
A-17	01-28	<i>e-o</i>	ἔω ‘to amplify’
A-18	18-23-10-25-27-02	<i>ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo</i>	*κυττοία-μυκάλιος ‘sound receptacles’
A-19	11-39	<i>to-re</i>	τορέω ‘in shrill, piercing tones’
A-20	38-23-32-12-02	<i>a-tu-pte-ki-jo</i>	*α-τυπητέος ‘unbeaten’
A-21	07-40-41-01	<i>ko-pi-me-e</i>	*κοπιμείς ‘kopis month’
A-22	35-19-41-12-02	<i>te-sa-me-ki-jo</i>	*τε σημάτιον ‘a small omen (to begin)’
A-23	35-26-31	<i>te-ko-ro</i>	*τε χορός ‘the dance’
A-24	■-18-06-06-02	■-ku-ta-ta-jo <i>error</i>	κτητέος ‘to be possessed’ <i>error</i>
A-24	■-18-06-12-02	■-ku-ta-ki-jo	*κτησίος ‘protector of one’s property’
A-25	08-44-27	<i>ke-lu-ka</i>	*κάλυκη ‘veil’
A-26	12-07-45-27	<i>ki-ko-ri.ja-ka</i>	*τε Κυριακή ‘the lord’
A-27	33-40-04-12-02	<i>ke-pi-k^ho-ki-jo</i>	<i>untranslated</i>
A-28	34-29-29	<i>de-ma-ma</i>	*δέδμημα ‘concubines’
A-29	07-45-29	<i>ko-ri.ja-ma</i>	*κόρημα ‘dance ground’
A-30	12-40-24	<i>ki-pi-ta</i>	κηπίδες ‘garden’, a metaphor for ‘freshening, vivifying’
A-31	18-01-13-12-02	<i>ku-e-zu-ki-jo</i>	*ku ἔξοχία ‘eminence, rising ground’
Five dots			

B-01	07-45	<i>ko-ri.ja</i>	*χορία ‘hunt’
B-02	25-23-34-29	<i>mu-i-de-ma</i>	*μυιδέμα ‘small beast’
B-03	07-23-35-06-02	<i>ko-i-te-ta-jo</i>	*κοιτηταῖο ‘bed chamber, lair’
B-04	07-18-39-30-09	<i>ko-ku-re-u-ti</i>	*κο(ρ)κυρεῦτι ‘exhausted, hibernating’
B-05	08-07-36-29-22	<i>ke-ko-ra-ma-no</i>	κεκορημένος *‘satisfaction, approval’
B-06	24-18-23-07	<i>ta-ku-tu-ko</i>	*τά κτύπος ‘the sound of many voices’, <i>i.e.</i> the crowd
B-07	07-45-07	<i>ko-ri.ja-ko</i>	*κῶριακός ‘lord’
B-08	35-18-07	<i>te-ku-ko</i>	*κοῦκκος ‘cuckoo’ metaphor ‘stammerer’ <i>i.e.</i> reciter
B-09	25-23-34-27	<i>mu-i-de-ka</i>	*μυιδέκα ‘small laws, <i>i.e.</i> decrees’
B-10	08-07-36-29-22	<i>ke-ko-ra-ma-no</i>	κεκορημένος *‘satisfaction, approval’
B-11	07-45-29	<i>ko-ri.ja-ma</i>	*χόρευμα ‘the choral dance’
B-12	13-08-29	<i>zu-ke²-ma</i>	σχῆμα ‘form, shape, figure’; in dancing, ‘gestures, postures’
B-13	08-07-36-29	<i>ke²-ko-ra-ma</i>	*κεκόρημα ‘applause’
B-14	01-27-09-02	<i>e-ka-ti-jo</i>	*ἐκᾶτιος ‘because of, by virtue of’
B-15	33-39-32-35-06	<i>ke-re-pte-te-ta</i>	*Κρηπητήτα ‘Cretan tourist, visitor’
B-16	01-33-29	<i>e-ke-ma</i>	*ἄκημα ‘cure, relief’
B-17	18-14-16	<i>ku-ze-to</i>	*χάζετο ‘rest’
B-18	35-20-24-24-29	<i>te-po-ta-ta-ma</i>	*τε ποτητάμα ‘winged (things)’
B-19	01-38-25-27	<i>e-a-mu-ka</i>	*ιαμβύκη ‘iambuka’, a kind of lyre used by <i>iambistai</i>
B-20	40-36-26-2	<i>pi-ra-ko-jo</i>	*περιέχω ‘to embrace, to encompass, to surround’
B-21	35-40-24-07	<i>te-pi-ta-ko</i>	*τε πτάκός ‘the cowering animal, <i>i.e.</i> hare’
B-22	35-42-37-22	<i>mu-ri-na-no</i>	*μυρίνινος ‘myrrh, myrrh colored’
B-23	18-01-13-07-15	<i>ku-e-zu-ko-te²</i>	*τύ ἐξοχότης ‘your (<i>i.e.</i> his) eminence’
B-24	33-39-01-13	<i>ke-re-e-zu</i>	*κράζω ‘to call for, to clamor for’
B-25	43-18-23-16	<i>a²-ku-tu-to</i>	ἀκάπτῦτος ‘not stitched, not repaired (of shoes), <i>i.e.</i> new’
B-26	12-20-24-33	<i>ki-po-ta-ke</i>	*κι πόταγε < Dor. for πρόσαγε ‘brought to’
B-27	27-25-22	<i>ka-mu-no</i>	κάμνον ‘to be hardpressed in contest’, <i>i.e.</i> *‘embattled’
B-28**	05-23-37-02	<i>u-ta-na-jo</i>	*Ἀθαναῖος ‘Athenian’
B-29	35-07-45-27	<i>te-ko-ri.ja-ka</i>	*τε Κυριακή ‘the lord’
B-30	07-40-22-12-02	<i>ko-pi-no-ki-jo</i>	*κόφινος ‘basket’, metaphor ‘debt’
Five dots			
** I disagree with the placement of the thorn, here, and argue for phrase continuity.			

Regarding the polyvalence of PHd *23, *Table 3a* outlines my proposals for the ten, sign groups.

A-14									23	33				
1									tu	ke				
B-28								05	23	37	02			
2								u	tu	na	jo			
B-09								25	23	34	27			
3								mu	i	de	ka			
B-02								25	23	34	29			
4								mu	i	de	ma			
B-03								07	23	35	06	02		
5								ko	i	te	ta	jo		
A-20								38	23	32	12	02		
6								a	tu	pte	ki	jo		
A-12								18	23	10	25	27	02	
A-18								18	23	10	25	27	02	
7-8								ku	tu	i,ja	mu	ka	jo	
A-05							35	19	23					
9							te	sa	i					
B-06							24	18	23	07				
10							ta ²	ku	tu	ko				
B-25							43	18	23	16				
11							a	ku	tu	to				

Regarding the polyvalence of PHd *45, *Table 3b* outlines my proposals for the five, sign groups.

B-01								07	45				
1								ko	ri,ja				
B-07								07	45	07			
2								ko	ri,ja	ko			
A-29								07	45	29			
B-11								07	45	29			
3-4								ko	ri,ja	ma			

A-26							12	07	45	27								
5							ki	ko	ri.ja	ka								
B-29							35	07	45	27								
6							te	ko	ri.ja	ka								

← ◆ ◆ ◆ →

Greek Translation

A-01 to A-04	38	03	10		01	13		21	37	35	27	27	12	02		38	03	10		
	<i>a</i>	<i>k^ha</i>	<i>i.ja</i>		<i>e</i>	<i>zu</i>		<i>wa</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>a</i>	<i>k^ha</i>	<i>i.ja</i>		
	Ἀχαΐα				*ἔζω			*ἀνατήκα-κακίω							ἀχαΐα					
	Ἀχαΐα *ἔζω *ἀνατήκα-κακίω ἀχαΐα. “Situated in Ak ^h aia where the melting spring weeps.”																			

A-01

(see also A-04)

a-k^h-a-i.ja > Ἀχαΐα < ἀχαΐα ‘grief’

Well documented in Homer, the foundation of Achaean distress is ἀχαΐα ‘grief’: “One of several, collective terms used by Homer to describe the Greeks, the Achaeans are indeed grief stricken – the Achaeans grieve the death of Agamemnon, Achilles grieves the death of Patroclus, Menelaus grieves the loss of Odysseus, and Ἀχαΐα, an epithet of Demeter, grieves the loss of her daughter. Quite simply, the Achaeans *ache*.” Moreover, ἠχή and Dor. ἀχά ‘sound’ appear to be at the root of ἄχος ‘distress, pain’, from ἀχέω ‘to grieve, to mourn’.¹³¹ Thus, *a-k^h-a-i.ja* is both a toponymic reference to Ἀχαΐα, a province in Greece, and a generic noun, its probable foundation.

τὸ Ἀχαϊκόν ‘the Ak^haian League’ was a confederation of cities, which, at its peak, controlled the entire Peloponnese, with the exception of southern Laconia. Following the Ak^haian war, the league was dissolved in 146 BC with the commencement of Roman rule. Nevertheless, Amyclae continued to maintain its independence as an Achaean town.

Godart observes that “[t]he Mycenaean period coincides with the [Achaean occupation] of the Mesara Plain and of Phaistos itself.”¹³² Regarding the provenance of the Phaistos disc, I propose that an Achaean tourist, perhaps a palace potter/scribe, travelled to Laconia to attend the *kopis* at Amyklae and created the disc to commemorate this festival, perhaps as a gift or as a personal souvenir. The clay for the disc, which “is not of this island”, was perhaps gathered in Laconia, and brought back to Phaistos by the potter/scribe who thought to innovate with the use of fine-ware stamps. If my hypothesis holds, then the disc would qualify as “a Cretan object of foreign origin”.

Cross Reference: *ko-pi-me-e* [A-21].

A-02

e-zu > *ἔζω for ἵζω ‘to set, to place’.

Cf. ἕζομαι ‘to sit’ and the imperative, ἕζεο ‘sit!’ Cf. also Jap. 座 *za* ‘seat; place, position’.

Initially assuming PHd *01 E, I began by searching the Greek lexicon for two-letter words beginning with E. Thus, I considered Dor. εἶ ‘where’, which would presume PHd *13 I, supported by its

¹³¹ Leonhardt (2020) 8.

¹³² Godart (1995) 46.

resemblance to that letter. However, I changed my mind with the suggestion of a correspondence between PHd *13 and AB *79 ZU.

If one is inclined to argue for PHd *13 KSU, rather than ZU, then *e-ksu* > ἔξω ‘outside’ and perhaps ‘beyond’ is plausible, though syntactically awkward. Nevertheless, “Ak^haia is either “situated (where)” or “beyond (where)” the melting spring weeps.

Cross Reference: PHd *13 ZU

A-03

(see also A-15)

wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo > *ἀνατήκα-κακίω ‘a melting spring’, from ἀνατήκω ‘to melt’+ and Doric κᾱκίω ‘to bubble up, to gush’. The final, three signs of both A-03 and A-15 may be compared with LB *ka-ki-jo* [KN So 894] and alt. *ke-ki-jo* [PY An 657]. A translation of κηκίω and Doric κᾱκίω is supported by both *ke-ki* > κηκίς [PY An 192] and *ke-ki-de* > κηκίδα ‘anything that flows or gushes’ [PY An 654+]. Note that, in LB, these words occur in a military context.

The isolation of the three, final signs makes it easier to determine the first word of the compound; thus, *wa-na-te-ka*ka-ki-jo* > *ἀνατήκα-κηκίω. In early eastern/central Ionic, the initial, semivowel /w/ in iambus was dropped in favor of the subsequent vowel (see also B-19 *e-a-mu-ka*).¹³³

It is possible that *wa-na-te-ka* is a metathesis of *wa-na-ka-te* [KN Ga 675+]; however, metathesis is less likely with a latter translation of ἀνακτες ‘king, lord, master’. Cf. *wa-na-ko-to* > ἀνακτός ‘drawn from a spring, water’, found on a tablet [HV Wq 117] from the archive of Ἅγιος Βασίλειος in the Evrotas valley in Laconia.

Cross Reference: *ka-ku-pte-ze*ka-ki-jo* [A-09].

A-04

(see also A-01)

a-k^h-a-i.ja > ἀχαία

Generic ἀχαία ‘grief’ in A-04 is expressed as a metaphor to describe the ‘weeping’ of *wa-na-te-ka*ka-ki-jo* > *ἀνατήκα*κηκίω ‘melting spring’, similarly expressed in Homer’s *Odyssey*:

τῆς δ’ ἄρ’ ἀκουούσης ῥέε δάκρυα, τήκετο δὲ χρώς: ὡς δὲ χιῶν κατατήκετ’ ἐν ἀκροπόλοισιν ὄρεσσιν, ἦν τ’ Εὐῖρος κατέτηξεν, ἐπὶν Ζέφυρος καταχεύη: τηκομένης δ’ ἄρα τῆς ποταμοὶ πλήθουσι ῥέοντες: ὡς τῆς τήκετο καλὰ παρήϊα δάκρυ χεούσης, κλαιούσης ἐὼν ἄνδρα παρήμενον.¹³⁴

[as Penelope listened to the disguised Odysseus], her tears flowed and her face melted, as the snow melts on the lofty mountains, the snow which the East Wind thaws when the West Wind has strewn it; and, as it melts, the streams of the rivers flow full: so her fair cheeks melted as she wept and mourned for her husband, who even then was sitting by her side.

Πάτροκλος δ’ Ἀχιλῆϊ παρίστατο ποιμένι λαῶν δάκρυα θερμὰ χέων ὧς τε κρήνη μελάνυδρος, ἣ τε κατ’ αἰγίλιπος πέτρης δνοφερὸν χέει ὕδωρ.¹³⁵

Then Patroclus drew near to Achilles with tears welling from his eyes, as from some spring whose crystal stream falls over the ledges of a high precipice.

The reference to the numerous, ‘weeping springs’ of Ak^haia provides regional context and a plausible foundation for LB as the underlying language of the disc, further compelling research into the rivers of Laconia. For several reasons, the Εὐρώτας ‘Evrotas’, the main river of Laconia and a major river of the Peloponnese, is the most logical choice. Cf. LB. *e-u-ru-wo-ta* [PY Eb 156], the springs of which are located

¹³³ Giannakis (2014) s.v. “Iambic Poetry, Diction of” 188.

¹³⁴ Hom. *Od.* 19.204-209.

¹³⁵ Hom. *Il.* 16.2.

near Pellana and Skortsinos. Tributaries course down Mt. Taygetos, the western flank, and Mt. Parnon, the eastern flank, of the Evrotas valley.

A-05 \ to A-09	35	19	23		01	13	12	02		12	26	31		19	17	18	06			
	<i>te</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>i</i>		<i>e-</i>	<i>zu-</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>ki</i>	<i>ko²</i>	<i>ro</i>		<i>sa-</i>	<i>pe</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>ta</i>			
	*στάσει			*ἔξοχία					*κι χορός					σφάκτης						
	27	18	32	14	27	12	02													
	<i>ka</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>pte</i>	<i>ze</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>													
	*τά κυπτάζεις- κηκίω																			
	*στάσει *ἔξοχία σφάκτης *κι χορός *τά κυπτάζεις- κηκίω “The priest stood on a raised, dance ground near the lurking spring.”																			

A-05

te-sa-i > στάσει

Cf. LB *te-se-e* [PY Na 531], which appears to be related to LB *ta-so* > τάσσω [KN As 608] and *ta-to* > Attic τάττω [PY Cn 4] ‘to array, to marshall’ esp. in a military sense. In LC, *ta-se* [ICS 4+] and *ta-si* [ICS 193] alternately refer to τάσις ‘a raising, a straining, a stretching; tension’ esp. as it relates to τάξις ‘arrangement, order’ of soldiers.

This ‘arrangement’ appears to be at the root of the ubiquitous, LC *sa-ta-sa* [ICS 21] and *sa-ta-si** > στάσις (ἵστημι) ‘placing, setting’, present in the many, compounded titles and male names throughout the Cypriot inscriptions. Cf. *sa-ta-si-ku-po-ro-se* > Στασικυπρος ‘establishing’ or ‘leading Cyprus’ [ICS 217], from στησι- ‘establishing, exhibiting, leading’ + κυπρος ‘Cyprus’. Cf., also, the given name, Στασι ‘Stacy’.

In the context of the Phaistos disc, *te-sa-i* may simply refer to στάσει ‘the position or standing, the state’, of a person. Thus, ‘the priest stood’. Moreover, the ‘establishment’ in στησι-, and thus στάσει, may be extended to include θάσει ‘sit idle’

If one is inclined to argue for PHd *23 TU rather than for I, then *te-sa-tu* > ταξῆτος (Lat. *taxatus*) ‘to assess the worth of, to value’, though phonetically plausible, seems unlikely in context.

Cross Reference: PHd *23 I or TU

A-06

e-zu-ki-jo > *ἔξοχία ‘eminence, a piece of rising ground’. Cf. LB *i.ja-zo-qi-jo* [PY Un 1193].

Cross References: *ku-e-zu-ki-jo* [A-31] and *ku-e-zu-ko-da* [B-23].

A-07 *ki-ko²-ro* > *κι χορός, perhaps, ‘dance place’, i.e. ‘dance ground’. *ki-* is possibly the proclitic form of the ubiquitous, LB suffix, *-qe*, about which I make a case for a locative enclitic.¹³⁶

Cross References: PHd *12 KI; *te-ko-ro* > τε χορός ‘the dance’ [A-23].

A-08

sa-pe-ku-ta > σφάκτης ‘a slayer’ or ‘a priest’, is the masculine form of LB *sa-pa-ka-te-ri-ja* [KN C- 941] and alt. *pa-ke-te-ri-|ja* [MY Wt 506] > *σφάκτρια ‘priestess’. As ‘sacrificer’, the σφάκτης uses a σφαγίς ‘sacrificial knife’ to cut the throat or *esophagus*. Cf. φάγος ‘glutton’ and σφάζω ‘to slaughter, to slay by cutting the throat’.

Moreover, cf. the island of Σφακτηρία, which “cuts off” Navarino Bay.

¹³⁶ Leonhardt (2020).

A-09

ka-ku-pte-ze-ka-ki-jo > *τά κυπτάζεις- κηκίω, from κυπτάζεις ‘lurking’ + κηκίω ‘to bubble up, to gush’, appears to be a variation of *wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo* [A-03, A-15]. Greece is known for its numerous, therapeutic, thermal springs.

A-10 \ A-12	26	31	12	2
	<i>ko²</i>	<i>ro</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>
	*κροτέω			
	“The crowd applauded”			

A-10

(see also A-13 and A-16)

ko²-ro-ki-jo > κροτέω, poet. κορτέω ‘applause’. On side A, *ko²-ro-ki-jo* appears three times as a stand-alone phrase. Cf. LB *ko-ro-ki-ja* [PY AB 372+]. I have ruled out κρόκεος ‘saffron colored’, κροκήϊος ‘of saffron’.

A-11 \ to A-12	01	28		18	23	10	25	27	02										
	<i>e</i>	<i>o</i>		<i>ku</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>i.ja</i>	<i>mu</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>jo</i>										
	ἔω			*κυττοία-μῦκάιος															
	ἔω *κυττοία-μῦκάιος “Amplified by the sound receptacles.”																		

A-11

(see also A-17)

e-o > ἔω ‘to release, to utter’. Cf. LB *e-o* [PY Eb 173; Ep 613]. This word appears at the beginnings of two phrases on side A.

A-12

(see also A-18)

ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo > *κυττοία-μῦκάιος ‘sound receptacles’, from κυττοί ‘receptacles’ + μῦκάομαι ‘sound, bellow’. Cf. LB *ku-su-i.ja* [TH Fq 278]. According to D’Angour, the Greeks may have employed numerous devices to amplify sound, which included “placing hollow vessels at strategic locations.”¹³⁷ Pantos observes a parallel in Dem. κουτια ‘boxes’.¹³⁸

A-13 \ A-12	26	31	12	2
	<i>ko²</i>	<i>ro</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>
	*κροτέω			
	“The crowd applauded”			

¹³⁷ Davis (2017).

¹³⁸ Observation by Emmanuel “Manolis” Pantos in an email dated April 4, 2022.

A-13

(see also A-10 and A-16)

ko²-ro-ki-jo > κροτέω, poet. κορτέω ‘applause’.Cross Reference: *Sound changes on the Phaistos disc*, following decipherment.

A-14 \ to A-15	23	33		21	37	35	27	27	12	02									
	<i>tu</i>	<i>ke</i>		<i>wa</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>									
	τύχη			*ἀνατήκα-κηκίω															
	<p>τύχη *ἀνατήκα-κηκίω. “For the providence of the melting spring.”</p>																		

A-14*tu-ke* > τύχη ‘fate, fortune, providence’. Cf. LC *tu-ke* [KA 3457].**A-15**

(see also A-02)

wa-na-te-ka-ka-ki-jo > *ἀνατήκα-κηκίω ‘melting spring’Cross Reference: *ka-ku-pte-ze-ka-ki-jo* [A-09].

A-16 \ to A-15	26	31	12	2
	<i>ko²</i>	<i>ro</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>
	*κροτέω			
	“The crowd applauded”			

A-16

(see also A-10 and A-13)

ko²-ro-ki-jo > κροτέω, poet. κορτέω ‘applause’.

A-17 \ to A-19	01	28		18	23	10	25	27	02		11	39							
	<i>e</i>	<i>o</i>		<i>ku</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>i.ja</i>	<i>mu</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>to²</i>	<i>re</i>							
	ἔω			*κυττοία-μῦκάλιος								*τορη							
	<p>ἔω *κυττοία-μῦκάλιος *τορη “The sound receptacles amplified the shrill, piercing tones.”</p>																		

A-17

(see also A-11)

e-o > ἔω ‘to release, to utter’.**A-18**

(see also A-12)

ku-tu-i.ja-mu-ka-jo > *κυττοία-μῦκάλιος ‘sound receptacles’, from *κυττοί* ‘receptacles’ + *μῦκάλιομαι* ‘sound, bellow’. Cf. Dem. *κουτια* ‘boxes’.

A-19

to²-re > *τορέω* ‘to bore, to pierce’; as a metaphor, ‘to proclaim in shrill, piercing tones’. Cf. LB *to-re* [PY Xa 412].

A-20 to A-28	38	23	32	12	02		07	40	41	01		35	19	41	12	02				
	<i>a</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>pte</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>ko</i>	<i>pi</i>	<i>me</i>	<i>e</i>		<i>te</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>me</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>				
	*α-τυπητέος					*κοπιμείς					*τε σημάτιον									
	35	26	31		18	06	12	02			08	44	27		12	07	45	27		
	<i>te</i>	<i>ko²</i>	<i>ro</i>		<i>ku</i>	<i>ta</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>			<i>ke²</i>	<i>lu</i>	<i>ka</i>		<i>ki</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>	<i>ka</i>		
	*τε χορός				*κτήσιος				κἄλῦκη				*κι κυριακή							
	33	40	04	12	02		34	29	29											
	<i>ke</i>	<i>pi</i>	<i>k^ho</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>de</i>	<i>ma</i>	<i>ma</i>											
<i>untranslated</i>					*δέδμημαι															
*α-τυπητέος *κοπιμείς *τε σημάτιον *τε χορός *κτήσιος κἄλῦκη *κι Κυριακή <i>ke-pi- k^ho-ki-jo</i> *δέδμημαι “unbeaten, <i>kopis</i> month > a small omen for the lord’s concubines to begin the veil dance																				

The syntax of this phrase is rather challenging, but the gist is that, during the celebration of the *kopis* for an undefeated army, a small omen begins the veil dance by the lord’s concubines.

A-20

a-tu-pte-ki-jo > *α-τυπητέος ‘unbeaten’ or, perhaps, *undefeated < τυπητέος ‘to be beaten’ < τύπτε or τύψε ‘strike’.

This sign group appears to have at least one, perhaps two corrections, at both *12 and *02. The presence of a sign under *02 is obvious, but the original sign does not appear identical to any signs in the final syllabary; thus, it is plausible that the erroneous stamp was effectively eliminated from the signary.

A-21

ko-pi-me-e > *κοπιμείς ‘*kopis* month’, from κοπίς ‘chopper, cleaver’ or ‘a feast given to strangers by Lacedaemonians during certain festivals’ + μείς ‘month’. Cf. LB *ko-pi* [KN Ap 639]. *a-tu-pte-ki-jo ko-pi-me-e* > *α-τυπητέος *κοπιμείς ‘undefeated, *kopis* month’.

The *Hyakinthius* at Amyklae

The *κοπιμείς ‘*kopis* month’ perhaps recalls Ὑακίνθιος ‘*Hyakinthius*’, the presumed, early-spring month during which the Spartan festival of Ὑακίνθια ‘*Hyakinthia*’ was celebrated at the ancient city of Amyklae, just five km. south of Sparta on the western bank of the Evrotas river in Laconia. Cf. *e-u-ru-wo-ta* [PY Jn 310+], an LB reference, which may pertain to the river valley, whereas two additional references may pertain to visitors from that region.

Xenophon states that the Spartans would suspend their campaigns to attend the festival:

οἱ Ἀμυκλαῖοι αἰεί ποτε ἀπέρχονται εἰς τὰ Ὑακίνθια ἐπὶ τὸν παιᾶνα, εἴαν τε στρατοπεδεύομενοι

τυγχάνωσιν ἐάν τε ἄλλως πως ἀποδημοῦντες.¹³⁹

The Amyclaeans invariably go back home to the festival of the *Hyakinthia* for the paeon to [Amyklaios Apollo], whether they chance to be on a campaign or away from home for any other reason.

Likewise, Pausanias:

ἀφίκετο δὲ καὶ αὐθις ἐπὶ Κόρινθον στρατιᾶ: καὶ—ἐπήει γὰρ Ἵακίνθια—ἀφίησι τοὺς Ἀμυκλαιεῖς οἴκαδε ἀπελθόντας τὰ καθεστηκότα τῷ τε Ἀπόλλωνι καὶ Ἵακίνθῳ δρᾶσαι.¹⁴⁰

[Spartan king Agesilaus] again marched with an army against Corinth, and, as the festival Hyacinthia was at hand, he gave the Amycleans leave to go back home and perform the traditional rites in honor of Apollo and Hyacinthus.

The Spartans celebrated *Hyakinthia* to honor the death of the legendary Hyakinthos, the princely son of Amyklas and grandson of King Lakedaemon and his wife, Sparta, a daughter of Evrotas.¹⁴¹

Ἀμύκλας δὲ ὁ Λακεδαίμονος, βουλόμενος ὑπολιπέσθαι τι καὶ αὐτὸς ἐς μνήμην, πόλισμα ἔκτισεν ἐν τῇ Λακωνικῇ. γενομένων δὲ οἱ παίδων Ἵακίνθον μὲν νεώτατον ὄντα καὶ τὸ εἶδος κάλλιστον κατέλαβεν ἢ πεπρωμένη πρότερον τοῦ πατρός, καὶ Ἵακίνθου μνημᾶ ἐστὶν ἐν Ἀμύκλαις ὑπὸ τὸ ἄγαλμα τοῦ Ἀπόλλωνος.¹⁴²

“Amyklas, too, son of Lacedaemon, wished to leave some memorial behind him, and built a town in Laconia. Hyacinthus, the youngest and most beautiful of his sons, died before his father, and his tomb is in Amyclae below the image of Apollo.”

Lakedaemon (ca. 900s to 192 BCE), a city-state or prefecture within the province of ancient Laconia, was interchangeably used with *Sparta*, which was its principle settlement on the banks of the Evrotas river. “According to Pausanias, [Amyklae was] an ‘Achaian’ or pre-Dorian stronghold, incorporated by conquest as the fifth village of Sparta, probably early in the 8th c. B.C. Excavation has been almost entirely confined to the hill of Haghia Kyriaki. . . . [This] prehistoric settlement, which spanned the entire Bronze Age, was concentrated on the SE slopes; the historical site may have extended in an arc from N of the hill to modern Amyklae.”¹⁴³ Haghia Kyriaki is the site of the sanctuary of *Apollo Amyklaios*. See *te-ko-ri.ja-ka* [B-29].

According to legend, the beautiful Hyakinthos had attracted the love of both Apollo and Zephyros, the god of the west wind. One day, while Apollo and Hyakinthos are practicing with the discus, the jealous Zephyros causes the discus to strike and kill Hyakinthos. The grief-stricken Apollo refuses to allow the body of Hyakinthos to be borne away by Hades, and a flower blooms where the body lies.

περὶ δὲ ἀνέμου Ζεφύρου, καὶ ὡς ὑπὸ τοῦ Ἀπόλλωνος Ἵακίνθος ἀπέθανεν ἄκοντος, καὶ τὰ ἐς τὸ ἄνθος εἰρημένα τάχα μὲν ἂν ἔχοι καὶ ἄλλως, δοκεῖτω δὲ ἢ λέγεται.¹⁴⁴

As for Zephyros (the West Wind), how Apollon unintentionally killed Hyakinthos, and the story of the flower, we must be content with the legends, although perhaps they are not true history.

¹³⁹ Xen. *Hell.* 4.5.11

¹⁴⁰ Paus. 3.10.1.

¹⁴¹ *Ibid.* 3.1.2.

¹⁴² *Ibid.* 3.1.3.

¹⁴³ PECS (1976) s.v. Amyclae.

¹⁴⁴ Paus. 3.19.5.

In Greek myth, handsome men in the “bloom of youth” are routinely transformed into flowers.¹⁴⁵ To paraphrase the popular, American, folk song, “Where have all the soldiers gone? To graveyards, every one. Where have all the graveyards gone? To flowers, every one.”¹⁴⁶

Denoted by the Laconian κοπίς/κοπίζω¹⁴⁷, the Hyakinthia was held during the month of *Hyakinthius*, which, inferred from Ovid, appears to have coincided with the the vernal equinox, when “the melting spring weeps” [A-01 to A-04] and the hyacinths begin to bloom; thus, according to Nobili, the Hyakinthia celebrated the new year and “the renewal of the world.”¹⁴⁸

Te quoque, Amyclide, posuisset in aethere Phoebus, tristia si spatium ponendi fata dedissent. Qua licet, aeternus tamen es: quotiensque repellit ver hiemem piscique aries succedit aquoso, tu totiens oreris viridique in caespite flores.¹⁴⁹

You also, Amyclides [Hyacinthus, son of Amyclae], would have been set in the sky! if Phoebus [Apollon] had been given time which the cruel fates denied for you. But in a way you are immortal, too, though you have died. Always when warm spring drives winter out, and Aries (the Ram) succeeds to Pisces (watery Fish), you rise and blossom on the green turf.

Essentially concurring with Ovid, Philostratus the Elder recites the description of an ancient, Greek painting, which states in pertinent part that

[τὴν ὑάκινθον] ἀναφῶναι τῆς γῆς ἐπὶ μειρακίῳ καλῷ, καὶ θρηνεῖ αὐτὸ ἅμα τῷ ἥρι, γένεσιν, οἶμαι, παρ’ αὐτοῦ λαβοῦσα, ὅτε ἀπέθανε.¹⁵⁰

[the *hyacinth*] sprang from the earth in honor of a beautiful youth; and it laments him at the beginning of spring, doubtless because it was born from him when he died.

Moreover, Ovid echoes the Homeric sentiment [at A04] – “the snow which the East Wind thaws when the West Wind has strewn it” – a telling reference to the month of March, which is marked by the windy interaction between cold and warm air, as winter transitions to spring. According to Richer, the end of the *Hyakinthia* “probably coincided with the full moon” after the vernal equinox.¹⁵¹

Any attempt to tie this festival to the Attic, festival calendar results in its commencement during ἐκάτομβαιών (July/August), named for the sacrifice of 100 oxen at the Πᾶνᾶθῆναια ‘all Athenian’ festival (mid-August), held in honor of Athena, patron Goddess of Athens. However, if the classic, Athenian calendar¹⁵² is a factor, then the eighth month of Ἀνθεστηριών (February/March), which celebrates the flowering of spring, is a more fitting tribute to a prince who is struck down in the bloom of his youth.

It is believed that the *Hyakinthos* lasted three days. The first and third days of the festival were solemn affairs, dedicated to the mourning of Hyakinthos through sacrificial offerings to deceased loved ones. In

¹⁴⁵ Adonis (red anemone ‘windflower’, or poppy), the beloved of Aphrodite; Ajax (*delphinium ajacis*, or larkspur), son of Menelaus; Krokos (*crocus sativus*, or saffron flower), the beloved of Hermes; Narkissos (narcissus), a young man enamored with his reflection; Orchis (orchid), the son of a nymph and a satyr; Paeon (peony), a protégé of Asclepius. Cf. *pa-ja-wo-ne* [KN V- 52] > Παιών ‘healer, esp. physician of the gods’.

¹⁴⁶ “Where Have All the Flowers Gone?” by Malvina Reynolds, attributed by Pete Seeger in a video, *Live in Sweden* (1968).

¹⁴⁷ Petropoulou (2015) 178.

¹⁴⁸ Nobili (2014) 136.

¹⁴⁹ Ov. *Met.* 10.162-166 (trans. Brookes More, 1922).

¹⁵⁰ Philostr. *Maj. Im.* 1.23 (trans. Fairbanks).

¹⁵¹ Richer (2004) abstract.

¹⁵² Commencing in July/August, the months in the classic Athenian calendar were *Hekatombion*, *Metageitnion*, *Boedromion*, *Pyanepsion*, *Maimakterion*, *Poseidon*, *Gamelion*, *Anthesterion*, *Elaphebolion*, *Munychion*, *Thargelion*, and *Skirophorion*.

the spirit of abstinence, unlike other festivals of Apollo, the Spartans wore no garlands, sung no paeans at the sacrifices, and ate unleavened, sacrificial cakes.¹⁵³

Just as the fate of a deceased, loved one is beyond the power to heal, the fate of Hyakinthos was beyond the power of Παιών, Apollo, ‘healer, physician of the gods’:

ἀμφασία τὸν Φοῖβον ἔλεν τὸ σὸν ἄλγος ὀρῶντα.
δίξετο φάρμακα πάντα, σοφὰν δ' ἐπεμαίετο τέχνην,
χρῖεν δ' ἀμβροσία καὶ νέκταρι, χρῖεν ἅπασαν
ὠτειλάν: Μοίραισι δ' ἀναλθέα φάρμακα πάντα.¹⁵⁴

When he beheld [Hyakinthos'] agony, Phoibos [Apollon] was dumb.
He sought every remedy, he had recourse to cunning arts,
he anointed all the wound, anointed it with ambrosia and with nectar; but all remedies
are powerless to heal the wounds of Fate.

On the second day, following the sacrifice at the shrine of Apollo, the Spartans held the *kopis*, a ritual feast named for the single-edged, curved knife used in Greek warfare and ritual slaughter. Cf. the sickle-shaped blade of the Egyp. *ḥpš* or *kopesh*. This ritual feast comprised bread and cake, meat, broth, raw herbs, figs, and dessert.¹⁵⁵ The *kopis* was accompanied by paeans to Apollo, choruses, and national songs. Euripides describes “the revels of Hyakinthos in nightlong joy”.¹⁵⁶ Slaves were also allowed to participate in the festivities, which included horse races and concluded with a solemn procession of “splendidly adorned” maidens in wicker chariots.¹⁵⁷ Perhaps these women were delivering Apollo’s tunic:

ὕφαινουσι δὲ κατὰ ἔτος αἱ γυναῖκες τῷ Ἀπόλλωνι χιτῶνα τῷ ἐν Ἀμύκλαις, καὶ τὸ οἶκημα ἔνθα
ὕφαινουσι Χιτῶνα ὀνομάζουσιν.¹⁵⁸

Each year, the women weave a tunic for the Apollo at Amyclae, and they call Tunic the chamber in which they do their weaving.

For counter arguments regarding both the commencement and the duration of the *Hyakinthia*, I defer to Petropoulou, who argues that the festival occurred within the context of the *ἱερομηνία* (*hieromenia*), which marked a holiday commencing with a given, ‘sacred month’ and which generally lasted nine, perhaps ten, days.¹⁵⁹

At Amyklæ, devotions to the hero, Hyakinthos, were eventually conflated with the *hieromenia* honoring Apollo. “There is no doubt that the cult of Hyakinthos took root on the hill of Agia Kyriaki, before Apollo settled there,” states Petropoulou. “Calligas has argued that it was established sometime around or after c. 800 BC.” (See *ki*ko-ri-a-ka* at A-26) Moreover, “[t]he festival bearing the name of Hyakinthos is first attested in connection with the conspiracy of the Partheniai and the foundation of Taras, i.e. historical events of the late eighth c. BC, which are described by Antiochus of Syracuse.”¹⁶⁰ Conversely, the cult of Apollo “is not attested until the end of the seventh c. BC.”¹⁶¹ Petropoulou

¹⁵³ DGR (1890) s.v. Hyakinthia.

¹⁵⁴ Bion of Phlossa, *Fragmenta* 11 (Εἰς τὸν Ὑκινθὸν) (trans. Edmonds)

¹⁵⁵ DGR (1890) s.v. Hyakinthia.

¹⁵⁶ Eur. *Hel.* 1469-1470

¹⁵⁷ DGR (1890) s.v. Hyakinthia.

¹⁵⁸ *Paus.* 3.16.2.

¹⁵⁹ Petropoulou (2015) 167.

¹⁶⁰ *Ibid.* 153.

¹⁶¹ *Ibid.* 154.

discusses at length the possible, historic foundation of Hyakinthos' heroic status.

The centerpiece of the eventual sanctuary of Apollo was the presumed, earthen tomb of Hyakinthos. By the early, 6th century, Apollo was represented as a 15-meter (45 foot) cylinder featuring both a helmeted head and two arms holding a bow and a spear. In 550 BCE, Apollo's face was plated with a gift of gold from King Croesus of Lydia. Also in 550, Bathycles of Magnesia is said to have designed the "throne" of Apollo¹⁶² or of Hyakinthos "the Amyklaean".¹⁶³ It is said that Hyakinthos was buried in the pedestal, or altar, of the statue. At the *Hyakinthia*, before the sacrifice to Apollo, devotees made offerings, "as to a hero", through a bronze door on the left side. Carved in stone relief on the altar were numerous,

mythological scenes. In addition to Zeus, Hermes, and Dionysus, there were also Demeter, Aphrodite, Artemis, and Athena, some of whom were bearing to heaven Hyacinthus and his sister, Polyboea.¹⁶⁴

Although the *kopis* month would eventually be observed in honor of Apollo, it appears that the disc commemorates the early celebration of the *a-tu-pte-ki-jo* or *α-τυπητέος 'unbeaten' army during κοπιμαίς. Moreover, it is possible that the occasion of the disc predates the debut of the *Hyakinthia* by at least several centuries, perhaps as early as the 13th century BCE, the attested date of the Trojan War.

A-22

te-sa-me-ki-jo > *τε σημάτιον 'a small omen' to begin [the dance]. Cf. LB *sa-me-ti-jo* [KN K- 875]; *-ki-jo* for *-ti-jo* is like Thess. κῖς for τῖς.

A-23

te-ko²-ro *τε χορός 'the dance'. Cf. the reference to Χορὸς, the region around Sparta:

Σπαρτιάταις δὲ ἐπὶ τῆς ἀγορᾶς Πυθαέως τέ ἐστὶν καὶ Ἀπόλλωνος καὶ Ἀρτέμιδος καὶ Λητοῦς ἀγάλματα. Χορὸς δὲ οὗτος ὁ τόπος καλεῖται πᾶς, ὅτι ἐν ταῖς γυμνοπαιδίαις—ἐορτὴ δὲ εἴ τις ἄλλη καὶ αἱ γυμνοπαιδίαι διὰ σπουδῆς Λακεδαιμονίοις εἰσὶν—ἐν ταύταις οὖν οἱ ἔφηβοι χοροὺς ἰστᾶσι τῷ Ἀπόλλωνι.¹⁶⁵

On their market-place the Spartans have images of Apollo Pythaeus, of Artemis and of Leto. The whole of this region is called *Choros*, because, at the *Gymnopaediae*, a festival which the Lakedaemonians take more seriously than any other, the lads perform dances in honor of Apollo.

A-24

ku-ta-ki-jo > κτήσιος 'protector of one's property'.

In addition to the obvious mutilation or correction of the first sign in A-24, the nature of the correction of the third sign becomes more obvious with scrutiny: PHd *12, appears to have been stamped over the erased, second impression of *06.

<i>ku-ta-ta-jo</i> 18-06-06-02	A-24 error	LB <i>ku-te-ta-jo</i>	PY Ta 707	> κτητέος	'to be possessed'
<i>ku-ta-ki-jo</i> 18-06-12-02	A-24	LB <i>ku-ta-si-jo</i> LB <i>ku-ta-ti-jo</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-ja</i> LB <i>ku-te-se-jo</i>	KN Da 1394 KN Ga 419+ PY Ta 713+ PY Ta 707	> κτήσιος	'protector of one's property'

¹⁶² PECS (1976) s.v. Amyklai.

¹⁶³ Paus. 3.18.9.

¹⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, 3.19.3-4.

¹⁶⁵ *Ibid.* 3.11.9.

Essentially, the author prefers the active ‘possessor’ (*ku-ta-ki-jo*) to the passive ‘possessed’ (*ku-ta-ta-jo*)

In the LB sheep tablets at Pylos, hand 2 writes *ku-te-ta-jo*, *ku-te-se-jo* [PY Ta 707], and *ku-te-se-ja* [PY Ta 713], whereas, at Knossos, hand 117 writes *ku-ta-si-jo* [KN Da 1394] and hand 136 writes *ku-ta-ti-jo* [KN Ga 419+]. Cf. *ku-ta-to* > κτητός ‘that which may be acquired as property’, occurring approximately 70 times in the same tablets. In PHd, however, *ku-ta-ki-jo* appears to refer not to sheep, but rather to concubines who dance for their lord or master.

A-25

ke²-lu-ka > κάλυκη ‘any covering, husk, shell’, esp. the κάλυκος or κάλυξ ‘calyx’ of a flower. Cf. κάλυψις ‘covering’ and κάλύπτρα, Ion. κάλύπτρη ‘veil or headdress’ esp. a bridal veil, or perhaps veils worn by mistresses, concubines, or slaves performing the ritual, veil dance for their lord or master.

A-26

ki-ko-ri.ja-ka > The meaning of *κι Κυριακή is rather ambiguous. On the one hand, it is possibly a direct reference to Ἁγία Κυριακή ‘Haghia Kyriaki’, the hilltop sanctuary of *Amyklaios Apollo* at Amyklae (‘lord place’). or it is simply a reference to the regional κῶριακός ‘lord, master’.

Cross References: *ko-pi-me-e* [A-21]; *te-ko-ri.ja-ka* [B-29] and *ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-07]; *ko-ri.ja* [B-01] and *ko-ri.ja-ma* [A-29, B-11]. Regarding my hypothesis that κι is a proclitic version of the locative enclitic, see *The proposed presence of proclitic articles on the Phaistos disc*.

A-27

ke-pi-k^ho-ki-jo > Thus far, there is no plausible translation for this sign group. Nevertheless, cf. *ko-pi-no-ki-jo* [B-30].

A-28

de-ma-ma > *δέδμημα ‘concubines’. Cf. δέδμημαι ‘was overpowered’, pf. pass. of δαμάζω and δέμω ‘to overpower’, ‘to make subject to a husband’ (of maidens); δεδαμαμένος ‘overpowered’. Cf. *dame* (PIE *dem- ‘house, household’).

A-29 \ to A-30	34	45	29		12	40	24													
	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>	<i>ma</i>		<i>ki</i>	<i>pi</i>	<i>ta²</i>													
	*χόρευμα				κηπίδες															
	*χόρευμα κηπίδες “The dance ground was swept free of refuse.”																			

A-29

ko-ri.ja-ma > χόρευμα ‘choral dance’; alternately **ko-ri-ma* > κόρημα ‘sweepings, refuse’ or χώρημα ‘space, room’, perhaps as reference to the ‘dance ground’. Both interpretations support *ki-pi-ta²*; however, in context, the former seems the most plausible.

Cross References: *ko-ri.ja-ma*, [B-11], *ko-ri.ja* [B-01], and *ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-07].

A-30

ki-pi-ta² > κηπίδες ‘garden’ is a metaphor for κηπεύω ‘to cultivate’ or ‘to vivify, to freshen’. Choristers dance on the άλωνία or άλωνεία, from ἄλωσις ‘threshing floor’, which must be swept clean of refuse, or ‘freshened’; cf. *ke-po* > κῆπος, Dor. κᾶπος ‘garden, orchard, plantation’ [MY Ge 602+] and alt. *ke-pu* [KN Ap 639]. From the round ἄλωσις likely arises ‘hallowed (ground)’.

αἰσυμνῆται δὲ κριτοὶ ἐννέα πάντες ἀνέσταν δῆμιοι, οἱ κατ' ἀγῶνας ἐὺ πρήσσεσκον ἕκαστα, λείηναν δὲ χορόν, καλὸν δ' εὐρυναν ἀγῶνα. κῆρυξ δ' ἐγγύθεν ἦλθε φέρων φόρμιγγα λίγειαν Δημόδοκῳ: ὁ δ' ἔπειτα κί' ἐς μέσον: ἀμφὶ δὲ κοῦροι πρωθῆβαι ἴσταντο, δαήμονες ὀρχηθοῖο, πέπληγον δὲ χορὸν θεῖον ποσίν.¹⁶⁶

Then stood up masters of the lists, nine in all, men chosen from out the people, who in their gatherings were wont to order all things aright. They leveled a place for the dance, and marked out a fair wide ring, and the herald came near, bearing the clear-toned lyre for Demodocus. He then moved into the midst, and around him stood boys in the first bloom of youth, well skilled in the dance, and they smote the goodly dancing floor with their feet.

A-31 \ to B-04	18	01	13	12	02
	<i>ku</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>zu</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>
	> ἐξοχία				
	‘rising ground’				

A-31

ku-e-zu-ki-jo > ἐξοχία ‘eminence, piece of rising ground’. Perhaps this is a reference to the hillside, the site of the following ritual.

B-01 \ to B-04	07	45		25	23	34	29		07	23	25	06	02		07	18	39	30	09	
	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>		<i>mu</i>	<i>i</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>ma</i>		<i>ko</i>	<i>i</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>ta</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>ko</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>re</i>	<i>u²</i>	<i>ti</i>	
	*χορία			*μυιδέμα					*κοιτηταῖο					*κο(ρ)κυρεύτι						
	*χορία *μυιδέμα *κοιτηταῖο *κο(ρ)κυρεύτι																			
	“The hunt of the small, hibernating beast in its lair”																			

B-01

ko-ri.ja > *χορία > χορεία ‘circling motion’ such as a dance or the hunt. Perhaps the circular, dance tradition incorporated the ritual enactment of the hunt. The Κόρεια is ‘the festival of Κόρη’, a reference to the daughter of Demeter, or Persephone, the maiden-goddess of the hunt. As the embodiment of maidenhood, Kore was known as the goddess of spring.

Conversely, it should perhaps be noted that LB *ko-ri-jo*, in the context of the sheep tablets, likely pertains to κρῖός ‘a ram’s horn’ [KN Db 1267].

Cross References: *ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-07], *ki-ko-ri.ja-ka* [A-26], *te-ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-29]; and *ko-ri.ja-ma* [A-29 and B-11].

B-02

mu-i-de-ma > *μυιδέμας, from μυῖα ‘fly’, metaphor for ‘small’ + δέμας ‘bodily frame’. Cf. μικρὸς δέμας ‘small in stature’. A ‘small (beast)’, such as a hare, is implied. The hare is perhaps intended as a ritual sacrifice.

Cross Reference: *mu-i-de-ka* [B-09].

B-03

¹⁶⁶ Hom. *Od.* 8.258 (trans. A.T. Murray, 1919).

ko-i-te-ta-jo > *κοιτηταιο > κοιταῖος ‘lair of the wild beast’. Cf. κοιτᾶτήριον ‘bed chamber’.

B-04

ko-ku-re-u²-ti > *κοκυρεύτι > κοκυρεύεται ‘to be exhausted’. This sign group compels a comparison with the island of Κόρκυρα ‘Corcyra’.

B-05 \ to B-06	08	07	36	29	22		24	18	23	07										
	<i>ke²</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>ma</i>	<i>no</i>		<i>ta²</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>ko</i>										
	*κεκορημένος					*τά κτύπος														
	κεκορημένος *τά κτύπος “The crowd cheered in approval.”																			

B-05

(see also B-10)

ke²-ko-ra-ma-no > *κεκορημένος ‘to be satiated, satisfied’ [Theognis *Elegiae* 751] (s.v. κορέννῳμι). Cf. κεκορεσμένως ‘to satiety’; thus, *‘appreciation, approval’. Note that *ke-ke-me-na* / *ke-ke-me-no* [PY Ep 704] and *ke-ka-u-me-no* [PY Ta 641] may be associated with satiation (i.e. consumption) through burning and cutting (καίω ‘to burn’; κείρω ‘to cut, to shear’). Cf. κεκαρμένα and κεκαρμένος.

Cross Reference: *ke-ko-ra-ma* [B-13].

B-06

ta²-ku-tu-ko > *τά κτύκος for *τά κτύπος ‘the sound of many voices’, i.e. cheering and applauding.

Cross Reference: *te-ku-ko* [B-08].

B-07 \ to B-09	07	45	07		35	18	07		25	23	34	27								
	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>	<i>ko</i>		<i>te</i>	<i>ku</i>	<i>ko</i>		<i>mu</i>	<i>i</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>ka</i>								
	> κῶριακός			*τέ κοῦκκος				*μυιδέκα												
	κῶριακός *τέ κοῦκκος *μυιδέκα “The lord recited the decrees.”																			

B-07

ko-ri.ja-ko > *κῶριακός ‘lord, master’.

Cross References: *ki-ko-ri.ja-ka* [A-26] and *te-ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-29]; *ko-ri.ja* [B-01] and *ko-ri.ja-ma* [A-29 and B-11].

B-08

te-ku-ko > *τέ κόκκῳ, *τέ κοῦκκος ‘cuckoo’ = κόκκυξ ‘stammerer’. Cf. LB *ko-ku* [KN Dh 1240]. The *cuckoo* is known for its incessant repetition, which, in context, may serve as metaphor for ‘recitation’.

Cross Reference: *ta-ku-tu-ko* [B-06]

B-09

mu-i-de-ka > *μυιδέκα < μυῖα ‘fly’, metaphor for ‘small’ + either δεκάς ‘ten’ or δίκας ‘order, right’, the latter perhaps in the sense of temporary decrees as distinguished from established laws. I have ruled out δεχάς ‘receptacle’, a word coined by Pythagoras to explain δεκάς.

In context, the Athenian lord appears to be reciting the proposed decrees, for approval, to the δῆμος, or the assembly of citizens. According to Blackwell, the Greek ἐκκλησία ‘duly summoned assembly’ was generally known as the δῆμος (Doric δᾶμος), “the local village, the population generally, and the assembly

of citizens that governed the state.” The “three pillars of democracy” comprised the assembly, the Council of 500 [citizens], and the People’s Court.¹⁶⁷

The first, annual meeting of the Athenian Assembly occurred on the 11th day of Hekatombian¹⁶⁸, which, by some accounts, coincided with the *Hyakinthia*.

Ἐπιχειροτονία Νόμων

ἐπὶ δὲ τῆς πρώτης πρυτανείας τῆ ἑνδεκάτῃ ἐν τῷ δήμῳ, ἐπειδὴν εὐξήται ὁ κῆρυξ, ἐπιχειροτονίαν ποιεῖν τῶν νόμων, πρῶτον μὲν περὶ τῶν βουλευτικῶν, δεύτερον δὲ τῶν κοινῶν, εἶτα οἱ κεῖνται τοῖς ἐννέα ἄρχουσιν, εἶτα τῶν ἄλλων ἀρχῶν. ἡ δὲ χειροτονία ἔστω ἢ προτέρα, ὅτῳ δοκοῦσιν ἀρκεῖν οἱ νόμοι οἱ βουλευτικοί, ἢ δ’ ὑστέρα, ὅτῳ μὴ δοκοῦσιν: εἶτα τῶν κοινῶν κατὰ ταῦτά. τὴν δ’ ἐπιχειροτονίαν εἶναι τῶν νόμων κατὰ τοὺς νόμους τοὺς κειμένους.¹⁶⁹

Ratification of Laws

In the first presidency and on the eleventh day thereof, in the Assembly, the Herald having read prayers, a vote shall be taken on the laws, to wit, first upon laws respecting the Council, and secondly upon general statutes, and then upon statutes enacted for the nine Archons, and then upon laws affecting other authorities. Those who are content with the laws respecting the Council shall hold up their hands first, and then those who are not content; and in like manner in respect of general statutes. All voting upon laws shall be in accordance with laws already in force.

Decrees of the Assembly alternately began with “It seemed best to the Demos . . . ,” “It seemed best to the Council . . . ,” or “It seemed best to the Demos and the Council”¹⁷⁰

Cross References: *mu-i-de-ma* [B-02] and *ko-pi-me-e* [A-21].

B-10 \ to B-12	08	07	36	29	22
	<i>ke²</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>ma</i>	<i>no</i>
	κεκορημένος				
	“The assembly approved.”				

B-10

ke²-ko-ra-ma-no > κεκορημένος ‘to be satiated, satisfied’.¹⁷¹ Perhaps, more specifically, the assembly approved, with a show of hands, the decrees as read.

B-11 \ to B-12	07	45	29		13	08	29	
	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>	<i>ma</i>		<i>zu</i>	<i>ke²</i>	<i>ma</i>	
	*χόρευμα				*σχῆμα			
	*χόρευμα *σχῆμα ‘Dance figures’							

B-11

ko-ri.ja-ma > *χόρευμα ‘the choral dance’ or *κόρευμα = κορεία ‘maidenhood’. The question is whether, in context with *zu-ke²-ma*, *ko-ri.ja-ma* is a reference to the generic ‘dance’ or to a specific type of dance

¹⁶⁷ *Ibid.* 3-4.

¹⁶⁸ Blackwell (2003) 7.

¹⁶⁹ Dem. 24 20 (trans. A.T. Murray, 1939)

¹⁷⁰ Blackwell (2003) 7.

¹⁷¹ L&S 2nd s.v. κορέννῃμι.

that honors Κόρη, Dor. Κόρα ‘Koré’, the daughter of Demeter and the embodiment of maidenhood. An image of Koré is featured on a tripod at Amyklæe.¹⁷² For discussion about the role of girls at the Hyakinthia, see Nobili. Since dancing is incidental rather than central to the *Hyakinthia*, it is permitted little more than a passing reference.

Cross References: *ko-ri.ja-ma* [A-29]; *ko-ri.ja* [B-01] and *ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-07].

B-12

zu-ke²-ma > σχῆμα ‘form, shape, figure’.¹⁷³ Cf. *scheme*. In dancing, figures are thematic ‘gestures or postures’. Among the figures mentioned by Athenaeus are the *dipodismo*, the *epankonismos*, the *hekaterides*, the *kalathiskos*, the *kallabidēs*, the *skōpeuma*, the *skōps*, the *strobilus*, and the *thermaustris*. “And the *skōps* was a figure intended to represent people looking out from a distance, making an arch over their brows with their hand so as to shade their eyes.”¹⁷⁴

B-13 \ to B-22	08	07	36	29		01	27	09	02		33	39	32	35	06		01	33	29
	<i>ke²</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>ma</i>		<i>e</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>ti</i>	<i>jo</i>		<i>ke</i>	<i>re</i>	<i>pte</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>ta</i>		<i>e</i>	<i>ke</i>	<i>ma</i>
	*κεκόρημα					*ἑκάτιος					*Κρηπητήτα ?					ἄκημα			
	18	14	16		35	20	24	24	29		01	28	25	27		40	36	26	02
	<i>ku</i>	<i>ze</i>	<i>to</i>		<i>te</i>	<i>po</i>	<i>ta²</i>	<i>ta²</i>	<i>ma</i>		<i>e</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>mu</i>	<i>ka</i>		<i>pi</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>ko²</i>	<i>jo</i>
	*χάζετο					*τε ποτητάμα					*ιαμβύκη					*περιέχω			
	35	40	24	07		25	42	37	22										
	<i>te</i>	<i>pi</i>	<i>ta²</i>	<i>ko</i>		<i>mu</i>	<i>ri</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>no</i>	.									
	*τε πτᾶκός					μυρίνινος													
	*κεκόρημα				*ἑκάτιος	*Κρηπητήτα	*ἄκημα	*χάζετο	*τε ποτητάμα	*ιαμβύκη	*περιέχω	*τε							
				πτᾶκός μυρίνινος															
“appreciation				the winged <i>iambuka</i> was causing				the golden hare to rest”											

The syntax of this phrase is beyond me, but essentially it appears to mean “Applause for the Cretan visitor who soothes the myrrh-colored hare with his “winged *iambuka*”.

B-13

ke²-ko-ra-ma > *κεκόρημα > κεκόρημαι ‘satisfaction’, i.e. applause.

Cross Reference: *ke-ko-ra-ma-no* [B-05 and B-10].

B-14

e-ka-ti-jo > *ἑκάτιος < Dor. ἑκάτι for ἑκητι ‘because of, by virtue of’, personified in Ἐκάτη ‘*Hecate*, she who works her will’; thus, Ἐκάτῃος ‘of *Hecate*’. Cf. given name, Αἰκατερίνη ‘*Aikaterini*’ and *Katherine*. Cf., also, LB *a-ke-ti-jo* [PY An 209].

B-15

ke-re-pte-te-ta > Κρηπητήτα? Perhaps an awkward crasis for *Κρήπητήτά, from *ke-re-te* > Κρήτη ‘Crete’ + *pte-te-ta* < ποτητά ‘fowl, birds’, as a metaphor for ‘refugees, i.e. tourists, visitors’, or even ‘ex patriots.’ I favor the former, since the disc was discovered in Phaistos. Perhaps the disc’s author was one

¹⁷² Paus. 3.18.8 (trans. W.H.S. Jones and H.A. Ormerod, 1918)

¹⁷³ L&S 2nd s.v. σχῆμα for σχέμα.

¹⁷⁴ Ath. 14.26 (trans. C. D. Yonge, 1854)

such Cretan visitor to the annual Hyakinthia (Cret. Βακίνθια, φακίνθια, and φᾶκίνθια¹⁷⁵). Cf. Jap. H-series: 𐀀 *ha*, 𐀁 *hi*, 𐀂 *fu*, 𐀃 *he*, 𐀄 *ho*. The H is said to have been derived from the P sound.¹⁷⁶ Moreover, the pre-Greek, suffix -nth- is said to have a Cretan origin.¹⁷⁷

B-16

e-ke-ma > ἄκημα ‘cure, relief’. Hermes is said to have invented the lyre, which he then gave to Apollo, the god of music, poetry, and medicine. Thus, Apollo would play his lyre to promote healing and balance. Apollo is further associated with music through his son, Orpheus; with medicine through his son, Asklepios. A suggested etymology of Apollo is ἀπόλουσις ‘ablution’ or ritual washing.

B-17

ku-ze-to > χάζετο ‘rest’; perhaps *χάζετω ‘to relax, to soothe’, in context. Ep. impf. of χάζω ‘was causing to retire’. Cf. μίνυνθα δὲ χάζετο δουρός ‘scant rest was [Hector] giving his spear’ [Hom. Il. 11.539].

B-18

*te*po-ta²-ta²-ma* > *τε ποτητάμα ‘winged (things)’. Cf. τὰ ποτητά ‘birds’ [Hom. Od.12.62] and πότημα ‘flight’.

B-19

e-a-mu-ka > ἰαμβύκη, which is described with limited reference in the lexicon as ‘a musical instrument, distinct from the σαμβύκη.’¹⁷⁸ One may correctly deduce a relationship between ἰαμβύκη and ἴαμβος:

“The basic language of Greek iambic poetry reflects the authors’ local dialect, namely Eastern (and Central) Ionic in the fragments of Archilochus, Semonides, Hipponax, and Ananius. The language of iambus is however an artificial language; therefore, correspondences with the ‘spoken’ dialect occur along with distinctive features of the genre, such as vulgarisms, colloquialisms, foreign vocabulary, vivid expressions (often *ad hoc* skillful creations of the poets), borrowings or modifications of features of pres-tigious literary traditions.”¹⁷⁹

More information is found in Athenaeus, who cites Phillis of Delos:

λέγων οὕτως· ‘φοίνικες, πηκτίδες, μαγάδιδες, σαμβῦκαι, ἰαμβῦκαι, τρίγωνα, κλεψιάμβοι, σκινδαβοί, ἐννεάχορδα. ἐν οἷς γάρ, φησί, τοὺς ἰάμβους ἦδον ἰαμβύκας ἐκάλουν· ἐν οἷς παρελογίζοντο τὰ ἐν τοῖς μέτροις κλεψιάμβους. μαγάδιδας δὲ <ἐν οἷς> τὰ διὰ πασῶν καὶ πρὸς ἴσα τὰ μέρη τῶν ᾄδόντων ἤρμωσμένα’.¹⁸⁰

[H]is words are these: ‘There are the phoenix, the pectis, the magadis, the sambuca, the iambuca, the triangles, the clepsiambus, the scindapsus, and the nine-string.’ For, he says, ‘the lyre to which they sang iambs, they called the iambuca, and the instrument to which they sang them in such a manner as to vary the metre a little, they called the clepsiambus, while the magadis was an instrument uttering a sound an octave apart, and equally in tune for every portion of the singers.’

Whether “the lyre” may describe ‘any lyre’ or ‘a specific type of lyre’ is hard to say. However, there is no question that the lyre may be described as ‘winged’. Cf. *te-po-ta-ta-ma e-a-mu-ka* > *τε ποτητάμα ἰαμβύκη ‘the winged *iambuka*’ [B-18 to B-19].

¹⁷⁵ LSJ *sv.* Ὑᾶκίνθια and Ὑᾶκίνθιος

¹⁷⁶ Research and citation needed.

¹⁷⁷ Research and citation needed.

¹⁷⁸ L&S 2nd *s.v.* σαμβύκη.

¹⁷⁹ EGR (2014) 187.

¹⁸⁰ Athen. 14.363b. For a more thorough discussion about ancient instruments and Greek dance, see Athenaeus, *The Deipnosophists* 14.628-638.

In another reference,

γυναῖκας ἔχοντας ἱαμβύκην τε καὶ τρίγωνον.¹⁸¹

women are carrying iambukas and triangles,¹⁸² in an evening procession.

B-20

pi-ra-ko-jo > *περιέχω ‘to embrace; to encompass, to surround’, perhaps a reanalysis of περίοικος ‘dwelling round, i.e. neighboring’. The *perioikoi*, principally from Laconia and Messenia, were second-class citizens of Sparta, without political rights.

B-21

*te*pi-ta²-ko* > *τε πτᾶκός > gen. of πτάξ ‘shy, timid’; also πτώξ ‘cowering animal, i.e. hare’, gen. πτωκός.

B-22

mu-ri-na-no > μυρίνινος alt. σμύρνινος ‘myrrh’ was used in the unguent industry of ancient Greece. Note that Σμύρνα, alt. ζμύρνα, the “fragrance port”, for its commerce in myrrh, was located on the west coast of ancient Anatolia in the state of Lydia.

Consequently, oils made with myrrh were also used to describe color. Cf. παλλίον σμύρνινος ‘myrrh-colored’ or ‘golden brown’ Albrecht Dürer’s iconic painting of the “Young Hare” (1502) is characterized as golden brown. Thus, *te*pi-ta²-ko mu-ri-na-no* > *τε πτᾶκός μυρίνινος ‘the myrrh-colored hare’ i.e. ‘the golden-brown hare’ [B-21 to B-22].

Notes: Contemporary Cretans are reknowned lyracists. The Cretan *lyra*, however, has more in common with a lute rather than with the ‘winged *iambuka*’ used by iambists. Nevertheless, the accomplished, Cretan musicians seem able to use the traditional, winged lyre of the legendary Apollo and Orpheus to charm the ‘myrrh-colored hare’, to *lure* the hare from his bed, after which it was probably captured as an offering to the Amyklean Apollo. Quite possibly, the Cretan musicians provide the inspiration for these legends.

B-23 \ to B-24	18	01	13	07	15		33	39	01	13										
	<i>ku</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>zu</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>te²</i>		<i>ke</i>	<i>re</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>zu</i>										
	*ἔξοχότης						κράζω													
	*ἔξοχότης *κράζω. “There was a call for his eminence.”																			

B-23

ku-e-zu-ko-te² > *ἔξοχότης ‘your (i.e. his) eminence’ < ‘eminentia’, < ‘eminence, i.e. fame or recognized superiority, especially within a particular sphere or profession’, ‘an important, influential, or distinguished person’, such as *te*ko-ri.ja-ka* [B-29] or *ko-ri-ja-ko* [B-07].

Cross reference: *ku*e-zu-ki-jo* [A-31].

B-24

ke-re-e-zu > *κράζω ‘to call for, to clamor for’. Cf. LB *ke-re-za* [PY Aa 762+].

¹⁸¹ Eup. 139

¹⁸² L&S 2nd s.v. τρίγωνος ‘a musical instrument of triangular form, somewhat like a harp, with strings of equal thickness but unequal lengths’.

B-25 \ to B-30	43	18	23	16		12	20	24	33		27	25	22		05	23	37	02			
	a^2	<i>ku</i>	<i>tu</i>	<i>to</i>		<i>ki</i>	<i>po</i>	ta^2	<i>ke</i>		<i>ka</i>	<i>mu</i>	<i>no</i>		<i>u</i>	<i>ta</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>jo</i>			
	ἀκάτῤῥτος					*κι πόταγε					κάμνον					*Ἀθηναῖος					
	35	07	45	27		07	40	22	12	02											
	<i>te</i>	<i>ko</i>	<i>ri.ja</i>	<i>ka</i>		<i>ko</i>	<i>pi</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>ki</i>	<i>jo</i>											
	*τε κυριακή					*κοφινοκιος															
	ἀκάτῤῥτος *κι πόταγε κάμνον *Ἀθηναῖος *τε κυριακή *κοφινοκιος. “A new pair of shoes was brought to the embattled, Athenian lord to pay a debt.”																				

****Note:** I disagree with the original syntax, which places a thorn at *u-ta-na-jo* [B-28]; nevertheless, I am open to any argument for the original syntax.

B-25

a^2 -*ku-tu-to* > ἀκάτῤῥτος ‘not stitched, not repaired, *i.e.* new’ (of shoes). Cf. νεο-κάτῤῥτος ‘freshly sewn’. Probably leather shoes or boots more suited for battle, versus the ἐμβάδες ‘felt shoes’. Cf. αἱ Ἀμύκλαι ‘shoes worn by Amyclaeans’ vs. αἱ Λακωνικά (sub. ἐμβάδες ‘felt shoe’), *Laconian shoes*, worn by men.

B-26

ki-po-ta^2-ke > *κι πόταγε < Dor. for πρόσαγε ‘brought to’.

B-27

ka-mu-no > κάμνον ‘to be hardpressed in battle or contest’, *i.e.* *‘embattled’.

B-28

u-tu-na-jo > *Ἀθηναῖος or Ἀθηναῖος ‘an Athenian’. Cf. LB *u-ta-ni-jo* [KN B- 807]. Following the peace treaty of Nicias, which ended the first half of the Peloponnesian War (ca. 421 BCE), the Athenians and the Lacedaemonians create an alliance. Thus, the presence of the Athenians at the Hyakinthos is provided by the terms of this alliance, per Thucydides:

‘κατὰ τάδε ξύμμαχοι ἔσονται Λακεδαιμόνιοι <καὶ Ἀθηναῖοι> πενήκοντα ἔτη. ἦν [δέ] τινες ἴωσιν ἐς τὴν γῆν πολέμοι τὴν Λακεδαιμονίων καὶ κακῶς ποιῶσι Λακεδαιμονίους, ὠφελεῖν Ἀθηναίους Λακεδαιμονίους τρόπῳ ὁποῖω ἂν δύνωνται ἰσχυροτάτῳ κατὰ τὸ δυνατόν.’¹⁸³

The Lacedaemonians shall be confederates with the Athenians for fifty years. If any enemy invade the territory of the Lacedaemonians and do the Lacedaemonians any harm, the Athenians shall aid the Lacedaemonians against them in the strongest manner they can possibly;

Likewise, the Lacedaemonians shall aid the Athenians:

ἀνανεοῦσθαι δὲ <τὸν ὄρκον> κατ’ ἐνιαυτὸν Λακεδαιμονίους μὲν ἰόντας ἐς Ἀθήνας πρὸς τὰ Διονύσια, Ἀθηναίους δὲ ἰόντας ἐς Λακεδαίμονα πρὸς τὰ Ὑακίνθια. στήλην δὲ ἑκατέρους στήσαι, τὴν μὲν ἐν Λακεδαίμονι παρ’ Ἀπόλλωνι ἐν Ἀμυκλαίῳ, τὴν δὲ ἐν Ἀθήναις ἐν πόλει παρ’ Ἀθηνᾶ. ἦν

¹⁸³ Thuc. 5.23, I (trans. Thomas Hobbes, 1843)

δέ τι δοκῆ Λακεδαιμονίοις καὶ Ἀθηναίοις προσθεῖναι καὶ ἀφελεῖν περὶ τῆς ξυμμαχίας, ὅτι ἂν δοκῆ, εὖορκον ἀμφοτέροις εἶναι.¹⁸⁴

Every year the Lacedaemonians shall go to Athens at the Dionysia and renew the oath, and the Athenians shall go to Lacedaemon at the Hyacinthia and renew the oath. Both parties shall erect pillars, one in Lacedaemon at the temple of Apollo in Amyclae, another at Athens in the Acropolis at the temple of Athenè.

Thus, the “similarities between Athenian Dionysia and Laconia Hyakinthia”¹⁸⁵ are explained.

B-29

te-ko-ri.ja.ka > *τε κυριακή ‘of or for the lord’ < κῶριακός ‘of or for an owner or master’.

Cross References: *ki-ko-ri.ja-ka* [A-26] and *ko-ri.ja-ko* [B-07]; *ko-ri.ja* [B-01] and *ko-ri.ja-ma* [A-29 and B-11].

B-30

ko-pi-no-ki-jo > κόφινος ‘basket’ + kios *‘offering’? Cf. κουφίζω ‘to lighten a load, to cancel a debt’ < κοῦφος ‘light, nimble’. Cf. also LB *ko-pi-na* [PY Ep 613].

Conclusion

With this decipherment, I have toiled very hard to present a three-dimensional view of a much-celebrated, Greek festival in its early days. Ultimately, a document that expands the holograph of Greek history is far more compelling than a hymn to a goddess, a celestial map or a game board, which simply cannot compete with the mundane excitement of the Achaean *kopis* month *cum* Hyakinthia.

We may agree that, although the dating of the Phaistos disc is circumstantial rather than actual, the context of the present decipherment, if attested, raises more questions than it answers. Nevertheless, one era emerges as an historic possibility. The eighth century BCE witnessed the rise of the supremacy of the Spartan army, the conquest of Amyklae at Haghia Kyriaki, and the establishment of the cult of Hyakinthos. I am not arguing for or against this historic context but merely making an observation.

If an attested decipherment challenges the policy against destructive, archeometric analysis, I suggest that such a challenge be postponed by simply beginning with a visual comparison among the clays of the Phaistos disc, the five LB tablets recovered in Haghia Vasileios (HV), and the excavated, Laconian pottery of the Evrotas valley. Does Haghia Kyriaki yield further artifacts that can offer comparative evidence? If analysis of these clays should ultimately negate an association, I shall humbly withdraw my hypothesis regarding a Laconian source for the clay of the Phaistos disc but will continue to stand behind my decipherment, with an open question about location and context.

Finally, I recognize that my translation syntax is awkward. Therefore, I invite debate and suggestions for refinements to both ancient-Greek syntax and historical context.

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January 6, 2023

¹⁸⁴ *Ibid.* IV.

¹⁸⁵ Richer (2004) *Abstract*.

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